

Ionospheric disturbance during strong Geomagnetic storms

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ABSTRACT

IONOSPHERIC DISTURBANCE DURING STRONG GEOMAGNETIC STORMS

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Helwan University,2011

The Earth's ionosphere is a region of the upper atmosphere that is a partially ionized gas. It extends from the mesosphere and through the thermosphere to altitudes ~ 1000 km where it ultimately merges with the magnetosphere. The strong coupling of the ionosphere to the dense regions below and the solar-driven magnetosphere above make it the most variable component of the atmosphere. Sources of ionospheric variability or "weather" originate from solar and geomagnetic activity and meteorological influences.

One motivation for studying the ionosphere is to improve techniques to predict ionospheric weather that affects space-borne and ground-based technological systems used for communication, navigation, surveillance and basic research. Geomagnetic storms can be particularly disruptive, leading to significant satellite systems failures. Even quiet-time disturbances, such as scintillation and spread- F events, can impact high frequency radio communications, especially in the equatorial and high-latitude regions.

The main objective of this thesis is to measure and monitor the ionospheric Total Electron Content (TEC) and studying the ionospheric phenomenas over Egypt during quite and disturbed days, using space-based radio navigation systems. Two dual frequency receivers were used in this study: Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver (CIDR) using UHF/VHF radio beacons on board of Low-Earth-Orbit satellites, and Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver. These receivers were installed

ABSTRACT

successively at Helwan, Egypt (Geographic coordinates: 29.86° N, 31.32° E) between the years 2008 and 2009.

This thesis presents observations for the daily Total Electron Content (TEC) variation and the northern hump of the Equatorial Ionization Anomaly (EIA) and their diurnal behaviors at all local times during geomagnetically quiet/disturbed times. Four geomagnetic storms were selected to be investigated, studying their effects on the variability of the ionosphere. Two storms – one in 2008 and another in 2009 – were monitored by CIDR system while the other two storms – during 2010 – were monitored by GPS-receiver. A substorm case study is also presented, showing the correlation between substorm and geomagnetic pulsation. In addition, an annual survey for the ionospheric TEC, during 2010, was achieved in order to showing the seasonal variation.

The vertical $E \times B$ drift velocity reversal in equatorial latitude and the downward plasma flow from greater heights were believed to be the main sources for the Night-Time TEC Enhancement at mid latitudes. These mid-latitude nighttime peaks in TEC appearing before midnight have been investigated also with satellite data reduced to TEC values.

Most of these studies were supported by a geomagnetic data from the Magnetic Data Acquisition System's (MAGDAS) installed at Fayum (Geographic coordinates: 29.30° N, 30.88° E) and Aswan (Geographic coordinates: 23.59° N, 32.51° E), Egypt.

Declaration

This work contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any university or other tertiary institution and, to the best of my knowledge and belief, contains no material previously published or written by another person, except where due reference has been made in the text.

I give consent to this copy of my thesis, when deposited in the Helwan University, being available for loan and photocopying.

Signature _____

Date _____

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7 Nov, 2010.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
AE	Auroral Electrojet
AGW	Atmospheric Gravity Waves
AS	Anti-Spoofing
ASCII	American Standard Code for information Inerchange
ASTEC	Absolute Slant Total Electron Content
BPS	Boundary Plasma Sheet
C/A-Code	Coarse/Acquisition Code
CC	Correlation Count
CI	Covington Index
CIDR	Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CODE	Center for Orbit Determination in Europe
CPS	Central Plasma Sheet
CS	Commercial Service
DCB	Differential Code Bias
DCP	Differential Carrier Phase
DoD	Department of Defense
DoT	Department of Transport
DPB	Differential Phase Bias
DPR	Differential PseudoRange,
Dst index	Disturbed storm time index
EA	Equatorial Anomaly
EEJ	Equatorial ElectroJet

EUV	Extreme Ultra-Violet
FAC	Field-Aligned Current
GEO	GEostationary orbit satellite
GLONASS	GLObal NAvigation Satellite System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRT	Gravitational Rayleigh–Taylor mechanism
GSM	Geocentric Solar Magnetospheric - coordinates
IAG	International Association for Geodesy
IAGA	International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy
ICME	Interplanetary CME
IDL	Interactive Data Language
IGS	International GNSS Service
IMF	Interplanetary Magnetic Field
IONEX	IONosphere map EXchange format
IP or IPP	Ionospheric Pierce Point
ITNE	Ionospheric Tomography Network in Egypt
Lat	Latitude
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LOS	Line Of Sight
MAGDAS	MAGnetic Data Acquisition System
MCS	Master Control Station
MEO	Medium-Earth-Orbit
MLat	Magnetic Latitude
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NAVSTAR	Navigation System with Time and Ranging

NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
NIMS	Navy Ionospheric Monitoring Satellites
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
Pc	pulsations continuous
P-Code	precision code
PE	phase error
Pi	pulsations irregular
PPS	Precise Positioning Service
PRN	pseudorandom noise
PRS	Public Regulated Service
QZSS	Quasi-Zenith Satellite System
RF	Radio Frequency
RINEX	Receiver INdependent EXchange format
RMS	Root-Mean-Squared
SA	Selective Availability
SCINDA	Scintillation Network and Decision Aid
SCORE	Self-Calibration Of pseudorange Error
SCW	Substorm Current Wedge
SEP	Solar Energetic Pericles
SNR	signal to noise ratio
SOHO	Solar & Heliospheric Observatory
SPS	Standard Positioning Service
SSC	sudden storm commencement
STD	STandard Deviation
STEC	Slant Total Electron Content
SW	Solar wind
SWMC	Space Weather Monitoring Center

TAD	Traveling Atmospheric Disturbances
TEC	Total Electron Content
TECU	Total Electron Content Unit
TID	Traveling Ionospheric Disturbances
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
ULF	Ultra-Low Frequency
UT	Universal Time
UV	Ultra-Violet
VHF	Very High Frequency
VTEC	Vertical Total Electron Content

1 INTRODUCTION

The story begins in December 10, 1901, when Marconi demonstrated transatlantic communication by receiving a signal in St. John's Newfoundland that had been sent from Cornwall, England. It had been assumed that electromagnetic radiation transmitted into the atmosphere travelled in straight lines. If there were no objects in the path, the maximum distance would be determined by the transmitter and receiver antenna heights and by the curvature of the Earth, this distance is often called the *Line-of-Sight* (LOS) distance. In Marconi's transatlantic demonstration, the radio waves bend around the Earth's curvature so that the communication signals could be heard over such an unprecedented distance.

In 1902, Oliver Heaviside and Arthur Kennelly each independently proposed that a conducting layer existed in the upper atmosphere that would allow a transmitted electromagnetic signal to be reflected back toward the Earth. In 1902, Lodge was probably the first to suggest that the reflecting properties of the conducting layer are due to free electrons produced by the action of solar radiation. Until 1926 this conducting layer of the atmosphere was named the *Heaviside layer* or *Appleton layer*. In 1926 the British National Committee for radiotelegraphy suggested a non-personal name for the conducting layer of the atmosphere and the name *ionosphere* came into common use about 1932 (Hargreaves, 1992). The ionosphere is that part of the upper atmosphere comprising free electrons that occur with a sufficient

density to have an appreciable influence on the propagation of radio frequency electromagnetic waves.

In 1924, Edward Appleton and others demonstrated the existence of the ionosphere by studying the reflections of radio waves from the atmosphere, which is the basic idea used in the *ionosonde** invention.

The ionosphere extends from about 80 km to many hundreds kilometers in altitude. It is important for its effects on radio waves and so transmissions of electromagnetic waves by satellite-based navigation systems such as Global Positioning System (GPS) are affected as they pass through the ionosphere. Such radio signals are slowed down as they propagate through the ionosphere, causing an increase in the propagation time of a signal when compared to the time of propagation through free space. This effect, called the propagation delay. The ionosphere is a dispersive medium, and since the dispersion changes with frequency in a known way, a dual frequency receiver can be used to effectively eliminate this propagation delay caused by the ionosphere. In fact the signal propagation delay is proportional to the line integral of the free electron distribution along the path of the signal from the satellite transmitter to the receiver. As explained in this thesis, this information can be used to determine the electron density distribution in the Earth's ionosphere and plasmasphere and so can be used not only to correct for the propagation delay satellite signals, but also to study the behavior of the ionosphere and magnetosphere. For example, changes occurring during ionospheric storms, ion composition changes, and space-weather effects on telecommunications are just a few of the phenomena that can be studied.

* An ionosonde is a radar that emits short bursts of radio waves at increasingly higher frequencies in the MF and HF bands. Each frequency is reflected at a particular value of electron density. By measuring the round trip time (ground to ionosphere and back) of each burst, it is possible to estimate the vertical profile of electron density occurring in the ionosphere. Typically, this is from about 100 km altitude to 250 or 450 km.

During the years, a variety of instruments have been employed to take direct measurements of the electron density of the ionosphere and plasmasphere. However, so far there is no universal method; each type has advantages as well as disadvantages.

For example, the pulsed HF ionosonde is not able to take measurements above the peak of the F-region. Similarly the incoherent radar techniques are limited to the scattering point between the transmitter and receiver radars. Consequently, TEC measurements, made using trans-ionospheric radio signals, are one of the most important methods of investigating the Earth's ionosphere and plasmasphere. However, by themselves, a series of TEC measurements are just a collection of line integrals of the free electron density.

A prime aim of this research has been to produce temporal and spatial profiles for the variation of the ionosphere and to study the response of the ionosphere to geomagnetic storms, over Egypt. Two satellite-based systems were utilized in this work: Global Positioning System (GPS) with two radio signals in the GHz range, and Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver (CIDR) system based on Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites with two radio signals in the MHz range.

In this chapter, the motivation of this work will be described. This will be followed by a literature review. The chapter will be concluded by the contribution of the dissertation and a brief outline of each subsequent chapter.

1.1 Motivation of the Research

The signals of a GPS satellite (L-band) – at 20,000 *km* altitude- must travel through the earth's ionosphere on their way to GPS receivers on or near the

earth's surface. A *carrier phase advance* and a *pseudorange group delay* are imposed on these signals by the ionosphere. Whereas this ionospheric effect may be considered a nuisance by most GPS users, they will provide the ionospheric community with an opportunity to use GPS as a tool to better understand the plasma surrounding the earth. If we have dual frequency GPS receivers, then the ionospheric effect can be almost totally accounted for by taking advantage of the ionosphere's dispersive nature.

The ionosphere is a dispersive medium for radio waves implying that the refractive index is a function of the radio waves' frequency, the electron density, and to a minor degree, the intensity of the earth's magnetic field.

After integrating the phase and group refractive indices along the path of the GPS signal we will obtain an observing range between the satellite and the receiver which is different from the true geometric range by the amount that we call ionospheric error. This error is negative for the carrier phase (phase is advanced; that is, the measured range is shorter than the geometric range), and positive for the pseudorange (a group delay; that is, the measured range is longer than the geometric range). The phase advance and the group delay are of equal size but opposite sign. To an excellent first order approximation, ionospheric error is proportional to the integrated electron density along the signal path (total electron content, TEC) and inversely proportional to the square of the carrier phase frequency (Langley, 1996). So, GPS can provide a unique tool to study the ionosphere. In November 2009, a Scintillation Network and Decision Aid (SCINDA) system was installed successfully at Helwan, Egypt (29.86° N, 31.32° E). This system monitor the ionosphere using signals transmitted from GPS satellites.

By a similar way, signal transmitted from a Low-Earth-Orbit (LEO) satellites were observed by a Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receivers (CIDRs) located at Helwan, Egypt (29.86° N, 31.32° E). This system was installed during summer 2008. The TEC measurements associated with Low-Earth-Orbit (LEO) radio beacons are quite different from GPS-based TEC measurements. These LEO beacons operate in the VHF (150 MHz) and UHF (400 MHz) bandwidth. The actual measurements are the frequency Doppler shift in the UHF and VHF radio channels.

1.2 Literature Overview

In this section, the history of the ionosphere-related work that has been done at the Space Weather Monitoring Center (SWMC) at faculty of science, Helwan University will be briefly summarized. Thus far, it will be followed by a summary of the work done elsewhere in the context of the research outlined in this dissertation.

1.2.1 Previous Ionospheric Work at SWMC

The Space Weather Monitoring Center at the University of Helwan in Egypt has been involved in ionosphere-related research since the middle of the 2008s. The first early CIDR (Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver) related ionospheric work was concentrated on studying the spatial variation of the ionosphere and its response to minor geomagnetic storms (A.Mahrous et al., 2010).

The ionosphere group at SWMC begins its activity by a theoretical basic about the plasma physics especially those related to the work of ionosphere. Experimental part was done to support the theoretical one. Parallel to this work, simulation software was investigated in order to combine the three main parts (theoretical, experimental and simulated) of the ionosphere work.

This thesis provides the experimental work together with a part from the theoretical work, considers the early GPS-related ionospheric work concentrated on monitoring the ionosphere at SWMC in addition to the comparing with that of CIDR.

1.2.2 Previous Work Elsewhere

The literature of relevance to this research is large. So, the studies that are closely related to this thesis will be concentrated on.

The first study of an ionospheric storm using radio frequency signals was made by Anderson, 1928, after which a tremendous effort has been made to classify and interpret the observed ionospheric disturbance effects (e.g., Essex et al., 1981; Fuller-Rowell et al., 1990; Buonsanto et al., 1990; Prolss et al., 1991). A quantity of papers has been devoted to study of ionospheric response to geomagnetic storms (Foster, 1993; Ho et al., 1996; Coster et al., 2001; Afraimovich et al., 2002, 2006; Foster and Rideout, 2005; Mannucci et al., 2005).

In 1935, Appleton and Ingram categorized the effects of geomagnetic storms on the F2-region (at a height of about 300 km, see Rishbeth and Garriott, 1969) ionosphere.

Berkner et al. (1939) and Berkner and Seaton (1940) discovered positive storm effects (increases of electron density during storms at lower latitudes), Appleton and Ingram (1935) also mentioned this phenomenon.

The concept of a substorm was first elucidated by a Japanese graduate student, Shun-ichi Akasofu (Akasofu, 1964) based on a large number of auroral images collected by ground-based all-sky cameras during IGY era (1957-1958). Yumoto et al. (2001) proposed also the excitation and propagation mechanisms of the substorm associated global Pi2 pulsations.

1.3 Contribution of the Research

Two space-based systems (GPS-SCINDA and LEO-CIDR) were used to independently produce in ionospheric Total Electron Content (TEC) profiles. These systems were located at the Space Weather Monitoring Center SWMC, Helwan University, EGYPT.

The contribution of my dissertation is as follows: The GPS-TEC technique provides a way to produce a temporal variation profiles for the ionospheric TEC, while the CIDR-TEC technique provides an alternative way to produce a spatial variation profiles for the ionospheric TEC.

By using these systems, an ionospheric observation is carried out during quite days, investigating the diurnal, seasonal and latitudinal variations. These observations were followed by a studying of the ionospheric TEC, as a key parameter, during a number of geomagnetic storms ranging from minor to sever storms. The TEC disturbances and perturbations during these geomagnetic storms were investigated and interpreted in the basis of magnetospheric and geomagnetic conditions. The ionospheric storms coincidence with the observed geomagnetic storms have been monitored and investigated as well, showing its positive and negative phases.

Also, an observed pulsations (Pi2) in the Earth's magnetic field, observed at Aswan magnetometer station (23.59° N, 32.51° E), were coincidence with a substorm case study followed one of the investigated storms.

Finally, an earlier survey for the ionospheric TEC over EGYPT during the year 2010 is included within the pages of this thesis.

This thesis was written to be a reference guide to other researchers who will supply and conduct this strategic field by their knowledge and efforts.

1.4 Outline of the Dissertation

This thesis consists of 6 chapters, Chapter 1 is an introduction. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the physics related to the Earth's atmosphere and the Sun. A brief introduction to the Earth's magnetic field, magnetic pulsation and magnetic activity indexes are given, since the magnetic field plays a central role in the transport processes in the ionosphere. The concepts of the magnetosphere, geomagnetic storms and substorms were included also.

In Chapter 3, the theory of the Earth's ionosphere formation is explained. Three principal photochemical processes: production, recombination and transport of ions and electrons involving in the ionospheric plasma continuity and momentum equations are reviewed. The combination of these three processes explains the temporal and spatial variation of the electron density in the ionosphere. The last part of this chapter also discusses ionospheric storms, variability and ionospheric phenomena.

Chapter 4 is devoted to the description of the experimental instruments, data, and software packages that have been used in this thesis. Background history of both LEO and GPS satellites and their data format are briefly described.

Chapter 5 gives the ionosphere's effects upon the satellite signals propagate within it. The TEC extraction methods used in both GPS-SCINDA and LEO-CIDR systems were discussed in details, giving samples for the fundamental ionosphere parameters observed by SCINDA and CIDR.

Finally in Chapter 6, most interesting observations for the response of the ionosphere to magnetic storm over the Egyptian region, which extends from equatorial regions to mid latitude regions, are presented. Four geomagnetic storms - from the years 2008, 2009 and 2010 - were investigated with one case of a substorm. Many ionospheric phenomena have been studied also

during the periods of these storms. The conclusions of this thesis are summarized and recommendations are given for future research.

2

The Earth's Atmosphere, Sun, and Geomagnetism

This chapter deals with the physical background of the Earth's atmosphere, the geomagnetism and the Sun. These are the three components that involved in the formation of the Earth's ionosphere. Understanding the features of these components is essential to an understanding of the formation of the Earth's ionosphere which will be discussed in the next chapter.

2.1. The Earth's Atmosphere

The Earth's atmosphere is a mixture of different gases and small particles. The atmosphere can roughly be defined as the region from sea level to about 1000 km altitude around the Earth, where neutral gases can be detected, although traces of atmospheric gases have been detected far into space. About 99% of the mass of the atmosphere lies below about 30 km altitude. Above 80 km altitude, the atmosphere contains ionized molecules and free electrons.

The Earth's atmosphere can be coarsely subdivided in several concentric spherical layers based on different characteristic features such as temperature, ionization, and propagation. Based on the vertical variation of temperature, the Earth's atmosphere is subdivided into four layers: *troposphere* (from sea level to about 10 km), *stratosphere* (from 10 km to about 50 km), *mesosphere* (from 50 km to about 80 km) and *thermosphere* (from 80 km to about 400 km). In general, the temperature in the troposphere decrease with height and increases in the stratosphere, but decreases again in the mesosphere. In the thermosphere the temperature increases again.

Above the thermosphere, the temperature is constant, is the *exosphere* which gradually merges into space. The exosphere is the uppermost layer of the Earth' atmosphere that the particles can escape to space. The temperature variation through the atmosphere layers is shown in figure 2.1.

With respect to signal propagation, the atmosphere is subdivided into two main layers of *troposphere* (also referred to as neutral atmosphere) and *ionosphere*. The troposphere, the lower part of the atmosphere, extends from

the sea level to about 40 km which is non-dispersive medium (the propagation delay is not frequency dependent), see figure 2.1. In the troposphere, signal propagation depends mainly on the water vapor content and on temperature.

The ionosphere, the upper part of Earth's atmosphere, is a dispersive medium which starts about 80 km altitude. In the ionosphere, signal propagation is mainly affected by the free charged particles.

The two most abundant atmospheric gases are Nitrogen (78% by volume) and Oxygen (21% by volume), and together they compose over 99% of the lower atmosphere. The remaining 1% of the atmospheric gases includes the noble gases (Argon, Neon, Helium, Krypton and Xenon) and so-called greenhouse gases (Carbon Dioxide, Methane, Nitrous oxide and Water vapor). Hydrogen is also present in the atmosphere, but because it is so light, over time much of it has escaped the Earth's gravity into space.

Figure 2.1: Subdivision of the Earth's atmosphere.

2.1.1. Pressure, temperature and density variations

The atmosphere is not physically uniform and has significant variations in temperature and pressure with altitude. A planet is capable of keeping its atmosphere by means of the gravitational force. On the other hand, the

thermal motion of the molecules prevents the atmosphere from collapsing into a thin sheet on the surface of the planet.

Let us consider a spherically symmetric atmosphere with a single molecular species around a planet with a radius R and a mass M . The gravitational acceleration at a distance r from the center of the planet is

$$\mathbf{g} = -G \frac{M}{r^2} \mathbf{e}_r = -G \frac{M}{R^2} \frac{R^2}{r^2} \mathbf{e}_r = -g_0 \frac{R^2}{r^2} \mathbf{e}_r \quad (2.1)$$

Here G is the gravitational constant, g_0 is the acceleration of gravity on the surface of the planet and \mathbf{e}_r is the radial unit vector. In a static atmosphere the momentum equation gives:

$$m\mathbf{ng} = \nabla p \quad (2.2)$$

Where m is the molecular mass and n the molecular number density. In the case of spherical symmetry, $\nabla p = dp/dr \mathbf{e}_r$. Hence the momentum equation reads

$$\frac{dp}{dr} = -mng_0 \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad (2.3)$$

From the ideal gas law, $n = p/(K_B T)$, so that

$$\frac{1}{p} \frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{mg_0}{k_B T} \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad (2.4)$$

This gives the height profile of the atmospheric pressure

$$p = p_0 \exp \left[-\int_R^r \frac{mg_0}{k_B T(r)} \frac{R^2}{r^2} dr \right] \quad (2.5)$$

This shows that the pressure profile can only be calculated, if the temperature profile is known. The temperature profile depends on the absorption of the incident radiation, heat conduction and thermal radiation of the heated atmosphere. Hence the determination of the state of a static atmosphere is a complicated problem. If the temperature profile is known, eq. (2.5) allows the determination of the pressure profile.

The simplest assumption is an isothermal atmosphere. If T is constant, eq. (2.5) gives:

$$p = p_0 \exp \left[-\frac{mg_0 R}{k_B T} \left(1 - \frac{R}{r} \right) \right] \quad (2.6)$$

Since $p = nk_B T$ and $p_0 = n_0 k_B T$, we also get

$$n = n_0 \exp \left[-\frac{mg_0 R}{k_B T} \left(1 - \frac{R}{r} \right) \right] \quad (2.7)$$

Obviously, $n = n_0$ when $r = R$, but when $r \rightarrow \infty$, $n \rightarrow n_0 \exp[-mg_0 R / (K_B T)]$. This would seem to suggest that the atmospheric mass could be infinite and it could be supported by +the pressure. This is unrealistic, of course, and it means that the assumption of an isothermal atmosphere is fundamentally unrealistic.

A reason for this probably is that the ideal gas law breaks down when the gas is so dilute that collisions between molecules becomes infrequent. Notice that a sufficient temperature decrease with distance can make the integral in eq. (2.5) approach zero when the distance approaches infinity. This is what actually happens at great heights in the atmosphere of the Earth.

Close to the surface of the planet we can take $r \approx R$. Using the notation $z = r - R$ for the height above the ground level, eq. (2.5) becomes:

$$p = p_0 \exp \left[-\int_0^z \frac{mg_0}{k_B T(z)} dz \right]$$

$$p = p_0 \exp \left[-\int_0^z \frac{dz}{H(z)} \right] \quad (2.8)$$

and

$$n = n_0 \frac{T_0}{T(z)} \exp \left[-\int_0^z \frac{dz}{H(z)} \right] \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$H = \frac{k_B T(z)}{mg_0} \quad (2.10)$$

is the scale height.

In the isothermal atmosphere:

$$p = p_0 \exp \left(-\frac{z}{H} \right) \quad (2.11)$$

and

$$n = n_0 \exp \left(-\frac{z}{H} \right) \quad (2.12)$$

where the scale height is constant. In the isothermal atmosphere both pressure and density decrease by the factor $1/e$ within one scale height.

2.1.2. Atmospheric temperature

According to the first law of thermodynamics (energy conservation),

$$du = d'q + d'w \quad (2.13)$$

where du is the change of internal energy (exact differential), $d'q$ and $d'w$ are the (inexact) differentials of the heat input and work done per unit volume, respectively. This equation assumes no mass transport. Hence, if mass transport (via convection and advection^{*}) takes place, the changes of internal energy within a given volume due to mass transport through the walls of the volume should also be taken into account.

However, the input or output of heat can be due to several different reasons:

1. External input from heating sources such as solar radiation, precipitating energetic particles from the magnetosphere and interplanetary space or plasma waves.
2. Internal heating or cooling associated with chemical reactions or Joule heating due to ionospheric currents.
3. Heat transfer by atmospheric radiation such as thermal radiation in the infrared and airglow.
4. Heat transfer by means of thermal conduction.
5. Frictional heating due to the air viscosity in the presence of shears in wind velocity.

In the presence of large scale atmospheric motions, changes in internal energy occur via the work term in the first law.

If we now neglect the energy transfer associated with the air motion, the only term in the first law is $d'q$ which can be divided into the heat production by means of external and internal sources (Q), loss due to radiation (L) and the conduction term $\nabla \cdot \Phi$, where Φ is the conduction flux density. Then the rate of change of the internal energy is:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = Q - L - \nabla \cdot \Phi \quad (2.14)$$

In the ideal gas approximation, internal energy depends only on temperature. Then, according to thermodynamics,

$$u = nc_V T \quad (2.15)$$

where c_V is the specific heat at constant volume.

^{*}In atmospheric sciences vertical and horizontal transport of mass and associated quantities are sometimes called convection and advection, respectively, but sometimes both are called just convection.

Then eq. (2.14) gives the time change of the temperature in the form

$$nc_V \frac{dT}{dt} = Q - L - \nabla \cdot \Phi \quad (2.16)$$

The terms on the right hand side are complicated and will not be treated here. However, it is customary to discuss the energy balance equation in terms of the heating rates.

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{source} = \frac{Q}{nc_V} \quad (2.17)$$

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{radiation} = -\frac{L}{nc_V} \quad (2.18)$$

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{conduction} = -\frac{\nabla \cdot \Phi}{nc_V} \quad (2.19)$$

Due to the minus signs, the latter two could be called cooling rates. The last one, however, could cause both heating and cooling since both heating and cooling may be caused by thermal conduction, depending on the sign of $\nabla \cdot \Phi$.

The main factor producing the heat source Q is photoabsorption of solar radiation, which will be discussed in connection with the formation of the ionosphere in chapter three.

2.1.3. Upper atmosphere

Due to solar radiation the molecules in the upper atmosphere are heated and electrons are released from them. It results in an ionized medium that is called the *ionosphere*. Not all the particles in the ionosphere are ionized, but the ionosphere consists of a mix of uncharged and charged atmospheric particles. Although less than 1% of the mass of atmosphere lies in the upper Earth's atmosphere, the free electrons in ionosphere are sufficiently numerous to influence the propagation of radio waves. Because of this the ionosphere plays an important role in radio communication and satellite navigation systems. The rate of ionization depends on the density of gas molecules and the intensity of the radiation (see chapter 3).

2.2. The Sun

The Sun is the largest object in our solar system. The Sun with a radius of $R_s = 696,000 \text{ km}$ (of the visible disc), mass ($1.99 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$), and luminosity, energy radiated per unit of time, ($3.9 \times 10^{26} \text{ watts}$) contains more than 99.8% of the total mass of the solar system. The Sun is composed mainly of hydrogen (90%) and helium (10%) with small amounts of argon, calcium, carbon, iron, magnesium, neon, nickel, nitrogen, oxygen, silicon, and sulfur. Like the planets, the Sun rotates on its axis; its rotation period is 27 day.

The Sun's energy comes mainly from the thermonuclear fusion of hydrogen to form helium. This thermonuclear reaction takes place in the Sun's core where the temperature is thought to reach nearly $1.5 \times 10^7 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$:

The net result of the above reactions is the following:

Note that; if the core temperature increases to about $10^8 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$, then the energy can be produced by burning helium to make carbon.

Very energetic gamma rays, with photon energies over $\sim 30 \text{ Gev}$, can be detected by ground based experiments. Since the atmosphere is as thick to gamma rays as a twelve-foot plate of aluminum, such high-energy gamma photons produce extensive showers of secondary particles in the atmosphere that can be observed on the ground. The Sun's interior can be divided into four zones (Fig.2.2):

The core. This is the high density, high temperature region ($1.5 \times 10^7 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$) at the center of the Sun, where thermonuclear energy production takes place. The core extends from the center to about $R_s/4$, but it contains about half of the solar mass. Practically all of the Sun's energy production takes place in this region.

Figure 2.2: (I) The Sun photographed by the Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA 304) of NASA's Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO), 19-8-2010. (II) Structure of the solar interior.

The radiative zone. The energy produced in the core is transported through the core and the radiative zone by gamma ray diffusion. The gamma rays are scattered, absorbed, and reemitted many times before they reach the outer edge of the radiative zone.

The convection zone. This zone is located in the uppermost 30% of the solar interior. In this region the solar material is convectively unstable, because the radial temperature gradients are large.

The solar atmosphere. The solar atmosphere consists of three layers. The lowest is the thin and dense (~500 km thick, with densities of about 10^{23} particles per m^3) **photosphere** that emits most of the sunlight. The temperature of the photosphere is 5,800 °K.

The next layer is the **chromosphere** (thickness ~3,000 km, density $\sim 10^{17} m^{-3}$), where the temperature increases from 4,200 °K to $\sim 10^4$ °K. The chromosphere is the source region of several transition lines (such as H- α and some UV lines) that are very important in the terrestrial upper atmosphere. The chromosphere is followed by the **solar corona**, the uppermost layer, where the temperature increases from $\sim 10^4$ °K to $\sim 10^6$ °K but there are regions with lower temperature (4000 °K) which are seen by observers on the Earth as dark *sunspots*.

The Sun’s magnetic field is generated by plasma motions below the Sun’s surface and extends out to shape and control the solar atmosphere and the

entire *heliosphere* (a bubble containing our solar system, solar wind, and the entire solar magnetic field). Close to the visible surface of the Sun, the magnetic field is strongest over the poles.

Sunspots Sunspots are cool regions with extremely strong magnetic fields, up to 3000 G, on the photosphere which emit significantly less radiation than their hot surroundings and therefore appear dark only by comparison with the surrounding regions (Prolss, 2004). The magnetic field inside the spots is from 100 to 5000 times more intense than the surrounding field. Sunspots can be very large, as much as 40000 km in diameter. Sunspots have an intense magnetic activity, which inhibits convection, forming areas of low surface temperature. This contrast leaves them clearly visible as dark spots (Fig.2.3).

Figure. 2.3. A close-up of a sunspot (Swedish Solar Telescope,G. Scharmer).

Sunspots tend to group together. In order to account for the statistical appearance of sunspots, the *relative sunspot number R*, (also called the *Wolf* or *Zurich number*) is used: $R = k (10 g + f)$, where *g* is the number of sunspots groups (a group may include one or more sunspots), *f* is the number of individual spots, and *k* is a correction factor, usually less than unity, which depends on the sensitivity of the observing equipment and is intended as a correction to get the original scale by Wolf (Davies, 1989). Note that a sunspot group is surrounded by a region of moderate field strength (about 100 G), an *active region*, which is hotter and brighter than its surroundings.

The most widely used index in ionospheric work is the 12-month smoothed relative sunspot number $R_{12}(n)$ defined by:

$$R_{12}(n) = [\sum_{i=n-5}^{n+5} R_i + 0.5(R_{n+6} + R_{n-6})]/12 \quad (2.25)$$

in which R_i is the mean value of R for month i .

Sunspots appear and disappear over time and R displays systematic variations that provide useful information on the state of the Sun. The magnitude of R varies between zero and 200, with a period of approximately 11 years; the so-called *sunspot cycle* or *solar cycle*. In figure 2.4, R is plotted for the current solar cycle (no. 24). Solar Minimum refers to the several years when the sunspot numbers are the lowest and Solar Maximum refers to the years when sunspots are the most numerous.

Figure 2.4: Solar cycle 24: Measured and predicted sunspot numbers (Graph courtesy of NOAA Space Environment Center [SEC], USA).

During Solar Maximum, activity on the sun and its effects on our terrestrial environment are high. For example, the frequency and intensity of geomagnetic storms and radiation showers in the Earth’s atmosphere increases during solar maximum.

2.2.1. The Solar radiation

Huge amounts of energy are continuously released from the Sun by both electromagnetic radiation (photon) and particle outflow (protons and electrons).

Photon radiation The energy transported from the Sun to Earth by the electro-magnetic radiation is described by *the radiative energy flux* as “the energy per second passing through a unit area perpendicular to the Sun’s rays above the atmosphere”.

The Sun radiates electromagnetic waves over a wide range of wavelengths, including the X-ray, ultraviolet, visible, infrared and radio waves (see Fig.2.5). The total radiated energy per second in all wavelengths is approximately constant and equal to 1370 watts/m^2 at top of the Earth’s atmosphere (at a Sun-Earth separation of 1 astronomical unit^{*}), and is called the *solar constant*.

Figure 2.5: The solar spectral distribution from the x-ray band through the radio band. The plot represents irradiance (watts/m^2) versus wavelength (nm) where the irradiance is normalized to a wavelength increment of 1.0 nm . Increasing wavelength is to the right, and increasing energy/photon is to the left.

^{*}An astronomical unit (abbreviated as AU, au or a.u.) is a unit of length equal to about $149,597,870.7 \text{ km}$ or approximately the mean Earth–Sun distance.

Table 2.1 shows the contribution of the different wavelengths to the solar constant. The major energy contributions are from the infrared (52%), visible (41%), and ultraviolet (<7%) spectral regions. The radio and X-ray wavelengths make only a minor contribution (<1%) to the solar constant (Schunk and Nagy, 2000; Tascione, 1994).

Particle radiation The Sun releases about one billion kilograms of the energetic charged particles (mainly protons and electrons) every second into space. This is the *solar wind*. The velocity of the particles is about 300 km/sec so it takes about 4-5 days to reach the Earth. The solar wind is mainly sustained by a continuously outflow of plasma from the Sun’s corona. A portion of the solar particle radiation is related to powerful events in the Sun’s atmosphere above sunspots, called *solar flares*.

The received total energy from solar particle radiation at top of the Earth’s atmosphere is only about one-tenth of the solar photon radiation energy from the X-ray and EUV spectral regions (Ratcliffe, 1972).

Table 2.1: The contribution of the solar spectral regions to the solar constant (Note: Å = 10⁻¹⁰m).

Solar spectral region	Wavelength range	Contribution
Radio	1mm < λ	< 0.1%
Far Infrared	10μm < λ < 1mm	52%
Infrared	0.75μm < λ < 10μm	
Visible	0.3μm < λ < 0.75μm	41%
Ultraviolet (UV)	1200Å° < λ < 3000Å°	< 7%
Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV)	100 Å° < λ < 1200 Å°	0.1%
X-rays	λ < 100Å°	< 0.1%

2.2.1.1. Variation of the radiation intensity

The total solar radiation per second in all wavelengths is approximately constant. Within the spectral range of maximum energy flux (the visible and neighboring infrared and ultraviolet ranges), the intensity of the solar radiation is practically constant, varying by less than 0.3% (Prolls, 2004). The minor radiation sources (the radio, extreme ultraviolet and X-ray spectral regions) display large fluctuations depending on solar activity.

Solar flares and rapidly moving plasma clouds in the Sun’s corona are more frequent during solar maximum, and therefore solar particle radiation showers near the Earth are also more frequent and more intense during the period of solar maximum. There is also a general increase in solar wind during the solar maximum. Solar activity varies not only during the solar cycle, but also from day to day. Therefore radiation will also vary from day to day.

The sunspot number is a useful way to describe solar activity in a quantitative sense and provides an approximate measure of the solar short wavelength (the X-ray and UV) radiation intensity. Another index that is very useful is the so-called solar radiation index *F10.7*.

2.2.2. Solar radiations index (F10.7)

The solar flux on the radio wavelength of 10.7 *cm* (2800 MHz) is well correlated with X-ray, EUV, and UV fluxes. The flux on wavelength of 10.7 *cm* is measured daily with a reflector of 1.8 *m* diameter at the Algonquin Radio Observatory, near Ottawa at 17:00 UT in units of $10^{-22}\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{Hz}^{-1}$ (solar flux unit). The 10.7 *cm* radio flux is known as *F10.7 index* or *Covington index* (CI) and varies from a minimum near 65 (corresponding to sunspot number zero at solar minimum) to a maximum of about 200 corresponding to a sunspot number of about 150 to 160 (Davies, 1989). Because of correlation with X-ray, EUV and UV fluxes, the F10.7 is one of the most commonly used indicators for solar activity.

The F10.7 index displays similar variations as the sunspot number (see figure 2.6). An empirical formula to convert the smoothed relative sunspot number (see equation 2.25) into monthly averaged F10.7 index is provided by the *Radiocommunication* sector of the *International Telecommunication Union* (ITU-R) as follow (Leitinger et al., 2005):

$$F_{10.7} = 63.7 + (0.728 + 0.00089 R_{12})R_{12} \quad (2.26)$$

and wise versa

$$R_{12} = [167273 + (F_{10.7} - 63.7)1123.6]^{0.5} - 408.99 \quad (2.27)$$

Figure 2.6: Progression of solar cycle 24: Measured and predicted F10.7 (Graph courtesy of NOAA Space Environment Center [SEC], USA).

2.2.3. Solar Wind

The solar wind is a gale of relatively low-energy atomic particles, protons and electrons that form hot magnetized, plasma. Solar wind comes from great rips in the Sun's corona, called *coronal holes**, as a result of the huge difference in gas pressure between the solar corona and the interstellar medium. This pressure difference permanently drives flux of the solar plasma outward into space.

These holes appear to be predominant in the polar regions and are fairly small. The fast wind blows at a steady 750 km/s , but the typical solar wind emerging from the Sun's equatorial zone is variable but relatively slow, at $350 - 400\text{ km/s}$. The solar wind flows straight out in all directions and carries a weak magnetic field, *interplanetary magnetic field* (IMF), with it. The IMF is "frozen in" to the plasma so that it moves together with the plasma.

The Sun's rotation, combined with the radial outward flow of the solar wind, causes the interplanetary field lines to take up a spiral form that extend deep into space (Figure 2.7).

***Coronal holes** are areas where the Sun's corona is darker, colder, and has lower-density plasma than average. Coronal holes are linked to unipolar concentrations of open magnetic field lines. During solar minimum, coronal holes are mainly found at the Sun's polar regions, but they can be located anywhere on the sun during solar maximum. The fast-moving component of the solar wind is known to travel along open magnetic field lines that pass through coronal holes.

The boundary of the region within which the solar wind and interplanetary field predominate (the *heliosphere*) is called the *heliopause* and is believed to lie at a distance of about 100AU. The radius of the heliosphere is expected to vary with the solar cycle.

Figure 2.7: Schematic diagram of the Sun–Earth system in the Sun’s ecliptic plane. The solar wind is in the radial direction away from the Sun and the magnetic field lines bend into spirals as the Sun slowly rotates.

Figure 2.8: Schematic diagram of the three-dimensional structure of the current sheet that flows in an azimuthal direction around the Sun. The inset at the top of the figure shows the opposite polarities of the magnetic fields on the two sides of the current sheet. (Courtesy of S.-I. Akasofu, Geophysical Institute, University of Alaska).

At the Earth’s orbit, the spiral angle is approximately 43° with respect to a line that connects the Sun and Earth. In three dimensions, the spirals can be described by the *ballerina skirt* model (Alfven, H., 1981).

Consideration of the Maxwell equation:

$$\nabla \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{J} \quad (2.28)$$

shows that a geometry with adjacent magnetic fields that are antiparallel must have a current sheet separating them (indicated by the crosshatched surface in Fig. 2.8). So the skirt represents a sheet of current that flows in an azimuthal direction around the Sun, but the skirt has a wavy structure that is similar to a ballerina's skirt (Figure 2.8). The magnetic fields on the opposite sides of this *heliospheric current sheet* have opposite polarity, and as the different folds of the skirt drape the various bodies in the solar system, they are exposed to different IMF polarities. The polarity of the whole system reverses at the beginning of each new 11-year cycle because of the reversal in polarity of the Sun's magnetic poles.

2.2.4. Solar Activity

The term *solar activity* refers to a wide range of transient solar phenomena that vary in a complex ways with the solar cycle. Solar activity is driven by the temporally and spatially varying distribution of magnetic flux in the photosphere, chromosphere and corona. It covers a range of phenomena at all levels in the solar atmosphere and time-scales ranging. Our modern hi-tech society has become increasingly vulnerable to disturbances from outside the Earth system, in particular to those initiated by explosive events on the Sun:

I. Flares

A localized explosive release of energy, usually from a site located within a complex solar active region, in which up to 10^{25} J can be liberated within a few minutes to several hours. Flares emit radiation over practically the entire electromagnetic spectrum from hard (short-wavelength) x-rays, or even gamma rays, to radio waves. The bulk of the energy being emitted at x- and extreme ultraviolet wavelengths. They eject streams of high-energy subatomic particles, including electrons (which in some cases are accelerated to speeds in excess of half the velocity of light), protons and small numbers of heavier nuclei, and expel bulk clouds of plasma through the corona into interplanetary space. As the high-speed particle streams and plasma clouds plow through the corona, they stimulate the emission of microwave and radio radiation across a wide range of frequencies. The correlations of the high energy electrons energized during the flare and the gamma rays are mostly

caused by nuclear combinations of high energy protons and other heavier ions. These gamma-rays can be observed and allow scientists to determine the major results of the energy released, which is not provided by the emissions from other wavelengths. Nuclear gamma rays were observed from the solar flares of August 4 and 7, 1972, and November 22, 1977 (Ramaty et al., 1977).

Flares are believed to be caused by the sudden release of magnetic energy that had previously been stored in the twisted magnetic fields of complex sunspot groups or active regions by means of a process called *magnetic reconnection*. This occurs when oppositely directed field lines come into contact, sever, and join up to form new field structures. For example, a closed loop with its ‘feet’ connected to the solar surface and an open U - shaped structure above. In the process, part of the energy contained in the magnetic field is converted into other forms of energy, such as thermal (heat) energy and kinetic energy for particle streams. Localized heating at the site of the reconnection produces much of the soft (longer wavelength) x-ray and extreme ultraviolet radiation, while electrons accelerated down the loops produce bursts of hard x-rays and hydrogen- α (optical) radiation where they plow into the chromosphere. Like an elastic string, a magnetic field line has tension in it. Consequently, when a magnetic field structure severs and reconnects, it catapults bulk plasma outwards. The exact form of that configuration is not certain, but one possibility is shown in Figure 2.9.

Figure. 2.9. A model of the solar flare, showing possible sources, for some of the known products. (After J. H. Piddington, *Cosmic Electrodynamics*. Wiley, 1969).

Table 2.2: Solar Flare Classification.

<i>Class</i>	<i>Peak Intensity (W/m²)</i>
A	$10^{-8} < = I < 10^{-7}$
B	$10^{-7} < = I < 10^{-6}$
C	$10^{-6} < = I < 10^{-5}$
M	$10^{-5} < = I < 10^{-4}$
X	$I > 10^{-4}$

Scientists classify solar flares according to their X-ray brightness in the wavelength range 1 to 8 Angstroms (see table 2.2):

- **X-class flares:** are big; they are major events that can trigger planet-wide radio blackouts and long-lasting radiation storms.
- **M-class flares:** are medium-sized; they can cause brief radio blackouts that affect Earth's polar regions. Minor radiation storms sometimes follow an M-class flare.
- **C, B and A-class flares:** Compared to X- and M-class events, C, B and A-classes flares are small with few noticeable consequences here on Earth.

Within each class the accurate intensity is given as a number. E.g., M7.5 corresponds to the flux of $7.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ W/m}^2$. The largest observed X-ray flare so far took place on November 4, 2003. It was classified as X27.

Nowadays the solar X-rays are monitored regularly, e.g., by the NOAA (*National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration*) GOES-satellites. The observed intensities are readily available at the NOAA web site: <http://www.noaa.sec.gov/>.

The following figure (2.10) shows a series of solar flares detected by NOAA satellites in July 2000 in which the three indicated flares registered (from left to right) X2, M5, and X6. The X6 flare triggered a radiation storm around Earth nicknamed the Bastille Day event.

Flares have a variety of effects on the Earth. High speed particles from solar flares take about 30 min to travel to the Earth. Low-energy particles and disturbances produced in the solar wind by the flare take from a few hours to a couple of days to arrive.

Figure. 2.10: Solar flare from active region 9077 registered as a powerful X6-class eruption on July 14, 2000 as measured by the NOAA GOES-8 satellite. Another X-class flare from 9077 was recorded on July 12, 2000.

Charged particles plunging into the upper atmosphere give rise to auroral displays. Flare-generated X-rays and UV radiation can affect Earth's ionosphere and disrupt long-range radio communications. Direct radio emission at decametric wavelengths may disturb operation of radars and other devices operating at these frequencies. It can also affect electrical systems and satellites. The frequency of occurrence of solar flares varies, from several per day when the Sun is particularly "active" to less than one each week when the Sun is "quiet". Large flares are less frequent than smaller ones.

II. Coronal mass ejections (CMEs)

Solar flares were, for a long time, thought to be the main drivers of geomagnetic storms. During the last 15–20 years this picture has been revised in favor of coronal mass ejections (CME). (Note that the term “*coronal mass ejection*” is a bit misleading. Much of the matter or *mass* in CME originates from the lower solar atmosphere, in particular from the chromosphere, and thus is not “*coronal mass*”. The word “*coronal*” in CME refers to the fact that CMEs are observed in the *corona*.)

Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) are spatially larger and temporarily slower events than flares in which huge amounts of plasma initially trapped in closed coronal magnetic field lines are ejected into interplanetary space.

First identified in the early 1970s, a typical CME can carry up to 10^{13} *k.g* of mass, and kinetic energy on the order of 10^{24} to 10^{25} J, into space as part of the Sun's atmosphere erupts.

The CME source regions within the Sun's atmosphere can be hundreds of thousands of *km* across and the resulting CMEs can expand into space at many hundreds of *km/s*. When a CME leaves the Sun its speed varies from less than 50 *km/s* to more than 2000 *km/s*.

Figure.2.11: An image sequence over two hours of a large coronal mass ejection 20 March 2000 taken by the LASCO C2 instrument. This CME was not headed towards Earth.

At 1AU the speed is only seldom larger than 750 *km/s* and never smaller than the minimum solar wind speed of about 280 *km/s*. Thus the originally slow CMEs are accelerated toward the solar wind speed whereas the very high speed CMEs are decelerated. A CME in the interplanetary space is called ICME (interplanetary CME). The rate of CME eruptions varies with the solar cycle. The whole-Sun occurrence rate is 0.8 events/day at solar minimum and 3.5 events/day at solar maximum.

Note that A CME does not radiate itself. The observed light is produced by Thomson scattering* of the solar photons from the electrons in the cloud. CME coronagraphs use white light because most of the solar photons are in the visible wavelengths. The white light brightness varies in proportion to electron density. Thus the brightness can be used to determine the density structure of the emitted cloud.

CMEs originate from the closed field line regions of the helmet streamers**, due to some reason, and this determines their magnetic topology. Since the magnetic structure has to be torn away from the Sun, the field must open locally. The disruption of a large stable magnetically closed structure still poses fundamental questions for the magneto-hydrodynamic theory. However, it is very likely that large-scale magnetic reconnection is involved in the formation of a CME.

The exact relationship between the flares and CMEs is unclear but only some 40% of CMEs have an associated flare close to the site of the ejection. These flares may take place before, simultaneously, or after the lift-off of the CME.

One must note that impulsive *Solar Energetic Pericles* (SEP) events are associated with solar flares. Gradual SEP events may be either of flare or CME origin.

Note also the difference between CMEs and the quiet solar wind. In quiet solar wind the kinetic energy of solar wind particles dominates over magnetic energy of IMF and the magnetic field is frozen-in in the plasma motion. The situation for CMEs is at least much further out from the Sun than in the quiet solar wind, opposite since the CME evolution is defined by the magnetic field or, in other words, magnetic energy dominates the particles' kinetic energy. CMEs represent a very significant disturbance to the solar wind.

***Thomson scattering** is the elastic scattering of electromagnetic radiation by a free charged particle, as described by classical electromagnetism. It is just the low-energy limit of Compton scattering: the particle kinetic energy and photon frequency are the same before and after the scattering. This limit is valid as long as the photon energy is much less than the mass energy of the particle: $h\nu \ll mc^2$.

****Helmet streamers** are bright loop-like structures which develop over active regions on the sun. They are closed magnetic loops which connect regions of opposite magnetic polarity. Electrons are captured in these loops, and cause them to glow very brightly.

Given their size and mass, combined with the fact that the expanding clouds carry a frozen-in magnetic field, such events can engulf the Earth's system and their arrival at the Earth can generate significant geomagnetic storms.

Forty years after the first detection, one might imagine that CMEs are well understood. There exists a vast range of measured parameters: speed, occurrence rate, latitudinal distribution, ICME speed, magnetic field strength etc. But major questions associated with CMEs persist.

- What is the physics of the initiation of CMEs and what are the observable signatures of this physics?
- What is the physical relationship between CMEs and flares?
- What determines where and when a CME takes place and how could we predict CMEs?
- How are CMEs accelerated?
- Is reconnection a primary driver of the release or its consequence? What are the effects of reconnection on the topology of the CMEs?

III.Solar energetic particles (SEPs)

Solar Energetic Particles are high-energy particles coming from the Sun which had been first observed in the early 1940s. They consist of protons, electrons and heavy ions with energy ranging from a few tens of keV to GeV (the fastest particles can reach speed up to 80% of the speed of light) arrive at the Earth's orbit within minutes. They are of particular interest and importance because they can endanger life in outer space (especially particles above 40 MeV). SEPs can originate from two processes: energization at a solar flare site or by shock waves associated with Coronal Mass Ejection (CMEs). SEPs can be accelerated to energies of several tens of MeV within 5-10 solar radii (0.05% of the Sun-Earth distance) and can reach Earth in a matter of a few hours after a flare or an ejection. This makes prediction and warning of SEP events quite challenging. The seed population and composition of these SEP events is also an active area of research.

During SEP events, a gamma radiation is observed by satellite-borne spectrometers. Energetic protons in SEP events interact with nuclei in the atmosphere to directly excite nuclear states, create reaction products, and produce secondary neutrons. These neutrons also excite nuclear states directly and through products of nuclear reactions. Letaw et al., 1989, listed the most intense gamma ray lines from these processes based on earlier compilations by Ling (1975), Ramaty et al. (1979), and nuclear data tables.

2.3. Magnetosphere and Geomagnetism

As it approaches the Earth, the solar wind interacts with the terrestrial magnetic field. In this section we examine the Earth's magnetic Field.

2.3.1. Earth's magnetic field

Electric currents in the Earth's core (due to circulation of liquid metal in the deep Earth) produce a magnetic dipole field (bar magnet) around the Earth. In the absence of any external forces (solar wind), the geomagnetic field near the earth can be approximated by a simple magnet that located in the earth's center with an axis tilted about 11.5° degrees from the earth's rotation axis (Davies, 1965; Pross, 2004).

The geocentric dipole axis intersects the surface of the Earth at the so called north and south geomagnetic poles. The magnetic poles however do not correspond exactly to the geographic poles and moreover, they are reversed, magnetic north is near the geographic south pole.

The geomagnetic field vector, \vec{B} , or the geomagnetic induction vector, is related to the so-called magnetic elements $B, H, I, D, X, Y,$ and Z (see figure 2.12). $X, Y,$ and Z are three field components along orthogonal directions with positive values for geographic north, east, and down, respectively. B and H are the total and horizontal field intensities (unit: *Tesla* = *Volt.Sec/m²*), respectively. The declination angle D is the angle between geographic North and the geomagnetic North. The angle that B makes with the horizontal plane is called the magnetic *inclination* or *dip angle* I . The seven elements are related through the following simple expressions;

$$D = \tan^{-1}(Y/X) \quad X = H \cos(D) \quad (2.29)$$

$$I = \tan^{-1}(Z/H) \quad Y = H \sin(D) \quad (2.30)$$

$$H = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2} \quad B = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2} \quad (2.31)$$

The magnetic inclination is independent of the height and is positive in the Northern Hemisphere. At the geomagnetic poles the inclination is 90° . The circle on the surface of the Earth with inclination 0° is called the *magnetic* or *dipole equator*, while the position on the Earth's surface where the geomagnetic field line is vertical ($I=90^\circ$) are called the dip poles.

Figure 2.12: Components of the geomagnetic field in a point located in the Northern Hemisphere (total field vector inclined into the Earth).

2.3.1.1. Geomagnetic regions

The ionospheric electron density has a large dependence on the geomagnetic latitude. The ionosphere may be divided broadly into three regions that have rather different properties and features according to their geomagnetic latitudes: Equatorial, Mid-latitude, and Polar (or Auroral) regions, see figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13: Division of the Earth into geomagnetic regions. Plotted are the geomagnetic parallel lines in the geodetic reference frame.

Equatorial region This the region spanning about 20° either side of the geomagnetic equator. Due to the horizontal geomagnetic field geometry at the dip equator ($I = 0^\circ$), the electromagnetic drift and associated plasma fountain (see chapter 3), results in a large variability of the electron density in low latitudes which makes it complication to model.

Mid-Latitude region The mid latitude region of the ionosphere includes geomagnetic latitudes from about 20° to about 60° . In this region, only solar photon radiation is responsible for the ionization process and the electron density is generally not affected by the particle radiation. The mid latitude ionosphere is the best understood of all regions.

Polar region The polar region consists of the high latitudes, which are divided in the auroral zone (approximately 60° - 70° geomagnetic latitudes) and the polar cap (poleward of the auroral zone). At high latitudes the geomagnetic field runs nearly vertical, and this leads to the existence of the ionosphere that is considerably more complex than that in the middle and low latitudes. This complexity is also because the geomagnetic field lines connect the high latitudes to the outer part of the magnetosphere which is driven by the solar wind.

In the mid and low latitude regions, the primary source of ionization is the solar photon radiation, but at high latitudes, solar particle radiation produces additional ionization particularly in the E-region.

2.3.2. Magnetosphere

The Earth's magnetosphere can be defined by the area of space around the Earth that is controlled by the Earth's magnetic field.

The space enclosed by the magnetosphere is not empty but filled with a trapped particles, namely ions and electrons. The magnetic forces are much stronger than gravity. The magnetosphere is not completely closed with respect to the solar wind magnetic field. The geomagnetic cavity, illustrated in north-south section in Figure 2.14, is formed because the solar wind is not able to penetrate the geomagnetic field, being swept around it and at the same time distorting the field. There is an ongoing input of magnetic field lines from the magnetospheric subsolar side and there is also ongoing output of the terrestrial field lines from the magnetotail into space. These two phenomena occur via the *reconnection* or *merging* process.

The real shape of the boundary of the magnetosphere, the *magnetopause*, is strongly modified by the solar wind. When the system is in equilibrium the pressure of the solar wind outside is - at every point of the surface - equal to that of the magnetic field inside.

The distance of the magnetopause is:

- 10 to 12 R_E on the side facing the Sun (R_E being the earth's radius, ~ 6400 km).
- 15 R_E over the poles.
- 100 R_E on the night.

The different parts of a magnetosphere are:

1. *Bow shock*: In this front region, the solar wind particles hit the magnetosphere.
2. *Magnetosheath*: The region between the bow shock and the magnetopause where the particles become thermalized. i.e., kinetic energy is converted to thermal energy and the plasma is highly turbulent there.

Figure 2.14. Cross-section of the geomagnetic cavity and external plasma flow showing the magnetopause and the bow shock (After *Vasyliunas* [1983], p. 243).

3. *Polar cusps*: The simple models of the magnetosphere predict two neutral points on the magnetopause where the total field is zero. These points connect along field-lines to places on the Earth's surface near $\pm 78^\circ$ magnetic latitude. These are the only points that connect the Earth's surface to the magnetopause and all the field from the magnetopause converges to those two points. They are therefore regions of great interest where solar wind particles (from the magnetosheath) can enter the magnetosphere without having to cross field-lines.
4. *The tail region* : The solar wind stretches the dipole field, compressing it on the dayside and stretching it into a long tail region in the nightside, usually known as the *magnetotail*. The field lines close at very large distances ($\sim 3000 R_E$).
5. *Plasmasheet* : This is a sheet of plasma in the tail region dividing the two lobes of the Earth's magnetic field.
6. *Lobes* : they are in the magnetotail, having an opposite direction and are separated by the plasmasheet. Otherwise they would cancel.
7. *plasmasphere*: A torus shaped region, surrounding the Earth. It was detected in 1963 and has a very sharp edge at the *plasmopause* extending from 4 to 6 R_E . It can be also regarded as an extension of the ionosphere. Inside the plasmopause geomagnetic field lines rotate with the Earth. Outside the plasmasphere, magnetic field lines are unable to corotate and the solar wind influence is too large. The plasmasphere is mainly composed of hydrogen.
8. *Van Allen radiation belts*: in 1958 Van Allen discovered the radiation belts; like the plasmasphere they are toroidally shaped. The inner radiation belt extends from 400 to 12000 *km* above the Earth, the outer belt from 12000 to 60000 *km*.

In order to understand the dynamics of the current system, we recapitulate the motions of charged particles in a magnetic field (Figure 2.15):

1. *Spiral motion*: circling about magnetic field lines; Charged particles cannot easily move across magnetic field lines but are forced to spiral around them. Electrons encircle the field line in one direction, ions in the other direction.
2. *Bounce motion*: the particles move along the field lines from pole to pole. Near the poles they become reflected (since the magnetic field line density is large).
3. *Drift motion*: Curvature of the magnetic field lines and the non-uniform strength of the magnetic field force particles to drift around the earth, ions in one direction, electrons in the other. For the Earth as seen from Egypt: Ions go west, electrons east.

Figure. 2.15: Motion of a gyrating ion in a magnetic field. On the left is the gyration of an ion about a straight field line. In the middle panel an ion is reflected by the converging magnetic field. On the right is illustrated the gradient and curvature.

2.3.2.1. Magnetospheric current systems

The combination of a constant solar wind plasma flow and the earth's magnetic field creates several current systems. Fig. 2.16 schematically sketches them, relative to the Earth size. These systems can be identified as (a) the magnetopause current, (b) the ring current, (c) the tail current.

Figure 2.16. Magnetospheric current systems: a) magnetopause current; b) ring current; c) tail current. The small circle stands for the earth ionosphere. (After W. P. Olsen, *Adv. Space Res.*, 2, 13).

Magnetopause current

Magnetic fields and electric currents are fundamentally related through the *Biot-Savart law*. The magnetopause current, Fig. 2.16.a, flows along the surface of the magnetopause so that its magnetic effect cancels the geomagnetic field outside the magnetosphere. In the inner magnetosphere, where the magnetic field is almost dipolar, the contribution from the magnetopause current to the total field is small compared to that from the Earth’s internal dipole.

Fig. 2.17 explains emergence of the magnetopause current. For simplicity we assume that the SW plasma is un-magnetized.

Generally speaking, a flow of any high conducting fluid leads to emerging a magnetopause in front of a magnet fixed in the fluid and not moving with it. The schematic shows a rectangular fragment of cross-section of the magnetosphere in the *XZ* plane in the GSM coordinate system. The magnetopause is shown as a thick grey vertical line. The subsolar area on the left contains no terrestrial magnetic field, whereas the magnetosphere on the right is filled with the earth’s magnetic field lines. According to Maxwell’s equation (with the term $\epsilon_0 \mu_0 \partial \mathbf{E} / \partial t$ zero due to assumed stationary conditions):

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{j} \tag{2.32}$$

By equation (2.32) the surface must contain the current \mathbf{j} with the streamlines perpendicular to the \mathbf{B} lines of force, as shown by the circles with dots in Figure 2.17.

The magnetopause current has counterclockwise sense of rotation if viewed from above the North Pole. It makes up two “funnels” near the dipole poles. These funnels indicate the positions of the earth’s geomagnetic field cusps.

Figure 2.17. Formation of the magnetopause current \mathbf{j} . The surface of magnetopause separates the interplanetary medium (on the left) and the earth’s magnetic field \mathbf{B} (on the right), therefore the magnetopause must contain the sheet current \mathbf{j} .

Tail current

In the nightside, Earth’s magnetic field due to the solar wind action is extended far away from the sun, forming a tube-like tail. The northern half of this tail confines the magnetic lines of force directed towards the earth, and the southern half confines the lines directed outwards. Due to the properties of magnetic field, described above, such confined configuration only exists if there are surface currents.

The latter are called *tail currents*. They form two solenoids, coalescent with the magnetopause current, bounding the northern and southern magnetic flux tubes as shown in Fig. 2.18. The tail current sheet density i_T (A/m) and the magnetic flux density B_T inside of the tail are related as $B_T = \mu_0 i_T$. Note that the tail current in the central plasma sheet CPS and the boundary plasma sheet BPS regions is $2i_T$

Figure 2.18. Tail current as seen from the earth (in antisunward direction). (After L. Svalgaard, *NASA Report SP-366*, 1975).

Ring current

The ring current flows around the earth clockwise (from the viewpoint over the North Pole), as shown in Fig. 2.16, b. Its magnetic field is such that it acts to oppose the Earth's magnetic field. The action of the ring current reveals itself during the global magnetic storms that are characterized by sudden increase in the ground-level magnetic field (due to the initial compression of the magnetosphere from increased solar wind pressure) and its subsequent decompression lasting from several hours to days.

The ring current consists of the trapped particles drifting at distances of (4- 6) R_E from the earth's surface, between the inner edge of the central plasma sheet and the outer edge of the trapping zone. In the tail reconnection point the particles are accelerated earthward. However, as they enter the regions of stronger magnetic field, they are trapped and join the ring current particle population. The total ring current is proportional to the total energy of the particles.

2.3.3. Geomagnetic indices

Mayaud (1980) has discussed the array of indices in his book, *Derivation, Meaning, and Use of Geomagnetic Indices*. He traces the history of magnetic index development from the earliest forms to those of the present. Table 2.3 displays a list of the current indices sanctioned by the *International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy* (IAGA) and used in this thesis.

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Table 2.3: List of used geomagnetic indices.

<p><i>K-index</i></p>	<p>Three-hourly quasi-logarithmic index. It is a measure of the irregular variations of the horizontal field component at a specified station or group of stations. For example Km corresponds to the Fredericksburg site, and <i>Kp</i> is associated with the planetary "average" value. The values of <i>K</i> run from 0-9 with "9" representing the most disturbed condition. <i>Kp</i> is derived from 12 stations between geomagnetic latitudes 48-63 degrees. The most widely used index is <i>Kp</i>. It is used for ionospheric predictions.</p>
<p><i>AE-index</i></p>	<p>The Auroral Electrojet (AE) index was originally introduced by Davis and Sugiura in 1966 as a measure of global electrojet activity in the auroral zone. The AE index is now widely used for researches in geomagnetism, aeronomy, and solar-terrestrial physics. The AE index is derived from geomagnetic variations in the horizontal H-component observed at selected (10-13) observatories along the auroral zone in the northern hemisphere. To normalize the data a base value for each station is first calculated for each month by averaging all the data from the station on the five international quietest days. This base value is subtracted from each value of one-minute data obtained at the station during that month. Then among the data from all the stations at each given time (UT), the largest and smallest values are selected. The AU and AL indices are respectively defined by the largest and the smallest values so selected. The symbols, AU and AL, derive from the fact that these values form the Upper and Lower envelopes of the superposed plots of all the data from these stations as functions of UT. The difference, AU minus AL, defines the AE index, and the mean value of the AU and AL, i.e. (AU+AL)/2, defines the AO index. The term "AE indices" is usually used to represent these four indices (AU, AL, AE and AO). The AU and AL indices are intended to express the strongest current intensity of the eastward and westward auroral electrojets, respectively. The AE index represents the overall activity of the electrojets, and the AO index provides a measure of the equivalent zonal current.</p>
<p><i>Dst-index</i></p>	<p>Dst stands for "disturbance storm time". It is an hourly index with units of nT. It is designed to be a measure of the ring current in the magnetosphere (i.e., that region above the geomagnetic equator at ~ 5.6 earth radii). It is constructed by averaging the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field from low latitude observatories from all over the world. Negative Dst values indicate a magnetic storm is in progress, the more negative Dst is the more intense the magnetic storm. These negative deflections in the Dst index are caused by the storm time ring current which flows around the Earth from east to west in the equatorial plane.</p>

2.3.4. Geomagnetic storm

A day is geomagnetically quiet when the geomagnetic field elements at the Earth's surface are changing gradually and smoothly due to the daily changing geometrical relationships between the Earth, Sun, and Moon. Sometimes, due to the arrival of a disturbance in the solar wind or a suddenly increase in the solar particle radiation over the Earth's polar upper atmosphere, additional currents circulate in the ionosphere and lead to irregular and rapid variations of the field elements and causing a geomagnetic disturbances at the Earth's surface that known as *geomagnetic storm*. Geomagnetic storm is an interval of several days duration during which there is a large reduction in the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field at the Earth's surface (Gonzalez et al., 1994). A classic magnetic storm begins with a sudden increase in the dynamic pressure of the solar wind as high speed and high-density plasma from the Sun suddenly arrive at the Earth.

A sequence of events in a typical major storm is as follows. The shock wave associated with a cloud of plasma ejected by the Sun, as a result of a solar flare or coronal mass ejection, compresses the Earth's magnetosphere, producing a rapid intensification of the geomagnetic field at ground level. This phase, which takes place over a few minutes, is called the '*sudden storm commencement (SSC)*'. This is followed by the '*initial phase*', which lasts for up to a few hours, during which the plasma cloud flows past the Earth and the geomagnetic field strength remains higher than normal.

Note that the effect of the CME when it hits the Earth's magnetopause, depends critically whether the magnetic field in front of the plasma cloud points toward the north or the south. The strongest effect is expected to take place when the field points toward the south, since the dayside reconnection then opens the magnetopause for the excessive amount of energy and plasma to penetrate into the magnetosphere, giving rise to magnetic storms and surges in power transmission lines.

During the next stage, the '*main phase*', charged particles flow through the inner magnetosphere, thereby creating an electrical current, 'ring current', flows around the Earth. This ring current generates a magnetic field opposite to that of the Earth and causes a pronounced drop in the geomagnetic field lasting from a few hours to about a day.

As the current declines, the field strength gradually returns to its normal state, this *recovery phase* lasting typically for a few days.

The intensity of a magnetic storm is commonly defined by the minimum *Dst* value, or the maximum depressed *Dst* magnitude, at the main phase. The depression has a strong latitudinal dependence, being maximum at the equator and minimum at the poles. The depression of the magnetic field during the main phase is explained as the effect of the ring current in the magnetosphere.

During the recovery phase, the ring current decays due to charge exchange, Coulomb interaction and wave-particle interaction processes in the volume of space occupied by the ring current particles. A general picture of a typical magnetic storm is shown in figure 2.19 in terms of variations in the *Dst* index.

Figure 2.19. Schematic diagram of a typical geomagnetic storm in terms of the *Dst* index. For the definition of the initial, main and recovery phases.

Geomagnetic storms are often accompanied by displays of “*Aurora*”, in which a charged particles flow along the geomagnetic field lines and interact with the neutral atmosphere causing colored displays.

Geomagnetic storms induce currents and surges in telephone lines and power cables that sometimes cause significant damage. For example, circuit breakers in transformer stations may be caused to trip out, thereby giving rise to power blackouts.

Disturbances in the Earth’s geomagnetic field can disrupt the operation of critical infrastructures relying on space-based assets but also can result in terrestrial effects.

Radiation hazards to humans: Intense solar flares release very-high-energy particles that can cause radiation poisoning to humans (and mammals in general) in the same way as low-energy radiation from nuclear blasts. Earth's atmosphere and magnetosphere allow adequate protection at ground level, but astronauts in space are subject to potentially lethal doses of radiation. The penetration of high-energy particles into living cells can cause chromosome damage, cancer, and a host of other health problems. Large doses can be fatal immediately. Solar protons with energies greater than 30 MeV are particularly hazardous.

In October 1989, the Sun produced enough energetic particles that, if an astronaut were to have been standing on the Moon at the time, wearing only a space suit and caught out in the brunt of the storm, he would probably have died; the expected dose would be about 7000 *rem*. The cosmonauts on the Mir station were subjected to daily doses of about twice the yearly dose on the ground, and during the solar storm at the end of 1989 they absorbed their full-year radiation dose limit in just a few hours.

Communications: Many communication systems use the ionosphere to reflect radio signals over long distances. Ionospheric storms can affect radio communication at all latitudes. Some military detection or early warning systems are also affected by solar activity. Some submarine detection systems use the magnetic signatures of submarines as one input to their locating schemes. Geomagnetic storms can mask and distort these signals. Geomagnetic storms affect also long-haul telephone lines, including undersea cables unless they are fiber optic.

Navigation systems: These systems are adversely affected when solar activity disrupts their signal propagation. During solar events and geomagnetic storms, the system gave navigators information that is inaccurate by as much as several miles. If navigators had been alerted that a proton event or geomagnetic storm was in progress, they could have switched to a backup system.

Satellite hardware damage: Geomagnetic storms and increased solar ultraviolet emission heats the Earth's upper atmosphere, causing it to expand. The heated air rises, and the density at the orbit of satellites up to about 1,000

km increases significantly. This results in increased drag on satellites in space, causing them to slow and change orbit slightly. Unless Low Earth Orbit satellites are routinely boosted to higher orbits, they slowly fall, and eventually burn up in Earth's atmosphere.

*Skylab** is an example of a spacecraft reentering Earth's atmosphere prematurely in 1979 as a result of higher-than-expected solar activity.

Figure 2.20. A view of the Skylab Orbital Workshop in Earth orbit as photographed from Skylab 4 on its return home. Image credit: NASA.

As technology has allowed spacecraft components to become smaller, their miniaturized systems have become increasingly vulnerable to the more energetic solar particles. These particles can cause physical damage to microchips and can change software commands in satellite-borne computers. Another problem for satellite operators is *differential charging*. During geomagnetic storms, the number and the energy of electrons and ions increase. When a satellite travels through this energized environment, the charged particles striking the spacecraft cause different portions of the spacecraft to be differentially charged. Eventually, electrical discharges can arc across spacecraft components, harming and possibly disabling them.

*Skylab was an American space station with a manned workshop, solar observatory, and other systems that orbited the Earth from 1973 to 1979.

Bulk charging (also called *deep charging*) occurs when energetic particles, primarily electrons, penetrate the outer covering of a satellite and deposit their charge in its internal parts. If sufficient charge accumulates in any one component, it may attempt to neutralize by discharging to other components. This discharge is potentially hazardous to the satellite's electronic systems.

Figure 2.21. A high energy particles degrade solar panels (image above left), generating a spurious signals that can corrupt data or even cause a satellite to spiral out of control. Image lower right shows an electron collection on satellite and cause static electrical discharge that physically damage the circuitry.

Geologic exploration: Earth's magnetic field is used by geologists to determine subterranean rock structures. For the most part, these geodetic surveyors are searching for oil, gas, or mineral deposits. They can accomplish this only when Earth's field is quiet, so that true magnetic signatures can be detected. Other geophysicists prefer to work during geomagnetic storms, when strong variations in the Earth's normal subsurface electric currents allow them to sense subsurface oil or mineral structures. This technique is called *magnetotellurics**. For these reasons, many surveyors use geomagnetic alerts and predictions to schedule their mapping activities.

*Magnetotellurics (MT) is an electromagnetic geophysical method of imaging the Earth's subsurface by measuring natural variations of electrical and magnetic fields at the Earth's surface.

Electric grid: When a magnetic field moves about in the vicinity of a conductor such as a wire, a geomagnetically induced current is produced in the conductor. This happens on a grand scale during geomagnetic storms on all long transmission lines.

The (nearly direct) currents induced in these lines from geomagnetic storms are harmful to electrical transmission equipment, especially generators and transformers, induces core saturation, constraining their performance (as well as tripping various safety devices), and causes coils and cores to heat up. This heat can disable or destroy them, even inducing a chain reaction that can overload and blow transformers throughout a system.

This is precisely what happened on March 13, 1989: in Montreal, Québec, as well as across parts of the northeastern U.S., the electrical supply was cut off to over 6 million people for 9 hours due to a huge geomagnetic storm. Some areas of Sweden were similarly affected.

Figure 2.22: (a) Induced electric potential on Earth's surface ,up to 6 volts/Km, (b) Severe internal transformer damage caused by the geomagnetic storm of March 13, 1989 in Montreal, Québec.

By receiving geomagnetic storm alerts and warnings (e.g. by the Space Weather prediction Center; via Space Weather satellites as SOHO or ACE), power companies can (and often do) minimize damage to power transmission equipment, by momentarily disconnecting transformers or by inducing temporary blackouts.

Pipelines: Rapidly fluctuating geomagnetic fields can produce geomagnetically induced currents in pipelines. This can cause multiple problems for pipeline engineers. Flow meters in the pipeline can transmit erroneous flow information, and the corrosion rate of the pipeline is dramatically increased (Gummow,2002 and Osella et al.,1998). If engineers incorrectly attempt to balance the current during a geomagnetic storm, corrosion rates may increase even more. Once again, pipeline managers thus receive space weather alerts and warnings to allow them to implement defensive measures.

In the late 1990s, NOAA (*National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration*) developed a set of so-called Space Weather Scales that provide some guidance in connection with various forms of solar-terrestrial disturbances. These are listed in Tables 2.4. NOAA has developed three basic categories for which space weather scales are defined. They are: *Geomagnetic Storms*, *Solar Radiation Storms* and *Radio Blackouts*.

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Table 2.4.NOAA Space Weather Scales

Category		Effect	Physical measure	Average Frequency (1 cycle = 11 years)
Scale	Descriptor	Duration of event will influence severity of effects		
Geomagnetic Storms(CMES)				
G5	Extreme	Power systems: widespread voltage control problems and protective system problems can occur, some grid systems may experience complete collapse or blackout. Transformers may experience damage. Spacecraft operations: may experience extensive surface charging, problems with orientation, uplink/downlink and tracking satellites. Other systems: pipeline currents can reach hundreds of amps. HF (high frequency) radio propagation may be impossible in many areas for one to two days, satellite navigation may be degraded for days, low-frequency radio navigation can be out for hours, and aurora has been seen as low as Florida and southern Texas (typically 40° geomagnetic lat).**	Kp values* determined every 3 hours	Number of storm events when Kp level was met; (number of storm days)
G4	Severe	Power systems: possible widespread voltage control problems and some protective systems will mistakenly trip out key assets from the grid. Spacecraft operations: may experience surface charging and tracking problems, corrections may be needed for orientation problems. Other systems: induced pipeline currents affect preventive measures, HF radio propagation sporadic, satellite navigation degraded for hours, low-frequency radio navigation disrupted, and aurora has been seen as low as Alabama and northern California (typically 45° geomagnetic lat).**	Kp=8	100 per cycle (60 days per cycle)
G3	Strong	Power systems: voltage corrections may be required, false alarms triggered on some protection devices. Spacecraft operations: surface charging may occur on satellite components, drag may increase on low-Earth-orbit satellites, and corrections may be needed for orientation problems. Other systems: intermittent satellite navigation and low-frequency radio navigation problems may occur. HF radio may be intermittent, and aurora has been seen as low as Illinois and Oregon (typically 50° geomagnetic lat).**	Kp=7	200 per cycle (130 days per cycle)
G2	Moderate	Power systems: high-latitude power systems may experience voltage alarms, long-duration storms may cause transformer damage. Spacecraft operations: corrective actions to orientation may be required by ground control; possible changes in drag affect orbit predictions. Other systems: HF radio propagation can fade at higher latitudes, and aurora has been seen as low as New York and Idaho (typically 55° geomagnetic lat).**	Kp=6	600 per cycle (360 days per cycle)
G1	Minor	Power systems: weak power grid fluctuations can occur. Spacecraft operations: minor impact on satellite operations possible. Other systems: migratory animals are affected at this and higher levels; aurora is commonly visible at high latitudes (northern Michigan and Maine)**	Kp=5	1700 per cycle (900 days per cycle)

* Based on this measure, but other physical measures are also considered.

** For specific locations around the globe, use geomagnetic latitude to determine likely sightings (see www.sec.noaa.gov/Aurora).

Solar Radiation Storms(Particle Events)		Flux level of ≥ 10 Mev particles(ions)*	Number of events when flux level was met**
S5	Extreme	10^5	4 per cycle (4 days per cycle)
S4	Severe	10^4	100 per cycle (60 days per cycle)
S3	Strong	10^3	200 per cycle (130 days per cycle)
S2	Moderate	10^2	600 per cycle (360 days per cycle)
S1	Minor	10	1700 per cycle (900 days per cycle)

* Flux levels are 5 minute averages. Flux in particles·s⁻¹·ster⁻¹·cm⁻² Based on this measure, but other physical measures are also considered.

** These events can last more than one day.

*** High energy particle measurements (>100 MeV) are a better indicator of radiation risk to passenger and crews. Pregnant women are particularly susceptible.

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Radio Blackouts (Solar Flares)		GOES X-ray peak brightness by class and by flux*	Number of events when flux level was met;(number of storm days)
R5	Extreme	HF Radio: Complete HF (high frequency**) radio blackout on the entire sunlit side of the Earth lasting for a number of hours. This results in no HF radio contact with mariners and en route aviators in this sector. Navigation: Low-frequency navigation signals used by maritime and general aviation systems experience outages on the sunlit side of the Earth for many hours, causing loss in positioning. Increased satellite navigation errors in positioning for several hours on the sunlit side of Earth, which may spread into the night side.	X20 (2×10^{-3}) 4 per cycle (4 days per cycle)
R4	Severe	HF Radio: HF radio communication blackout on most of the sunlit side of Earth for one to two hours. HF radio contact lost during this time. Navigation: Outages of low-frequency navigation signals cause increased error in positioning for one to two hours. Minor disruptions of satellite navigation possible on the sunlit side of Earth.	X10 (10^{-3}) 100 per cycle (60 days per cycle)
R3	Strong	HF Radio: Wide area blackout of HF radio communication, loss of radio contact for about an hour on sunlit side of Earth. Navigation: Low-frequency navigation signals degraded for about an hour.	X1 (10^{-4}) 200 per cycle (130 days per cycle)
R2	Moderate	HF Radio: Limited blackout of HF radio communication on sunlit side, loss of radio contact for tens of minutes. Navigation: Degradation of low-frequency navigation signals for tens of minutes.	M5 (5×10^{-5}) 600 per cycle (360 days per cycle)
R1	Minor	HF Radio: Weak or minor degradation of HF radio communication on sunlit side, occasional loss of radio contact. Navigation: Low-frequency navigation signals degraded for brief intervals.	M1 (10^{-5}) 1700 per cycle (900 days per cycle)

* Flux, measured in the 0.1-0.8 nm range, in $W \cdot m^{-2}$. Based on this measure, but other physical measures are also considered.

** Other frequencies may also be affected by these conditions.

URL: www.sec.noaa.gov/NOAAAScales

2.3.5. Substorm

Substorms are brief (2-3 hour) magnetospheric disturbances that occur when the IMF turns southward, permitting interplanetary and terrestrial magnetic field lines to merge at the dayside magnetopause and energy to be transferred from the solar wind to the magnetosphere.

Figure 2.23. :The substorm cartoon is from W. Baumjohann and R.A. Treumann, *Basic Space Plasma Physics*, 1996. The three auroral images were obtained with the IMAGE WIC instrument.

The storage of some of this energy in the Earth's magnetotail constitutes the first of the three phases of the substorm, the “*growth phase*”.

During the second phase, the substorm “*expansion phase*”, the energy stored in the tail is released when the field lines in the inner magnetosphere relax from their stretched, tail-like configuration and “snap” back into a more dipolar configuration. This process, known as *depolarization*^{*}, results in the energization of charged particles in the plasma sheet and their injection deeper into the inner magnetosphere. It is not known what triggers substorm expansion, although several theories have been proposed.

The third phase is the “*recovery phase*”, during which the magnetosphere returns to its quiet state. The storage and release of energy in the magnetosphere during a substorm leads to characteristic changes in auroral morphology and emission intensity and to the enhancement of currents flowing in the polar ionosphere and associated disturbances in the strength of the high-latitude surface magnetic field.

^{*}Magnetic field depolarization is a sudden change of the magnetic field structure, from a stretched configuration (tail-like) toward a dipolar configuration, and is observed associated with fast plasma flows.

Substorms occur, on the average, six times a day; they occur more frequently, and are more intense, during geomagnetic storms.

The following figure (2.24) shows a model of substorm expansion phase onset and Pi2s. The braking of high-speed ion flows in the near-Earth central plasma sheet, at the boundary between regions of dipolar and tail-like field, produce the substorm current wedge and compressional pulses, which lead to *Pi2 pulsations** at high and low latitudes respectively.

Figure 2.24.Schematic diagram of the modified near-Earth neutral line substorm model (Shiokawa et al., 1998).

Substorms are distinct from geomagnetic storms in that the latter take place over a period of several days, observable from anywhere on Earth, injects a large number of ions into the outer radiation belt, and are rare occurrences. Substorms, on the other hand, take place over a period of a few hours, are observable primarily at the polar regions, do not inject many particles into the radiation belt, and are relatively frequent, often occurring only a few hours apart from each other.

 Pi2 pulsations are impulsive, damped geomagnetic field oscillations, which occur at the time of magnetospheric substorm onsets and intensifications.

Also, the sources of the magnetic disturbances during full storms are the ring current, whereas the sources of magnetic disturbances during substorms are in the ionosphere.

2.3.6. Geomagnetic pulsation (ULF waves)

Solar activity is carried out into the solar system by the solar wind. The solar wind interacts with the Earth's magnetic field and generates measurable ground level and atmospheric effects. For example, from the Earth's surface, we observe in near to real time the *Ultra-Low Frequency* (ULF) geomagnetic field line resonances known as "*pulsations*". So geomagnetic pulsations could be considered as the magnetic signatures of ULF waves in the Earth's magnetosphere.

Observations of pulsations help remotely diagnose activity occurring in the plasmasphere, for example, the density variations in the plasma that can disrupt satellite communications. Pulsation frequency is considered to be "ultra" low when it is lower than the natural frequencies of the plasma, like plasma frequency and the ion gyrofrequency. Geomagnetic pulsations were first observed in the ground-based measurements of the 1859 Great Aurora events (Stewart, 1861).

Waves of different frequencies and polarizations originate in different regions of the magnetosphere. The location of the projections of these regions onto the Earth depends on the solar wind dynamic pressure and magnetic field. The occurrence of various waves also depends on conditions in the solar wind and in the magnetosphere.

Changes in orientation of the IMF or an increase in solar wind velocity can have dramatic effects on the type of waves seen at a particular location on the Earth. Similarly, the occurrence of a magnetospheric substorm or magnetic storm will affect which waves are seen.

The magnetosphere is a resonant cavity and waveguide for waves that either originate within or propagate through the system. These cavities respond to broadband sources by resonating at discrete frequencies. These cavity modes couple to field line resonances that drive currents in the ionosphere. These currents reradiate the energy as electromagnetic waves that propagate to the ground. Because these ionospheric currents are localized in latitude there are very rapid variations in wave phase at the Earth's surface. Thus it is almost

never correct to assume that plane ULF waves are incident on the Earth from outer space.

The properties of ULF waves seen at the ground contain information about the processes that generate them and the regions through which they have propagated. The properties also depend on the conductivity of the Earth underneath the observer.

In 1963, *International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy* (IAGA) committee classified ULF waves using a system dependent on waveform and wave period (Jacobs et al., 1964). Oscillations with quasi-sinusoidal waveform, of a regular and mainly continuous character, were called *pulsations continuous* (Pc). Those with wave forms that are more irregular were called *pulsations irregular* (Pi). Each major type was subdivided into period bands that roughly isolate a specific type of pulsation. Today it is known that the limits of these bands are not precise, and that more than one process produces waves in a particular band. ULF waves are created by a variety of processes in magnetized plasma. The definitions of these frequency bands are shown in Table (2.5).

Table .2.5. Classifications of the geomagnetic pulsations of periods and frequencies.

Type	Notation	Period Range (sec)	Frequency range (mHz)
<i>Continuous Pulsations</i> (Pc)	Pc1	0.2-5	200 - 5000
	Pc2	5-10	100 - 200
	Pc3	10-45	22.2 - 100
	Pc4	45-150	6.7 - 22.2
	Pc5	150-600	1.7 - 6.7
	Pc6	> 600	< 1.7
<i>Irregular Pulsations</i> (Pi)	Pi1	1 - 40	25 - 1000
	Pi2	40-150	6.7 - 25
	Pi3	> 150	< 6.7

Two processes transform the ULF wave energy that enters the magnetosphere from outside. One is called *field line resonance* and the other *cavity resonance*. The most common source of ULF wave energy on the ground is field line resonances. A variety of internal plasma instabilities can also generate ULF waves. The frequencies of these waves tend to be controlled by properties of the charged particle distributions that provide the energy.

Many of the ULF waves generated internally in the magnetosphere are associated with either substorms or magnetic storms. The reason is that these processes create distributions of charged particle pressure, energy, and pitch angle that are unstable to the creation of various types of waves.

Impulsive ULF waves, Pi2s, with periods of 40–150 s are observed at the onset of auroral substorms, in the magnetosphere (Saito, 1969; Olson, 1999; Yumoto et al., 2001). These Pi2 pulsations are believed to be generated by a sudden change in magnetospheric configuration or convection during the expansion phase onset. This change may be caused by a sudden generation of the substorm current wedge, SCW, (McPherron et al., 1973) with field-aligned currents, FACs, between the polar ionosphere and the magnetospheric plasmashet in association with the disruption of cross-tail currents (Yumoto, 1986, 1988) and earthward plasma flows (Kepkp and Kivelson, 1999) from the reconnection region, see figures 2.25, 2.26 and 2.27.

Pi2 waves are commonly observed across many hours of local time, and hence their occurrence cannot be used to identify any localized ionospheric region associated with substorm initiation.

High latitude Pi2 pulsation in the mid-night region (23-00 LT) must show one-to-one correspondence with onsets of auroral substorms. This means that at the moment of substorm onset, there is a sudden formation of field-aligned coupling between the magnetosphere and ionosphere.

Figure 2.25.Schematic model showing the field-aligned and ionospheric currents.

Figure 2.26. Illustration of plasma flow within the magnetosphere (convection) driven by magnetic reconnection. The inset shows the positions of the feet of field lines in the northern high-latitude ionosphere and the corresponding plasma flows, an anti-sunward flow in the polar cap, and a return flow at lower latitudes.

Figure 2.27. Diversion of the cross-tail current through the midnight ionosphere to form the substorm current wedge [Ritter and Lüehr, 2008].

3 Physics of the Earth's Ionosphere

The ionosphere is a region of the Earth's atmosphere where significant numbers of free electrons and ions are present. The free electrons and ions are produced via ionization of the neutrals by means of solar radiation (photons) and collisions with energetic particles (solar wind) that penetrate the upper atmosphere. The ionization produced by solar wind is usually small compared with that produced by photons, and this source of ionization, SW, only plays a role at polar latitudes. In this chapter, we will only consider solar ionizing radiation (solar extreme ultraviolet and X-ray radiations) in the formation of ionospheric plasma in the Earth's atmosphere by *photoionization* of the neutral atmospheric gases. This is what we called *Ionosphere Formation Theory*.

The ionosphere of the Earth consists of weakly ionized gas. No more than about a fraction of the order of 10^{-3} of the atmospheric molecules is ionized. This means that the mass of neutrals surpasses overwhelmingly that of ions and electrons, and the result is that neutrals also have a major effect on the motion of the ionized species, whereas the effect of the latter ones on neutrals is weak or slow, at least. As a result of ion chemistry, the ionosphere consists of ions of several species, and relative abundances of different ion species varies with altitude. A simplified picture of ionospheric plasma dynamics is obtained by considering that the atmosphere consists of neutral molecules, ions and electrons occupying the same volume.

3.1. Continuity equations

Separate continuity equations are valid for all three gas species. Since only a very small fraction of neutrals is ionized, the continuity equation of the neutral molecules is not altered by ionization and written as

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\partial n u) = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

where n and u are the density and velocity of the neutral molecules, respectively.

Since ions and electrons are continuously created by ionization and they also disappear in recombination producing neutral molecules, the continuity equations for these particles is

$$\frac{\partial n_{i,e}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_{i,e} V_{i,e}) = q - l \quad (3.2)$$

where q and l are the production and loss rates per unit volume and n_i , n_e , V_i , V_e are the densities and velocities of the ions and electrons respectively. Since we assume all ions are singly ionized, the production and loss rates for ions and electrons are the same. The production term (q) is determined by the density and properties of the neutral molecules as well as the ionizing radiation and the detailed ionization process. The loss rate (l) depends on the electron / ion densities and the rate coefficients of the recombination processes.

3.2. Momentum equation

For the neutrals, the following momentum equation is valid,

$$n \left[(u \cdot \nabla) u + \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \right] = f \quad (3.3)$$

where (f) is a force density (the force per unit volume). In most cases, however, we do not solve it but simply assume a neutral wind velocity u remains unaltered. This is a reasonable approximation, because collisions with the dilute ion and electron gas can change the neutral velocity only very slowly.

The momentum equations for ions and electrons in a gravitational field are

$$n_i m_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + V_i \cdot \nabla \right) V_i = n_i m_i g + e n_i (E + V_i \times B) - \nabla p_i - n_i m_i v_i (V_i - u) \quad (3.4)$$

$$n_e m_e \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + V_e \cdot \nabla \right) V_e = n_e m_e g + e n_e (E + V_e \times B) - \nabla p_e - n_e m_e v_e (V_e - u) \quad (3.5)$$

Here E is electric field, B is magnetic induction, p_i and p_e are the pressures of the ion and electron gas, and the ion-neutral and electron-neutral collision frequencies are denoted by v_i and v_e , respectively. Because force densities

due to collisions between ions and electrons are necessarily much smaller than the force densities due to collisions with neutrals, these terms are dropped out from the very beginning.

The momentum equations are greatly simplified, if the plasma is in a stationary and homogeneous state, no gravitational field is present, and the neutral air is at rest. Then the momentum equation for the ion gas is:

$$e(E + V_i \times B) - m_i v_i (V_i - u) = 0. \quad (3.6)$$

3.3. Absorption of ionizing radiation

Photons associated to solar UV, EUV, and X radiation collide with the neutral molecules in Earth's upper atmosphere resulting in absorption of energy by these molecules.

The absorbed energy may lead to three important processes: *photodissociation*, *photoionization*, and the combination of these two, *dissociative photoionization* (Prolss, 2004).

The absorption processes of interest are:

1) *Photodissociation* ($\lambda \leq 242 \text{ nm}$)

2) *Photoionization* ($\lambda \leq 103 \text{ nm}$)

3) *Dissociative Photoionization* ($\lambda \leq 72 \text{ nm}$)

Absorption of solar radiation has a significant influence on the properties of the upper atmosphere. For instance, the photodissociation process produces atomic oxygen which not only changes the chemical composition of the upper atmosphere but also its absorption characteristics. Photoionization causes the upper atmosphere to transform into a conducting medium. During absorption

processes heat is generated, which raises the temperature of the upper atmosphere significantly.

The different gas particles are dissociated or ionized only by a certain minimum of amount of energy from incident photons. Therefore, dissociation and ionization processes of different gases are performed by different wavelengths. This implies that the depth of penetration of incident solar radiation into Earth's atmosphere depends on wavelength. Figure 3.1 shows the depth of vertically incident solar radiation penetration into the atmosphere as a function of wavelength.

Figure 3.1: A typical representation of the depth of penetration of vertically incident solar radiation into the atmosphere.

For $\lambda > 3100 \text{ Å}$, the radiation reaches the ground, but for $\lambda \in [2000 \text{ Å}, 3000 \text{ Å}]$ all radiation is absorbed by photodissociation of *ozone* at about 40 km , for $\lambda \in [1000 \text{ Å}, 1700 \text{ Å}]$ is absorbed by photodissociation of O_2 around 100 km altitude, and photoionization of the upper atmosphere above 90 km is caused by the portion of the spectrum with $\lambda < 1400 \text{ Å}$ approximately.

In the following we will derive the *ionization production function* in the atmosphere. Let the intensity of the solar photon radiation at wavelength λ be $I(\lambda, z)$ in units of photons $m^{-2} s^{-1}$ at an altitude z . Assume a slab with an area A and thickness ds , perpendicular to the incident radiation (Fig. 3.2). The number of neutral molecules in the slab is $n A ds$, where n is the number density of the neutral molecules (single species assumed). Then the total absorption cross section of the slab is $\sigma n A ds$, where σ is the absorption

cross section of a single molecule. The number of photons incident to the slab per unit time is $I A$, and the number of absorbed photons per unit time is $I \sigma n A ds$. The decrease of intensity (dI) is given by the number of absorbed photons per unit time divided by the area A .

$$dI = -n\sigma I ds. \quad (3.12)$$

Figure 3.2: Absorption of incident radiation in the vertical direction

Therefore; If the ionization enters the atmosphere at a zenith angle χ , then;

$$ds = -\frac{dz}{\cos \chi} = -\sec \chi dz. \quad (3.13)$$

Then eq. (3.12) gives

$$\frac{dI}{I} = -\sigma n ds = \sigma n \sec \chi dz \quad (3.14)$$

where $\sec \chi = 1/\cos \chi$. Using the notation I_∞ for the intensity at infinity ($z = \infty$), we then obtain

$$\int_{I_\infty}^I \frac{dI}{I} = \sigma \sec \chi \int_\infty^z n(z) dz. \quad (3.15)$$

The integration gives

$$I(z) = I_\infty \exp \left[-\sigma \sec \chi \int_z^\infty n(z) dz \right] = I_\infty \exp(-\sigma \sec \chi N_T) = I_\infty \exp(-\tau) \quad (3.16)$$

where N_T is the total number of neutral particles from height z to infinity per unit area and the *optical depth* τ is defined by

$$\tau(z) = \sigma \sec \chi N_T(z). \quad (3.17)$$

A large value of τ corresponds to strongly absorbing and optically thick gas volume, while a small value of τ indicates a weakly absorbing and optically thin gas volume. The absorption depends on wavelength and altitude so that each wavelength will have its own optical depth.

The real atmosphere is composed of different neutral particles, and each particle species has a different cross section and density. Therefore, in a multicomponent atmosphere, eq. (3.15) can be written as;

$$\int_{\infty}^I \frac{dI}{I} = \sec \chi \sum_j \sigma_j \int_{\infty}^z n_j(z) dz. \quad (3.18)$$

Here n_j and σ_j are the particle density and absorption cross section of gas species j , respectively. This gives

$$I(z) = I_{\infty} \exp \left[\sec \chi \sum_j \sigma_j \int_{\infty}^z n_j(z) dz \right] = I_{\infty} \exp(-\tau), \quad (3.19)$$

where the *optical depth* is

$$\tau(\lambda, z) = \sec \chi \sum_j \sigma_j(\lambda) \int_z^{\infty} n_j(z) dz. \quad (3.20)$$

3.4. Ionization rate

The classical theory of ionospheric ionization by means of photoionization was presented by Chapman. His equation is now known as *Chapman's formula* or *Chapman production function* for the rate of ion production with respect to height (Tascione, 1994). To obtain the classical Chapman formula for the ion production rate q , the theory assumes that the atmosphere is isothermal and obeys the hydrostatic equation so that the scale height H is

independent of altitude. So from now on we write H instead of $H(z)$. We also assume that the atmosphere is composed of a single neutral species and the absorption cross section is constant. Constant cross section is equivalent to assuming monochromatic radiation.

It was concluded above that the total number of photons absorbed per unit time in a slab with an area A and thickness ds is $I \sigma n A ds$. Hence the total number of photons absorbed per unit volume per unit time is $n \sigma I$. However, not all their energy goes to the ionization process. The *ionization efficiency* η is the number of photoelectrons produced per photon absorbed.

Then the number of photo-electrons produced per unit volume per unit time, the ionization rate q (called also the *ion production function*), can be expressed as;

$$q = \eta n \sigma I = \eta n \sigma I_{\infty} \exp \left[-\sigma \sec \chi \int_z^{\infty} n(z) dz \right]. \quad (3.21)$$

Instead of eq. (2.12), we write the neutral density profile (assuming an isothermal atmosphere) as;

$$n(z) = n_m \exp \left(-\frac{z - z_m}{H} \right) = n_m e^{-h}, \quad (3.22)$$

where n_m is the molecular density at the reference height z_m and $h = (z - z_m) / H$ is the distance from the reference height, scaled by H . Then,

$$\int_z^{\infty} n(z) dz = H n(z) = H n_m e^{-h}, \quad (3.23)$$

and the ionization rate, eq (3.21), is

$$q(\chi, h) = \eta I_{\infty} \sigma n_m e^{-h} \exp[-\sigma \sec \chi H n_m e^{-h}], \quad (3.24)$$

$$= \frac{\eta I_{\infty} \sigma H n_m}{H} \exp[-h - \sigma \sec \chi H n_m e^{-h}]. \quad (3.25)$$

The expression is still simplified if we choose a reference height such that

$$\sigma H n_m = 1. \quad (3.26)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 q(\chi, h) &= \frac{\eta I_{\infty}}{H} \exp[-h - \sec \chi e^{-h}] \\
 &= \frac{\eta I_{\infty}}{H e} \exp[1 - h - \sec \chi e^{-h}] \\
 &\quad \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}}_{q_m}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{q(\chi, h) = q_m \exp[1 - h - \sec \chi e^{-h}],} \tag{3.27}$$

where

$$q_m = \frac{\eta I_{\infty}}{H e} \tag{3.28}$$

If we choose a height variable $h' = h - \ln \sec \chi$, we obtain:

$$\boxed{q(\chi, h) = \underbrace{q_m \cos \chi}_{q_{max}} \cdot \exp[1 - h' - e^{-h}].} \tag{3.29}$$

In terms of variable h' , the ionization rate can be presented for all zenith angles χ with a single shape, which only has a scaling factor $\cos \chi$ for different zenith angles. The expressions in eqs. (3.27) or (3.29) are called the *Chapman production function*.

Since n increases and I decreases as we go down in altitude, the ion production rate q has necessarily a maximum at some altitude. From eq. (2.25) we can show that the maximum value is encountered at an altitude,

$$h'_{max} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad h_{max} = \ln \sec \chi \tag{3.30}$$

and the maximum value is

$$q_{max} = q_m \cos \chi. \tag{3.31}$$

This shows that the maximum production is encountered at $\chi = 0$, i.e. when the sun is shining overhead. Then also the maximum is encountered at lowest altitudes.

When the zenith angle increases, the maximum raises at higher altitudes and the maximum value decreases (see Fig.3.3).

Figure 3.3. Chapman production profiles for different solar zenith angles (Van Zandt and Knecht, 1964).

Figure 3.3 illustrates the ionization rate profiles for different zenith angles χ . The profiles have the same shape but the height of the peak increases with increasing zenith angle.

It is obvious that, when the zenith angle is high enough, the curvature of the Earth and the atmosphere should be taken into account and the theory should be modified by considering a spherical stratification in the idealized atmosphere. This is because, if the atmosphere would be flat, the ray path in the atmosphere would approach to infinity when the elevation angle would approach zero.

At very large values of h ($z \gg z_m$) the profile takes the form;

$$q = q_{m_0} \exp\left(-\frac{z}{H}\right) \quad (3.32)$$

So that well above the maximum the ionization rate profile decays with height in the same way as the atmospheric density. This holds for $h > 2$, i.e. at distances more than two scale heights above z_m . This relation arises because at these heights the intensity of the radiation is only weakly reduced, and the rate of production is essentially proportional to the gas density (see Chapman, 1931a; Chapman, 1931b; Davies, 1989).

Much more effort is required to account properly for the spherical shell form of the atmosphere. This can be carried out by introducing the so-called *Chapman grazing incidence function* $Ch(\chi, h)$ that its detailed derivation is given in (Chapman, 1931a). The Chapman grazing incidence function is a measure of the depth of atmosphere (or absorption of ionizing radiation by atmosphere) as a function of the solar zenith angle and height (Chapman, 1931b).

In order to determine the vertical profile of the rate of ion production in the real upper atmosphere, the Chapman production function must be modified. First, the upper atmosphere consists of several gases rather than a single gas. Therefore, $\sigma n(h)$ in equation 3.24 must be replaced by a sum of the products accounting for the contributions from the various gas particles. Furthermore, because the incident solar radiation is polychromatic rather than monochromatic, it is necessary to add up the different contributions from the individual wavelengths. Accordingly, equation 3.24 becomes the following form for real upper atmosphere:

$$q(\chi, h) \approx \sum_{\lambda} \sum_{i=O, N_2, O_2} \eta_i \sigma_i n_i I_{\infty}(\lambda) \exp \left\{ -Ch(\chi, h) \sum_{j=O, N_2, O_2} \eta_j \sigma_j n_j H_j \right\} \quad (3.33)$$

where \sum_{λ} indicates a summation over the different wavelengths of interest and $\sum_{i=O, N_2, O_2}$ and $\sum_{j=O, N_2, O_2}$ are summations over the gas particles of the upper atmosphere (only the most important gases are considered). Note that the upper atmosphere is surely not isothermal, but considering non-isothermal condition is too complicated to be considered in the analytical calculations.

3.5. Recombination

Each ion in the ionosphere has a finite lifetime: either it is destroyed by ionic chemical reactions or after a certain time it is recombined with an electron, returning to the neutral state. Once electrons are produced by solar radiation in the upper atmosphere, there are three principal reactions in which electrons may disappear after some time:

- *Radiative recombination* (an electron combines with an atomic positive ion):

- *Dissociative recombination* (an electron combines with a molecular ion):

- *Attachment* (an electron attach to a neutral particles and produce negative ion):

The probability of the radiative recombination reaction is low because of the demand put by simultaneous conservation of energy and momentum, whereas those of the dissociative recombination reaction are more easily satisfied by this reaction. So, since the radiative recombination is a much slower process than dissociative recombination, the greater part of electrons tends to recombine with positive molecular ions (Gran, 1965).

The attachment process only occurs in lower altitudes of the ionosphere, where more neutral particles are available, to form negative ions (D-region). The negative ions are in turn rapidly neutralized by further reactions, so that loss of electrons by the attachment can be neglected.

In this section we will discuss the loss term which, together with production, determines the electron density profile (n_e) in the absence of transport. When the convection term in the continuity equation is neglected and assuming *photochemical equilibrium* i.e. production and loss are in balance, then

$$q_i = l_i \quad \& \quad n_i = n_e. \quad (3.37)$$

1) for the electrons loss by Recombination;

- If ONLY the *dissociative recombination* is considered, the recombination rate of ions and electrons can be computed as follows.

The probability (l_i) of a single electron to be recombined must be proportional to the ion density n_i , since recombination implies that the electron must hit an ion.

The number of electrons lost per unit volume and unit time (l_i) must also be proportional to the number of electrons which can recombine, which is proportional to electron density (n_e).

Since the electron and ion densities are identical ($n_e = n_i$), the loss term must be;

$$l_i = \alpha n_e^2 \quad (3.38)$$

where α is known as *quadratic recombination coefficient* or *reaction coefficient*, which varies only weakly with height via its temperature dependence (Prolss, 2004).

Magnitudes of the reaction coefficients for dissociative recombination are of the order of $10^{-13} \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ and for the radiative recombination $10^{-18} \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$. These numbers indicate that dissociative recombination is much faster than radiative recombination.

When the Chapman production function is inserted in the photochemical equilibrium and a dissociative recombination is assumed, the result is

$$\alpha n_e^2 = q = q_m \exp[1 - h - \sec \chi e^{-h}]. \quad (3.39)$$

The electron density solved from this equation is

$$n_e = \underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\alpha}}}_{n(0)_{max}} \exp\left[\frac{1}{2}(1 - h - \sec \chi e^{-h})\right]. \quad (3.40)$$

In which $n(0)_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\alpha}} = \sqrt{\frac{\eta I_\infty}{H e \alpha}}$ is the peak electron density with the sun overhead ($\chi = 0$).

This electron density profile is called the *Chapman α -profile* or *Chapman model*. It is representative of the ionospheric E-region where the most common ions are O_2^+ and NO^+ .

When neglecting the height variations of α (actually α does not depend directly on height but on temperature), we find that the peak electron density for a given solar zenith angle is occurred when $e^{-h} = \cos \chi$ in eq. (3.40);

$$n(\chi)_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\alpha}} \sqrt{\cos \chi} = n(0)_{max} \sqrt{\cos \chi} \quad (3.41)$$

2) For the electron loss by attachments to a molecule;

If electrons are lost by attachment to a molecule

the electron loss rate (l_e) is only proportional to n_e and can be expressed as

$$l_e = \beta n_e, \quad (3.43)$$

where β is the *attachment coefficient*, proportional to the density of neutral molecules, n_M . In this case the plasma consists of electrons and positive and negative ions, and the positive ion density is the sum of electron and negative ion densities.

In equilibrium the electron density profile is given by:

$$n_e = \frac{q_m}{\beta} \exp[1 - h - \sec \chi e^{-h}]. \quad (3.44)$$

If we again neglect height variations in β (which is NOT a good assumption since the density of neutral molecules decreases with height), the maximum electron density will be;

$$n_m = \frac{q_m}{\beta} \cos \chi. \quad (3.45)$$

This is called the *Chapman β -profile*.

Note that;

In D-region, production of negative ions takes place (where ion chemistry is complicated).

In E-region, dissociative recombination with molecular ions is the most important loss mechanism for electrons.

In F2-region, loss mechanisms associated with atomic oxygen ions dominate.

In F1-region ($F2 > F1 > E$), both dissociative recombination and a reaction containing atomic oxygen ions are active and one of them dominates, depending on the values of reaction rate coefficients.

3.6. Transport processes in the ionosphere

The Earth's external magnetic field plays a key role in the charged particles transport in the ionosphere. This is because of the fact that the Earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere are closely linked together via magnetic field lines and strong interactions between the field lines and the charged particles result in the capture of the particles and impose restrictions for their motion in the ionosphere. In the ionosphere, charged particles transportations are mainly related to the process of diffusion in a gravity field, and to thermospheric winds and electric fields (Davies, 1989).

3.6.1. Charged particle motion in electro-magnetic field

The motion of a charged particle in a magnetic and electric fields is described by the Lorentz equation (Walt, 1994)

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = q(\vec{v} \times \vec{B} + \vec{E}) \quad (3.46)$$

where \vec{F} is the force in Newton, q is the charge in Coulomb, \vec{E} is the electric field in *Volt/m*, \vec{B} is the magnetic field in Tesla and \vec{v} is the velocity in *m/s*. Equation 3.46 can be separated into two components, parallel and perpendicular to the magnetic field giving

$$\vec{F}_{\parallel} = m \frac{d\vec{v}_{\parallel}}{dt} = q\vec{E}_{\parallel} \quad (3.47)$$

$$\vec{F}_{\perp} = m \frac{d\vec{v}_{\perp}}{dt} = q(\vec{v}_{\perp} \times \vec{B} + \vec{E}_{\perp}) \quad (3.48)$$

Equation 3.47 is the usual equation for describing the motion of a charged particle in an electric field. In equation 3.48, the magnitude and direction of the magnetic force is a function of the velocity, therefore the solution of equation 3.48 is complicated when the magnetic field is not uniform. For simplicity, we consider only a uniform magnetic field and the solution of equation 3.48 is described only for following two cases:

I) In the absence of an external electric field $\vec{E}_{\perp} = 0$, the velocity \vec{v}_{\parallel} along the magnetic field lines is constant according to equation 3.47 and the acceleration $d\vec{v}_{\perp}/dt$ in equation 3.48 must be perpendicular to \vec{v}_{\perp} , so that also $\|\vec{v}_{\perp}\| = \text{constant}$. Therefore, the trajectory of the charged particle in a uniform magnetic field with no electric field is a *helix* (see figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Charged particle motion in a uniform magnetic field ($\vec{E}_\perp = 0$).

The projection of the helix on to a plane perpendicular to magnetic field line is a circle with radius equal $m \vec{v}_\perp / q B$, which is the so called *Larmor radius*. The angular frequency of this gyration motion is $\omega = \vec{v}_\perp / r$ in *radian/s*, which is called the *angular gyro-frequency*. The direction of the magnetic force depend on the charge, therefore the direction of the circular motion for positively charged particles is opposite to that for negatively charged particles.

II) The presence of an external electric field, $\vec{E}_\perp \neq 0$, results in a drift motion of the charged particles in the geomagnetic field. The force $q \vec{E}_\perp$ which is perpendicular to \vec{B} , results into a drift of charged particles in a direction is perpendicular to both \vec{B} and \vec{E} . The drift velocity is obtained by

$$\vec{v}_{Drift} = \frac{\vec{E}_\perp \times \vec{B}}{\|\vec{B}\|^2}. \quad (3.49)$$

The drift velocity is charge independent. Therefore, both ions and electrons move together (*ambipolar*) with the same velocity in the same direction perpendicular to both magnetic and electric fields (see figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5: Drift motion in a uniform magnetic field ($\vec{E}_\perp \neq 0$).

3.6.2. Plasma diffusion

The Earth's gravitational force causes a downward motion of the ions and electrons in the ionospheric plasma. In the other direction, the vertical pressure gradient force induces an upward motion of the ions and electrons. Since charged particles are only free to move parallel along the geomagnetic field, the forces must be mapped along the geomagnetic field lines in order to compute the total flux or *diffusion speed* of the ions and electrons (see figure 3.6).

The expression for the diffusion speed of ions and electrons along geomagnetic field line, under the ambipolar approximation that the ions and electrons move together with the same velocity, is given by (Davies, 1989)

$$v = -D(h) \sin I \left(\frac{1}{n_e} \frac{\partial n_e}{\partial h} + \frac{M g}{2kT} \right) \quad (3.50)$$

where M and T are respectively the ion mass and temperature, $D(h)$ is plasma (or ambipolar) diffusion coefficient, n_e is electron density, I is geomagnetic inclination and k is *Boltzmann's Constant*.

Since $D(h)$ is inversely proportional to the neutral density, diffusion increases rapidly at higher altitude. In equation 3.50 the first term in the bracket relates to the pressure gradient force and second term is due to the gravitational force.

Since diffusion across the magnetic field is inhibited, the vertical component of diffusion vanishes at the geomagnetic equator ($I = 0^\circ$). Vertical diffusion has a maximum at the geomagnetic poles where $I = 90^\circ$.

Figure 3.6: Plasma diffusion along geomagnetic field lines.

3.6.3. Thermospheric wind

A considerable temperature differences exist in the upper ionosphere between day and night sides of the Earth. This creates a pressure difference that drives a horizontal wind in the upper atmosphere from the dayside toward the nightside, called the *neutral wind* or *thermospheric wind*. Since the horizontal neutral wind can not move the ions and electrons across the earth's magnetic field lines, they stick to the magnetic field lines like rings on a bar; they can slide along the field lines easily but can not move across it.

If the horizontal wind is toward the equator, which occurs mainly at night in mid-latitude, the ionospheric plasma is lifted and tends to increase the ion density at higher altitudes of the ionosphere.

If the wind is toward the pole, which occurs mainly by day at mid-latitude, the plasma is lowered and tends to reduce the ion density in the higher altitudes of the ionosphere (see figure 3.7).

These effects depend on the geometry of the magnetic field and vary with latitude and the geomagnetic inclination. The plasma velocity along geomagnetic field is given by

$$v = u \cos I \tag{3.51}$$

where u is speed of the neutral wind which follows from the equation of motion by taking the horizontal pressure gradient, the inertia and viscosity of

the air, gravity, the Coriolis and centripetal accelerations due to the Earth's rotation, and ion-drag into account (Rishbeth, 1972).

Figure 3.7: Illustration of the vertical plasma transport caused by the neutral wind in the mid-latitude region.

Note that at the geomagnetic poles ($I = 90^\circ$), the thermospheric plasma velocity is non-existent.

3.6.4. Electromagnetic drift

At the dip equator, the geomagnetic field lines are horizontal ($I = 0^\circ$), and this special geometry leads to an intense current sheet, known as the *equatorial electrojet* * that flows along the dip equator and is concentrated in a strip only a few degrees wide in geomagnetic latitude (Tascione, 1994). During day time, the equatorial electrojet flows toward the east, and during night time toward the west, however the produced electric field in night time is small because of small electron concentration at night.

**Equatorial electrojet* (EEJ) is a narrow ribbon of current flowing eastward in the day time equatorial region of the Earth's ionosphere due to the neutral wind.

The presence of an eastward electric field results in an upward drift motion of the charged particles (see subsection 3.6.1) into the high altitudes (F-region).

The drift velocity is charge independent, therefore both ion and electron move together in the direction perpendicular to the magnetic field \vec{B} and the electric field \vec{E} .

This ambipolar movement of the charged particles in the ionosphere is known the *electromagnetic drift* or $\vec{E} \times \vec{B}$ drift, with velocity

$$v_{drift} = \frac{E}{B} \cos I . \quad (3.52)$$

The electromagnetic drift is the main mechanism that can cause plasma to move across magnetic field lines at high ionospheric altitudes (see figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8: Electromagnetic drift caused by the west-to-East electric field

3.7. Ionospheric stratification

Above the *turbopause** - which typically starts at 80 km- in the Earth's atmosphere, the density of each atmospheric component reduces exponentially with height. The reduction depends on the scale height H (see subsection 2.1.1).

*The **turbopause** marks the altitude in the Earth's atmosphere below which turbulent mixing dominates. The region below the turbopause is known as the homosphere, where the chemical constituents are well mixed and display identical height distributions.

Since scale height is inversely proportional to the mass of the component and proportional to the temperature, the relative concentration of components is a function of height, and in high altitudes the lightest components become predominant (Banks, 1969).

According to sections 3.3 and 3.4, the photoionization and photodissociation of the atmospheric components are caused by various parts of the solar UV spectrum. The absorption of the solar incidence energy depends on the absorption cross-sections, or more accurately on the ionization cross-section (see equation 3.12). Consequently, because of the height dependency of the composition and the absorption characteristics of the atmosphere, the Earth's ionosphere has a tendency to be horizontally stratified at all latitudes, so that different ionospheric regions are formed. The term regions is preferred rather than layers because the boundary transitions are not distinct. The ionospheric regions not only differ from the predominant ion composition point of view, but also their formation mechanisms are not the same. From the composition point of view, the ionosphere can be divided into four main ionized regions: the D, E, F and topside regions in order of increasing altitude.

In the following sections these ionospheric regions are explained. Note that the heights given in the following sections should only be considered as indication only.

3.7.1. D-Region

The lowermost region of the ionosphere, below a height of roughly $< 90 \text{ km}$, is called the *D-region*. It has comparatively weak electron density that develops shortly after sunrise and disappears shortly after sunset. In the D-region the primary source of photoionization is solar X-rays, causing ionization of the major neutral gases N_2 and O_2 , and strong solar the Lyman- α radiation (wavelength $\lambda = 1216 \text{ \AA}$) causing ionization of the nitric oxide NO. As can be seen from figure 3.1, the Lyman- α wavelength can penetrate to heights of the D-region with little absorption at high altitudes. However, the vertical profile of the electron density in the D-region does not have a typical maximum (Hunsucker and Hargreaves, 2003).

Since the neutral gas density is relatively large in the D-region, collision with electrons are more frequent resulting in negative ions (mostly O_2^-) due to attachment (see subsection 3.6). This O_2^- can react with other particles to produce other kind of negative ions. The distinguishing feature of the D-

region is therefore the predominance of negative ions. The produced negative ions disappear either by recombination with a positive ions or by a process in which the electron is detached to become free again (Ratcliffe, 1972). The attachment and detachment of electrons occur very fast, and the electrons finally disappear mostly due to recombination with positive ions.

3.7.2. E-Region

The E-region is an ionospheric region that extends between heights typically from 90 to 170 *km*. This region of the ionosphere is dominated by O_2^+ and NO^+ ions. O_2^+ is mainly produced by photoionization of O_2 and NO^+ produced by a rapid charge exchange process .

Unlike the D-region, the ionization of the E-region remains at night due to the solar particle (or proton) radiation, though it is considerably diminished.

The collision frequency of the charged particles increased with respect to their angular gyrofrequencies in heights of the E-region (Prolss, 2004) and results in a very short lifetime of the principal ions NO^+ and O_2^+ (about 10 second). Because of the high collision frequency, the transport of the charged particles also becomes quiet difficult, therefore the transport process is negligible in the E-region as compared with the other two photochemical processes (Tascione, 1994; Ivanov-Kholodny and Mikhailov, 1986; Schunk and Nagy, 2000; Titheridge, 2000).

The main consequence of this condition is that the *conductivity* of the ionosphere is increased in this region and reaches to maximum value in height about 100 *km*, which leads to possibility of the electric currents and the formation of the central *dynamo layer* or the *conducting plasma layer*. In the E-region, NO^+ and O_2^+ disappear principally by dissociative recombination, that the ion loss rate is proportional to squared electron density n_e^2 . Because of this, under geomagnetically quiet condition, the vertical electron density profile of the E-region is reasonably well explained by the Chapman model.

It could be said that the E-region of ionosphere is formed under *photochemical equilibrium* (ion production rate is balanced by the ion disappearance rate). The electron density has a maximum at a height about 110 *km* and the maximum electron density is typically 10^5 electrons per cubic centimeter during the day in the mid-latitudes.

Because the neutral density is greater than 10^{11} cm^{-3} , the E-region is only a weakly ionized region with respect to higher regions (Schunk and Nagy, 2000). The mean coefficient for the dissociative recombination of electrons and molecular ions (O_2^+ and NO^+) is $\alpha \approx 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$ (Titheridge, 2000).

3.7.3. F-Region

The F-region is located between 170 km and 600 km. It is divided into lower F1 (170-200 km) and upper F2 (200-600 km) sub-regions.

The F1-Region: In the F1-region, the main primary ions which are produced directly by photoionization are O^+ and N_2^+ . The most numerous is the atomic oxygen ion O^+ . Since atomic oxygen ion rarely loses its charge by the radiative recombination, indirect dissociative recombination is carried out in case of the F1-region. While in case of the E-region, dissociative recombination is carried out directly. This is the distinguishing feature between the E- and F1-regions.

In the F1-region due to the relatively high density of the neutral molecules (Oxygen and Nitrogen molecules) the loss rate is proportional to squared electron density n_e^2 . Thus, vertical electron density profile of this region is also explained reasonably well by the Chapman model. It implies that the formation mechanism of the F1-region is governed by the photochemical equilibrium. The maximum electron density of the F1-region appears as a bulge below the main peak (*F2-peak*) of vertical electron density profile of ionosphere where the height of maximum electron density of the F1-region ($h_{m,F1}$) is smaller than the transition height (h_t)^{*} (Ratcliffe, 1972; Hunsucker and Hargreaves, 2003). The bulge is called the *F1-peak* and its appearance depends on the solar cycle and the solar zenith angle.

Since $(h_t - h_{m,F1})$ is increased for small solar zenith angles, the F1-peak is more common near midday and in summer time (Ratcliffe, 1972).

The F2-Region: This is the region between roughly 200 km to 600 km which has the greatest concentration of electrons. The F2-region is the most important region from navigation and space communication point of view.

^{*}A transition height, h_t ; at which the recombination coefficient changes from quadratic (α) to linear $\beta(h)$, i.e. are equally.

It is also the region which is the most variable and the most irregular from prediction point of view. The electron concentration reaches its maximum value in the F2-region (particularly in the F2-peak) and persists during day and night times. F2-region is dominated by the atomic oxygen ion O^+ . The maximum electron density is typically 10^6 electrons per cubic centimeters, which is roughly a factor of 10 greater than that of the E-region. The neutral density (10^8 cm^{-3}) is still orders of magnitude greater than the ion density (Schunk and Nagy, 2000). Above the F2-peak, the electron density decreases exponentially with altitude.

In this region, the rate of ion production is maximized. Due to a smaller number of the neutral particles the recombination rate is proportional to the electron density n_e (see subsection 3.5). Furthermore, the collision frequency of the charge particles is less than their angular gyro-frequencies, which results in an increased lifetime of the charged particles. Therefore the transport process can not be neglected. In the F2-region, all three photochemical processes contribute simultaneously to its formation and a transition from photochemical equilibrium to diffusive equilibrium takes place (Ivanov- Kholodny and Mikhailov, 1986; Schunk and Nagy, 2000).

3.7.4. Topside region

The topside ionosphere is the region above the F2-peak extended from about 600 to 1000 *km* where atomic Oxygen ion is still dominant. In this region, the decrease in the density of neutral particles increases the coefficient of diffusion, but also decreases the production and loss rates. Consequently, the transport processes becomes the principal processes, while the processes of ionization and recombination are insignificant in the formation mechanism of the topside region. In other words, the diffusive equilibrium is dominant. The electron density decreases exponentially with altitude in the topside region.

Above the topside region, there is a region where the lighter ions (Hydrogen ion, H^+ , and Helium ion, He^+) dominate. This region of ionosphere is effectively fully ionized, is called the *plasmasphere* or the *protonosphere*. The boundary between the topside and protonosphere regions is defined as the transition from atomic oxygen to atomic hydrogen as the primary ion constituent. This transition occurs at an altitude roughly 600 to 2000 *km*.

In table 3.1, the main characteristics of the ionospheric regions are outlined. A typical profile of the vertical electron density during day time at the mid-

latitude region is shown in figure 3.9. The solid curve gives the electron density and dashed curves indicate the contributions from each region (D, E, F1, F2, and topside).

Vertical structure of the ionosphere governed by two equilibrium regimes, photochemical and diffusive, which play an important role in the formation of the ionospheric regions at different heights. The *E* and *F1*-regions are formed in photochemical equilibrium, the *topside* region is formed in diffusive equilibrium, and the *F2*-region is a transition between these two equilibriums. Here in *F2*-region, the diffusive equilibrium regime is assumed as the dominant regime.

Figure 3.9: A typical height profile of the ionospheric electron density during day time at the mid-latitude region (as the summation of the E, F1, and F2).

3.7.5. Plasmasphere

The plasmasphere refers to the ionization above the ionosphere that is trapped by closed field lines. Since ions are charged, they are constrained within flux tubes and move along the magnetic field lines.

At mid-latitudes, where the magnetic field lines are closed, the upward flowing ions become trapped and create a relatively dense plasma-filled region (mainly filled with cold hydrogen plasma of ionospheric origin) is called *plasmasphere* (Kelley, 1989; Lemair and Gringuaz, 1998).

At high-latitude, however, the magnetic field lines are open and the ions flowing upward from the ionosphere are not trapped, instead they are lost into the magnetosphere.

Because at high latitudes (above $\sim + 60^\circ$ or below $\sim - 60^\circ$ magnetic), the flux tube volumes are very large and the plasma outward flow is almost continuous, the plasma density never builds up to the values that occur at lower latitudes in the plasmasphere. The plasmasphere extends up to and beyond the altitudes of GPS satellites (20,000 Km). Hence, it can produce a significant time delay in signals that traverse through it.

Normally, the plasmasphere extends to about six to seven Earth radii. During magnetic storms, the plasmasphere compresses, and during large storms it can be compressed to as little as three Earth radii, causing the greater portion of plasma to be lost to the ionosphere. Then when quiet geomagnetic conditions return, plasma flows back upward from the ionosphere and refills the outer plasmasphere, expanding the outer boundary back to about six to seven Earth radii as shown in Figure 3.10 (Lemair and Gringuaz, 1998; Förster and Jakowski, 2000).

A good general description of the plasmasphere is given in “The Earth’s plasmasphere” by Lemair and Gringuaz (1998).

3.8. Ionosphere-Plasmasphere plasma exchange

Ionosphere-plasmasphere thermal plasma flow along the magnetic field lines is one of the most important processes that control the energy and mass exchange between the ionosphere and plasmasphere. In the region of the plasmasphere, neither significant production of ionization nor significant loss of ionization occurs.

However, the variations in electron content in the plasmasphere arise from the interchange of plasma with the underlying ionosphere (e.g., Evans, 1973; Yeh and Foster, 1990; Webb, 2000). It was found that, at mid-latitudes during daytime, the total ion flux in the topside ionosphere is generally directed upward, and its mean flow rate is of the order of $(1 - 4) \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Förster and Jakowski, 2000). The total ion flux to and from the plasmasphere may be different in different seasons of the year.

Figure 3.10. Satellite observations of ion density, showing the plasmapause location during nighttime as a function of geomagnetic activity, Kp index. L is the distance in Earth's Radii. (After Hargreaves, 1992 page 168).

In general, in the winter hemisphere the field aligned plasma flow is downward (plasmasphere to ionosphere), particularly during post midnight hours. In summer, however, the plasma flow is upward through out the night. Thus, the plasmasphere supplies ionization to the winter nighttime ionosphere whilst being maintained by the summer hemisphere ionosphere (Buonsanto, 1986; Balan et al., 1991).

The ionosphere-plasmasphere plasma exchange process may change drastically during magnetically active periods. Balan et al (1991) observed that both the downward and upward field aligned plasma flows increased with increasing magnetic activity. They also found that the duration of downward plasma flow in winter nighttime decreases with increasing solar activity, whereas the upward flow throughout summer nighttime increases with increasing solar activity.

Ch.3. Physics of the Earth's Ionosphere

Region	D	E	F1	F2	Topside	Protonosphere
Neutral Particles	N_2, O_2, NO	N_2, O_2, NO	N_2, O_2, O	N_2, O_2, O	O, H, He	H, He
Height range (km)	< 90	90 - 170	170 – 200	200 – 600	600 - 1000	1000 <
Nominal neutral electron density (m^{-3})	$10^{11} <$	10^{11}	$10^8 <$	10^8	$< 10^8$	—
Dominant ions	N_2^+, O_2^+, NO^+	O_2^+, NO^+	O^+, O_2^+, NO^+	O^+	O^+	H^+, He^+
Source of ionization	X rays, Lyman- α	X rays, charge particle radiation	X rays	X rays	X rays	X rays
Dominant photochemical process	Recombination, Photoionization, Attachment	Recombination, Photoionization	Recombination, Photoionization	Recombination, Photoionization, Transport	Transport	Transport
Type of recombination	—	Dissociative recombination	Indirect Dissociative recombination	Indirect Dissociative recombination	Radiative recombination	—
Recombination coefficient	—	Quadratic	Quadratic	Linear	Linear	—
Chapman Layer	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Appearance duration	Daytime	Daytime Nighttime	Daytime	Daytime Nighttime	Daytime Nighttime	Daytime Nighttime
Nominal daytime electron density (m^{-3})	$< 10^9$	10^{11}	2×10^{11}	10^{12}	10^{10}	10^9
Nominal height of Maximum electron density	—	110 Km	h_f	300 km	—	—
Equilibrium regime	—	Photochemical equilibrium	Photochemical equilibrium	—	Diffusive equilibrium	Diffusive equilibrium
Special feature	Negative ions (mostly O_2^-)	Maximum conductivity	—	Plasma foundation	—	Exosphere

Table 3.1: The characteristics of the ionospheric regions.

3.9. Characteristic parameters of the ionospheric regions

Every electromagnetic wave is modified during its passage through the ionosphere and its propagation direction, amplitude and velocity are changed. This is not only needs to be considered in radio communication, it can be also used to extract information about the properties of the ionospheric regions for ionospheric research. The interaction between an electromagnetic wave and the ionosphere results in the oscillation of the charge particles in the ionosphere, regardless the geomagnetic field. The angular frequency of the oscillation is given by (Dendy, 1993):

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{n e^2}{\epsilon_0 m}} \quad (3.53)$$

where n is charged particle density per cubic meter, e and m are charge and mass of the particle and ϵ_0 is the electric permittivity of vacuum (8.85×10^{-12} Farad/m).

Since the mass of an ion is much larger than that of an electron, the ions oscillate at much lower amplitude than the electrons, and so to a very good approximation the motion of the ions can be ignored. In other words, only the electrons respond to the wave. Therefore the angular frequency of electrons is generally known as the plasma frequency. As a handy rule-of-thumb $\omega_p \approx 56.4 \sqrt{n}$ or $f_p \approx 8.98 \sqrt{n}$ (Prolss, 2004).

It is well-known that the ionosphere is a *dispersive medium* and the type of interaction between a radio wave (from KHz to GHz) and the ionosphere depends on the frequency of the wave. When the frequency of a radio wave is less than the plasma frequency, the ionosphere behaves like a metallic mirror, if the frequency is larger than the plasma frequency the wave penetrates into the ionosphere without being reflected. Due to height dependency of the electron density in the ionosphere, a transmitted radio wave from the ground in vertical direction penetrates into the ionosphere up to that height where the local plasma frequency reaches the wave frequency. At this point the wave is reflected back toward the Earth (see figure 3.11).

Radio sounding using an *ionosonde* takes advantage of this property of the ionosphere to measure maximum frequency at which a wave reflects from each ionospheric region. This is known as the *critical frequency* or *peak*

plasma frequency or *maximum plasma frequency* of the region. The ionosphere does not reflect radio waves on frequencies above 30 MHz, because the electrons can not respond fast enough to changes in the electric field of those waves to reflect them back to the Earth for these high frequencies. Consequently, frequencies above 30 MHz usually penetrate the ionosphere without any reflection and are very useful for ground to space communications.

Figure 3.11: Illustration of the peak plasma frequency and the peak height.

Typically, an ionospheric region (E, F1, and F2) is generally described by the peak plasma frequency (foE , $foF1$, and $foF2$) and peak height (hmE , $hmF1$, and $hmF2$) for which the electron density decreases with altitude on both sides of peak height. The maximum or peak electron density of the ionospheric regions, which is proportional to the squared peak plasma frequencies, is denoted by NmE , $NmF1$, and $NmF2$.

3.10. Ionospheric phenomena

In addition to the general picture given in the previous sections, the ionosphere contains other phenomena with their specific mechanisms, extending from small scales of the order of meters to others of the order of hundreds or thousands of kilometers. Some of them are discussed in this section.

3.10.1. The Sq Current System and Dynamo Electric Field

The conductivity of the ionosphere varies with height and reaches a maximum about 100 km (E-region). This is known as the *central dynamo layer* or the *conducting plasma layer*. This is due to an increase of the collision frequency of the charged particles with respect to their angular gyro-frequencies. The conducting plasma layer is moved across the earth's magnetic field under the influence of mainly the sun and moon. The solar EUV radiation, is not only responsible for the ionization at low-altitudes of the ionosphere, but also heats up the atmosphere and induces the thermospheric wind and resulting horizontal atmospheric movements with period of 12 hours. The gravitational attraction of the moon results in an atmospheric tide with a period of half a lunar day.

The motion of the conducting plasma layer across the geomagnetic field generates an electric field (\vec{E}) and as a result, a system of electric currents is produced in this layer. The pattern of the currents is fixed with respect to the Sun, with the Earth rotating under it. The electric currents produced by the solar heating and lunar atmospheric tide are called Sq and L electric currents, respectively (Matsushita and Campbell, 1967). The idealized, current system is shown in figure 3.12.

On the Earth's sunward side, solar radiation heats the thermosphere near the equator causing it to expand. Subsequently, there exists a local high pressure at the equator due to the expansion and a lower pressure toward the northern and southern poles. This pressure gradient leads to neutral thermospheric winds flowing away from the equator, one toward the north pole in the northern hemisphere and another toward the south pole in the southern hemisphere. In turn, the neutral wind tends to drag the ionospheric plasma toward the poles.

Figure 3.12: Ionospheric Component of the Sq Current During Equinox (1957-1960) (Volland, 1984).

The rest of this argument will focus on the northern hemisphere, and be later applied to the southern hemisphere. As stated earlier, we will consider the E-region to be a highly conducting plasma layer parallel to the Earth's surface. The Sq current system is created through the effect of Faraday's Law:

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}_z}{\partial t} \quad (3.54)$$

When applying Faraday's Law, however, we are concerned solely with the B_z (radial) component of the magnetic field; that component perpendicular to the conducting E-region and the Earth's surface.

When the E-region plasma layer is located above the magnetic (dip) equator, the Earth's magnetic field lines are parallel to the surface, minimizing the B_z component of the field and the amount of flux passing through the sheet. However, as the thermospheric wind drags the conducting E-region plasma sheet toward the northern pole, the magnitude of the B_z component and the amount of flux through the sheet increases. As the magnitude of B_z and the flux increases, $\partial B_z / \partial t$ increases and points toward the Earth's surface.

A counterclockwise electric field “vortex” is generated in the northern hemisphere. This electric field produces a counterclockwise current flow in the highly conducting E-region. Near the magnetic equator, the electric field and associated current point in an eastward direction (figure 3.11). When this same argument is made relative to the southern hemisphere, the overall electric field flow pattern is clockwise; this also results in an eastward field at the magnetic equator. The resultant eastward electric field in the equatorial E-region is known as the *dynamo electric field*.

On the anti-sunward side of the Earth, a thermal low at the equator reverses the flow direction of both vortices; thus, the electric field reverses direction to flow westward nears the magnetic equator.

3.10.2. Equatorial Electrojet

Within E-region altitudes at the magnetic equator, where magnetic field lines are parallel to the surface and directed northward, this applied dynamo eastward electric field is perpendicular to \vec{B} . Electrons in this region are magnetized and therefore will experience $E \times B$ drift motions, whereas the ions are not magnetized. Because of this, the ions must move parallel to any applied force, including the eastward electric field.

The eastward dynamo electric field initially creates an upward $E \times B$ electron Hall motion within the E-region. It is then important to remember that the E-region is sandwiched between two bad-conducting layers. When the upward moving electrons encounter the bad-conducting plasma, they build up at the boundary between the regions. The ions, because they are not magnetized, only experience a Pederson motion parallel to the applied eastward electric field.

Therefore, there is a resulting charge separation that induces an upward polarization electric field as shown in Figure 3.13. Outside $\pm 2^\circ$ magnetic latitude, this charge separation cannot be maintained, since there is enough vertical components of the magnetic field lines for the built-up charge to drain.

Figure 3.13: Diagram of Electric Fields and Current Systems that Contribute to the Equatorial Electrojet [Anderson, private communication, 2003].

Within these bounds, however, the charge separation can be maintained due to the horizontal nature of the magnetic field near the dip equator. When the induced, polarization electric field is crossed with the northward magnetic field, a “new” westward electron Hall motion results in addition to a corresponding eastward current. Due to an enhanced Cowling conductivity (a combination of Pedersen and Hall conductivities) at the magnetic equator, the eastward ion Pedersen current due to the initial eastward electric field and the eastward electron Hall current due to the charge separation, sum to create a substantial eastward current; this current is the *equatorial electrojet*.

3.10.3. Equatorial Anomaly: “Equatorial fountain effect”

The equatorial anomaly (EA) region of the ionosphere is characterized by a trough at the geomagnetic equator bordered by two crests on either side of the magnetic equator during daytime and typically lasting several hours after sunset (Kelley, 1989; Tsai et al., 2001). Above the magnetic equator, an eastward daytime electric field is present in the ionosphere. Since the magnetic field points northward, then the plasma will experience an $E \times B / B^2$ upward drift. In the topside ionosphere, the plasma tends to diffuse along the geomagnetic field lines to higher latitudes, under the action of gravity force and pressure gradients. This plasma flow looks like water flow in a fountain; therefore it is called “*fountain effect*” (see fig.3.14).

The trough is located at the magnetic equator and crests near $\pm 20^\circ$ geomagnetic latitude. The EA is mostly a daytime process, which begins in the morning and develops throughout the sunlit period. However, during nighttime the intensity of the EA usually reduces and it dies out. The nature and variation of the equatorial anomaly have been studied by the scientific community for the past decades (Torr and Torr, 1973; Huang et al., 1989; Walker et al., 1994; Abdu et al., 1995; Millward et al., 1996; Tsai et al., 2001).

Figure 3.14. A simplified sketch illustrates the foundation effect at geomagnetic equator. An eastward field at the geomagnetic equator drives the plasma vertically upward. Pressure gradients and gravity drives it down again along the magnetic field lines toward higher latitudes (After Kelley, 1989).

Using Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data during the solar minimum period of October 1985 to September 1988, Huang et al (1989) observed the seasonal variation of TEC in the northern equatorial anomaly region. They found that the anomaly crest location occurred at different latitudes in different seasons of the year. These movements of the anomaly crests could be fully explained by the combined effects of the transequatorial neutral wind and the seasonal effect due to the location of the *subsolar point** (see Figure 3.15).

Walker et al (1994), using observations from the satellite S-66, investigated the seasonal variation of TEC in the southern and northern equatorial anomaly region.

* The subsolar point on a planet is where its sun is perceived to be directly overhead.

They observed enhanced ionization crests in the morning during winter. They explained the annual variation they observed as being due to the seasonal variation of the subsolar point relative to the geomagnetic equator, which results in the plasma transportation from summer to winter hemisphere, depending on the location of subsolar point. The region in which the subsolar point is located is the summer hemisphere and the conjugate hemisphere is winter. In other words, the ionization crests of EA are stronger in winter hemisphere than in summer hemisphere.

Figure 3.15. Simplified description of trans-equatorial neutral wind, subsolar point, and equatorward wind originating in the auroral region (modified after Tsai et al., 2001).

3.10.4. Mid Latitude trough

A minimum in the F region electron density is observed at latitudes southward of the auroral region. This minimum is longitudinally elongated. The minimum is deepest at night but a shallow minimum can also be observed in the daytime. The minimum lies at lower latitudes at night than in the evening or in the morning. The detailed structure of the minimum varies considerably but, in general, its latitudinal width is several degrees. Due to its elongated shape, the minimum is called the *ionospheric trough* or *mid-latitude trough* or *main trough*. When considering the possible trough mechanisms, the continuity equation offers three terms to consider: production, loss and

transport. The small production in the nighttime ionosphere must be a major factor contributing to the trough but it cannot explain the phenomenon alone because the production is small at night also. Increased night-time production due to particle precipitation is possible to the north of the trough and therefore it could partly contribute to the shape of the trough. Increased loss could lead to the trough, provided the temperatures in the trough region are enhanced; this is because the recombination processes are faster at higher temperatures. The effect of plasma transport is a complicated problem which can be divided into the effects of horizontal and vertical transport.

There is some indication that the equatorward edge of the trough may be associated with the plasmopause (see Fig.3.16.a). Plasmopause is the outer edge of the plasmasphere, which is the innermost region of the magnetosphere. Plasmasphere can be considered as an extension of the ionosphere within the region of closed field lines. The shape of the plasmasphere is affected by the magnetospheric dawn-to-dusk electric field. When the position of the plasmopause is compared with tomographic images of the F region electron density, results such as those in the right hand panels of Fig. 3.16 are obtained.

Figure 3.16. (a) Shows a picture shows the positions of the plasmopause mapped along the geomagnetic field lines to the ionospheric altitudes (b), a tomographic observation to the ionospheric trough.

They indicate that high electron densities are encountered on the equatorward side of the plasmopause, while the F region just to the north of the plasmopause is nearly empty. Moffett and Quegan (1983) also suggested that

the plasmopause and mid-latitude ionospheric trough often occur on or about the same field line.

Rodger and Smith (1987) have observed the position of plasmopause and mid-latitude trough simultaneously on five different occasions that included quiet and disturbed conditions. They found that the trough lay several degrees of invariant latitude higher than the plasmopause in the early evening hours, but the two features came closer together in the morning sector.

One of the trough theories is the *Stagnation Model*, which is connected to the plasma transport (due to the electric field of a magnetospheric origin) and the co-rotation of the ionosphere with the rotating Earth. At mid-latitudes in the dusk sector the sunward convection plasma flow and the anti-sunward co-rotation plasma drift oppose each other and plasma flows very slowly (e.g., Aladjev et al., 2001). Then the F region plasma is stagnated to stay for a long time in darkness and it has time to recombine even if the recombination is slow.

Figure 3.17. Shows the local time frame of reference where the Earth is viewed from the above the North Pole.

The trough behavior is well established, in particular its motion to lower latitudes, during the night and its rapid retreat to higher latitudes at dawn (Pryse et al., 1998). Observations during severe magnetic storm periods (Mallis, 1989; Horvath, 2002, Yizengaw et al., 2004) show that the trough moves rapidly to lower latitudes. As a consequence, the ionization must move into the region previously occupied by the trough. As the ionosphere is the major sources of plasma within the plasmasphere, we expect the trough

structure to be reflected in the plasmasphere, suggesting that the ionospheric trough and plasmopause should be on the same field lines.

3.10.5. Equatorial spread F

Equatorial spread F (ESF) is instability in the ionospheric F-region which forms irregularities in the plasma distribution. It occurs usually at night, but may also appear in daytime. The post sunset enhancement of the upward $E \times B$ drift raises the F-region ionosphere above 300 km. In the absence of sunlight, the lower ionosphere rapidly decays and a steep density gradient develops on the bottomside of the raised F region that sets the preconditions for instability development. The instability is believed to be driven by the Gravitational Rayleigh–Taylor (GRT) mechanism, characterized by a situation similar to a heavy fluid resting on a light fluid. An illustration of how electrodynamics processes equivalent to the GRT mechanism can cause growth of plasma-depleted structures is represented in Fig. 3.18.b (adapted from Kelley, 1989). Here, the bottom of the nightside F-layer is approximated by a step function with an electron density n_1 in the F-layer and zero ($n_2 = 0$) below, see Fig 3.18.a.

In the F-region where collisions are negligible, the gravitational force produces an electric current which is directed eastward (Kelley, 1989). A gravitational force is antiparallel to the plasma density gradient (∇n), which is upward, and in the equatorial region the magnetic field (B) is horizontal (into the page). The ions are affected downwards by the gravitational force.

Therefore, without solving the momentum equation, we can conclude that a gravitational force $M_i g$ must create a drift velocity

$$V_{ig} = \frac{M_i g \times B}{e B^2}. \quad (3.55)$$

A corresponding result is valid for electrons but due to the small electron mass, the resulting electron velocity is small. Hence, the combined effect of the gravitational force and the magnetic field is to produce a net current that flows eastward (in the x -direction). This eastward current, which is proportional to the species' mass (M_i) and electron density (n_e), is:

$$J_x = n_e e V_{ig} = \frac{n_e M_i g \times B}{B^2} \quad (3.56)$$

J_x will be large when n_e is large and small when n_e is small. So since J_x depends on the electron density n_e , a perturbation in n_e could cause a current divergence and the charge will pile up on the edges of the small initial perturbation, resulting in perturbation electric fields (δE). These electric fields produce a $\delta E \times B/B^2$ drift which is the same for ions and electrons. The direction of the drift is such that it enhances the original disturbance; the drift is downwards in regions where the boundary is bent downwards (in the density enhancement) and upwards where the boundary is bent upwards (in the lower density). This makes the disturbance grow and instability is created.

Figure 3.18: (a) Schematic diagram of the plasma analog of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability in the equatorial geometry. (b) Sequential sketches made from shots of the hydromagnetic Rayleigh-Taylor instability. A heavy fluid is initially supported by a transparent light fluid (adapted from Kelley, 1989).

If a signal from a satellite passes through such a disturbed region, the receiver picks up fluctuations in the signal strength, which is known as *scintillation* (Kelley, 1989).

The diurnal behavior of the gravitational dynamo is almost with the same as the F-region dynamo. During the daytime, any perturbation electric fields due to plasma instability are shorted out in the E-region because of the Sunlit E-region's high conductivity. All the perturbation electric field and thus the occurrence of spread F are active in the F-region during nighttime. This explains why spread F and thus ionospheric scintillation do not begin until well after sunset, even though g and ∇n are antiparallel on the bottomside during the day as well as night.

- Note that the system is stable if g and ∇n are parallel.
- It is necessary to have an initial density perturbation as a seeding source for the instability to grow into plasma depletions and associated irregularities (M.A. Abdu., 2005). The nature of the seeding perturbation is widely believed to be gravity waves (see for example Kelley et al., 1981) whose precise sources are, however, unknown.
- The unresolved questions related to the seeding source include:
 - (1) possibility of gravity wave generation through (a) a supersonic motion of solar terminator (the border between day and night upon the surface of a planetary body) in the lower thermosphere, and (b) in situ generation of gravity waves from the evening F-layer rise permitting zonal wind acceleration and associated strong vertical shear as discussed by Anderson et al. (1982);
 - (2) remote sources such as tropospheric convection activity that could produce upward propagating gravity waves as was suggested by Rottger (1981).

3.10.6. Ionospheric scintillations

Ionospheric scintillations are rapid variations in the amplitude and phase of transionospheric radio signals resulting from density irregularities in the ionosphere and variations in the local index of refraction along the propagation path. Scintillations show strong diurnal, seasonal, geographic and solar cycle dependence being at their most severe during the evening hours, in the months of the equinox, at equatorial latitudes and during the years of solar maximum.

The fluctuations in the signal amplitude are quantified by the scintillation intensity index, S_4 , which is defined as follows:

$$S_4 = \frac{\sqrt{\langle I^2 \rangle - \langle I \rangle^2}}{\langle I \rangle} \quad (3.57)$$

where I represents the signal intensity (amplitude squared), $\sqrt{\langle I^2 \rangle - \langle I \rangle^2}$ is the Signal intensity standard deviation and $\langle I \rangle$ is the Signal intensity mean. The scintillation index may be interpreted as the fractional fluctuation of the signal (e.g. $S_4=0.0$ indicates no modulation whereas $S_4=1.0$ indicates 100% modulation). Scintillations can disrupt the flow of information in the radio signals.

3.11. Total Electron Content

The property of the ionosphere that produces most of the effects on satellite signals is the Total Electron Content (TEC). Values of TEC from 10^{16} to 10^{19} electron per m^2 , along the radio wave path, represent the general extremes of observed values in the Earth's ionosphere. No values of TEC greater than 10^{19} el/m^2 has ever been reported, even along long slant paths in the Earth's ionosphere during a high solar maximum period (Klobuchar, 1996).

Although TEC measurements are generally made from satellite radio signals of opportunity, observed at arbitrary elevation angles, the TEC normally is expressed as an equivalent vertical Total Electron Content (VTEC). It is a very important quantity for describing the ionosphere of the Earth. Studies of the diurnal, seasonal, and solar cycle behaviour of TEC have been conducted by numerous observers, using various measurement techniques, over more than four decades (Evans, 1977; Essex, 1978; Davies, 1980; Jakowski et al., 1999; Horvath, 2002 and the reference therein).

Some of the spatial and temporal fluctuations in TEC are strongly related to space weather (Solar-Terrestrial Relations: via the solar wind, EUV and X-radiation (Brekke, 1997)). Here, the diurnal, latitudinal, seasonal, magnetic storm and solar cycle variations of TEC have been discussed

There are a number of factors which influence the magnitude of the TEC, including (Klobuchar, 1991);

- the time of day ,
- the latitude,
- the season,
- the level of solar activity, and
- erratic variation associated with enhanced geomagnetic activity, particle precipitation and atmospheric disturbances.

Other causes of ionospheric variability, which lie in the upper atmosphere itself, include:

- Variations of composition (O/N_2 or O/O_2 ratio).
- Travelling ionospheric, atmospheric disturbances, (TIDs/TADs).
- Neutral winds.
- Electric fields.

All of these fluctuations have been termed "geophysical noise" (Davies et al., 1992).

3.11.1. Diurnal and seasonal variation of TEC

One of the factors that affect the reliability of any ionospheric prediction scheme is the large day-to-day variability of the ionosphere and this is reflected in the variations in the TEC. Since TEC is a function of the amount of incident solar radiation, it is generally greater during the day when sunlight is present, producing ionization. On the night side of the Earth, the recombination dominates, thereby reducing the TEC.

Maximum TEC usually occurs in the early afternoon (~ two hours after solar noon) and minimum TEC usually occurs just before dawn (Figure 3.19). As a consequence, at night the ionospheric delay is approximately five to ten times less than for day time observations (Klobuchar, 1991). Jayachandran et al (1992) founded that the TEC variability is more a function of time of day than of solar activity. Furthermore, they also found that the variability is smaller (average about 20%) during daytime and larger (average about 35%) at night, at all latitudes and at both solar maximum and minimum.

Figure 3.19: Ionospheric Total Electron Content (TEC) variation at Helwan, Egypt for day 29 May, 2010.

Changes in TEC can also occur on much shorter time scales (< 1 hour). One of the phenomena responsible for such changes is the Travelling Ionospheric Disturbance (TID), which have characteristic periods on the order of 15 minutes or greater.

In considering the diurnal variation of TEC, seasonal variations need to be considered as well. Observational (Balan and Rao, 1990) and theoretical (Fuller-Rowell et al., 1994) studies show that the diurnal variations of TEC are different at different seasons of the year. During the summer, the TEC variation has a maximum occurring during late afternoon and there is a continuous decrease in TEC throughout the night (Davies, 1980), while during winter the TEC variation has a diurnal maximum occurs at about 13 hr LT and the TEC remains relatively constant shortly after sunset but eventually decays to a pre dawn minimum.

3.11.2. Latitudinal variation

As previously discussed, the TEC varies with geographic latitude. While this is partly due to changing zenith angle of the Sun, there are also effects due to the changing magnetic dip angle and it is convenient to distinguish three regions based on magnetic latitude, viz. high latitudes, mid latitudes, and low latitudes (see subsection 2.3.1.1). Usually TEC is a maximum at low latitudes (the tropical zone) and at the poles (the auroral zone), and is a minimum at mid-latitudes.

The TEC increases with decreasing latitude and usually the maximum TEC is recorded over the low-latitude region. The TEC peak at the tropical latitude region decreases as the equator is approached so that a trough like structure, known as the *Equatorial Anomaly* (subsection 3.10.3), occurs at or near the magnetic equator, and this trough becomes more pronounced during severe magnetic disturbances.

3.11.3. Solar cycle variation

As mentioned in section 3.3, ultraviolet radiation from the Sun is primarily responsible for the ionosphere existence. The UV output of the Sun varies with solar activity, with a clear variation with a mean period of about 11 years (section 2.2). Within the 11 year solar cycle period two main conditions occur; solar maximum (maximum sunspot number) and minimum (minimum sunspot number) and the TEC is much larger during solar maximum than solar minimum conditions (Garriott et al., 1970). Fortunately, due to the time constraint given to this research, most of (if not all) measurements have been conducted during the enhancing phase of the present solar cycle 24 (see fig.2.4).

3.11.4. Magnetic Storm variation

Space weather is driven by the activity of the Sun when a massive explosions send magnetic disruptions containing clouds of particles contains billions of tons of material travelling at high speed toward Earth. When these clouds reach the Earth's upper atmosphere, they enhance electric fields, currents, and energetic particle precipitation in particular, causing geomagnetic storms which produce severe space weather conditions.

Numerous theoretical and experimental studies (Fuller-Rowell et al., 1997; Prölss, 1997; Buonsanto, 1999; Danilov and Lastovicka, 2001; Blagoveshchensky et al., 2003 and the references therein) show that the behavior of the ionosphere during geomagnetic storms is significantly different to its normal behavior. The term "*ionospheric storm*" is used to describe several disturbances that appear in the ionosphere following a geomagnetic storm. The ionosphere reacts to the geomagnetic activity in a complex way and its behavior varies with latitude, longitude, time of day and season (Dieminger et al., 1996). The mid latitude F2-region responses to geomagnetic storm in three phases: (1) an initial or positive phase in which

the peak electron density increases with respect to pre-storm conditions and lasts for a few hours on the first day of a storm (Hunsucker and Hargreaves, 2003), known as *positive ionospheric storm*, (2) a negative phase in which the peak electron density decreases relative to pre-storm conditions, known as *negative ionospheric storm*, which can last several days. (3) Finally, the ionosphere gradually returns to normal conditions over a period of one to several days in the recovery phase. The changes in the vertical electron density profile are shown in figure 3.20.

Figure 3.20: Changes in vertical electron density profile during a positive (dotted) and a negative (dashed) ionospheric storms in the F2 region, solid curve is the profile during normal ionosphere.

A geomagnetic storm can produce thermospheric winds, generate electric currents and change the composition in the upper atmosphere. These three effects influence the normal ionosphere structure. Every one of them can make non-normal variation in the photoionization, recombination, and transport processes and cause an irregular change in the electron concentration of the ionosphere. It should be noted that the morphology and the physics of the ionospheric storms are not completely understood and a number of open issues concerning this phenomenon exist.

Some major effects is that the neutral wind circulation and the atmospheric composition change significantly and the latter causes changes in the rate of production and loss of ionization.

These changes in turn modify and redistribute the atmospheric electron density. The neutral winds can also cause the production of F-region electric fields through the disturbance dynamo mechanism. Such electric fields in turn also redistribute the F-region plasma, affecting the production and loss rates, and they may also destabilize the plasma, producing plasma irregularities.

Manifestations of ionospheric storms are evident in the behavior of the ionospheric TEC which is most conveniently described in terms of the percentage change in TEC, $\Delta TEC\%$ (Jakowski, 1996; Jakowski et al., 1999, and 2002; Förster and Jakowski, 2000; Yizengaw and Essex, 2003).

$$\Delta TEC\% = \frac{(TEC_{obs} - TEC_{quiet})}{TEC_{quiet}} \times 100 \quad (3.58)$$

where TEC_{obs} and TEC_{quiet} are the TEC values during magnetically disturbed and quiet periods, respectively. $\Delta TEC\%$ is the percentage deviation of TEC from the corresponding quiet day TEC value. The morphologies of negative and positive phases of an ionospheric storm are different because the principal physical mechanisms responsible for their formation are believed to be different.

3.11.4.1. Negative phase

During geomagnetic storms the cross-polar-cap potential increases markedly, leading to heating and expansion of the neutral atmosphere. Such rapid expansion may cause an upwelling (i.e., the motion of air through constant pressure surfaces), which causes the depletion of the atom-to-molecule ratio in the thermosphere, as air of different composition moves up from below.

Seaton (1956) first suggested that the changes in thermospheric composition (depletion of the atom-to-molecule ratio) are the primary cause of the ionospheric storm negative effect in the mid and high latitude regions. Mikhailov et al (1995) and Danilov and Lastovicka (2001) found that at the F-layer peak height the electron concentration, and thus TEC, is directly proportional to the atom-to-molecule ratio.

3.11.4.2. Positive phase

Several mechanisms have been proposed as probable sources of the ionospheric storm positive effect. F2 layer uplifting due to vertical drift, downwelling of the gas as a result of the storm-induced thermospheric circulation, and plasma fluxes from the plasmasphere are the probable sources of the positive phase of the ionospheric storm (Danilov and Belik, 1991).

The F-layer drift may be caused by two principal mechanisms:

1. an increase in the electric fields of magnetospheric origin as well as dynamo electric fields.
2. equatorward horizontal thermospheric circulation that lifts up the F-layer plasma along the inclined field lines (Buonsanto, 1999; Danilov, 2001).

The former is the dominant mechanism at lower latitudes and the latter at mid-latitude regions where the magnetic dip angle is close to 45° (Jakowski, 1999).

The disturbed thermospheric circulation causes the downwelling of the neutral species through constant pressure surfaces increasing the atom-to-molecule ratio and thus reducing recombination and so increasing the TEC above normal values (Fuller-Rowell et al., 1997). Energetic particle precipitation during severe magnetic storms is also considered to be a significant source of ionization, producing positive storm effects in TEC at high latitude regions. The plasma flux from the plasmasphere to the ionosphere at night has been studied at different locations by different authors (Essex and Klobuchar, 1980; Jakowski et al., 1991; Horvath and Essex, 2003b and the references therein).

Horvath and Essex (2003a), using data from TOPEX and GPS, suggested that the downward plasma flux from the plasmasphere is governed by the occurrence of a disturbance zonal electric field. During nighttime there is a storm time intensified magnetospheric westward electric field that might drive the plasmaspheric ionization down to the ionosphere across the magnetic field lines. Thus, the plasma pressure in the flux tubes is increased, and enhanced plasma from the plasmasphere is driven down to ionospheric F-region heights leading to the nighttime storm positive effect. During the daytime, however, reverse plasma flows (ionosphere-plasmasphere) happen due to the daytime eastward electric field.

Another point, on which a clear evidence is not yet available, is the case of a positive phase appearance before the beginning of the corresponding magnetic disturbance. Danilov and Belik (1991) suggested this might be related to some other path of penetration of the soft particle precipitation, bringing energy from the solar wind into the ionospheric dayside cusp regions*. They also concluded that the cusp region begins to move equatorward a few hours before the beginning of the Dst depletion, which then triggers positive storm effects before the SSC at auroral and mid-latitude regions.

3.11.5. Nighttime TEC enhancement

It has long been realized that the ionospheric TEC does not decrease throughout the night in the way predicted by simple theory but shows anomalous, nighttime enhancements under a wide range of geophysical conditions (Balan et al., 1991; Balan et al., 1992).

Results from previous studies shows that the nighttime enhancements occur over a wide geographical area and at any time of the year (Titheridge, 1968, 1973; Davies et al., 1979; Essex and Watkins, 1973; Balan et al., 1992; Horvath, 2002 and the reference therein).

Nighttime enhancements may be caused by several different mechanisms. The important mechanisms are: vertical plasma motion across the magnetic fields lines due to ionospheric and magnetospheric electric fields (e.g, Balan et al., 1991); plasma diffusion from the plasmasphere (e.g., Horvath and Essex, 2003a); plasma transfer from the conjugate hemisphere (e.g., Walker et al., 1994); plasma motion due to neutral air wind (e.g., Bailey et al., 1991); movement of the mid-latitude ionospheric trough (e.g, Jakowski et al., 2002); and corpuscular ionization (e.g. Balan et al., 1991).

The post-sunset increase in the upward vertical equatorial $E \times B$ drift velocity and the meridional neutral wind velocity are accepted as the primary sources of nighttime enhancement at low latitudes. Namboothiri et al (1989) observed that the $E \times B$ vertical drift velocity increased during post-sunset and it is believed to be caused by the F-region dynamo.

* Cusp regions or Polar Cusps: it is funnel-shaped areas with near zero magnetic fields, located between the magnetic field lines on the sunward and tailward sides of the planet. These cusps provide a directly entry for the plasma from the magnetosheath into the magnetosphere.

The post sunset $E \times B$ drift raises the equatorial F-region to higher altitudes where recombination rate is low and the subsequent diffusion of ionization along the magnetic field lines gives rise to enhancements in TEC at latitudes around the equatorial anomaly crests at $\pm 20^\circ$ magnetic (Anderson and Klobuchar, 1983; Balan et al., 1991). The plasma motion across the field lines caused by $E \times B$ and the neutral wind interaction with the plasma are important mechanisms causing nighttime enhancements at mid-latitudes (Balan et al., 1991; Bailey et al., 1991; Horvath and Essex, 2003b).

Furthermore, the downward diffusion can be enhanced by the $E \times B$ drift causing compression of the plasma in flux tubes as they convect to lower latitudes. This mechanism is more significant in winter (Davies et al., 1979; Webb, 2000). In summer, however, diffusion is generally not a cause of nighttime TEC enhancements because the plasma diffusion is mostly upward, i.e., from the ionosphere to the plasmasphere.

At mid-latitudes during all seasons the meridional neutral winds are equatorward during nighttime, reaching maximum speed about midnight. Thus, the interaction between the neutral air wind and the plasma raises the augmented ionization, from high-altitude region, to altitudes of lower chemical loss, leading the nighttime enhancements.

Movement of the mid-latitude ionospheric trough and corpuscular ionization are important mechanisms for TEC nighttime enhancement at high-latitude regions. TEC enhancements occur on the edges of the trough region are due to corpuscular ionization (Balan et al., 1991) or particle precipitation (Jakowski et al., 2002).

During magnetically active periods, the plasmasphere is compressed causing the mid-latitude trough to move to lower latitudes (Lamair and Gringuaz, 1998). Hence, the TEC enhancements become strong on either side of the trough. Strong TEC enhancements at the poleward side of the trough are due to corpuscular ionization whilst on the equatorward side they are due to magnetospheric compression. Balan et al (1991) suggested that the magnetospheric compression causes the plasma to be dumped into the topside ionosphere from the plasmasphere, resulting in TEC being enhanced at the equatorward side of the trough.

In general the nighttime TEC enhancements characteristics, such as frequency of occurrence, time of occurrence, amplitude and duration are depend not only on the location and season but also on the magnetic activity as well.

4 Instruments and Software.

The space age began in 1957, opening a new frontier for both the Cold War and commerce. Both the United States and the Soviet Union allocated vast resources over the next ten years to the space race. An important benefit to flow from this intense competition was that the potential for space-based communication, navigation, and surveillance systems was recognized and realized quickly.

In this chapter, we concerns on two Satellite Navigation Systems: TRANSIT and GPS, as theses systems were used as a tools in this study. A brief description about other satellite navigation systems: GLONASS, Galileo, Compass and other navigation systems are reviewed in order to give an overall view to the reader about the famous navigation systems.

The observations from these two systems were supported by magnetic observations from MAGDAS (MAGnetic Data Acquisition System) magnetometers. A brief description about this magnetometer is located at the end of chapter.

4.1. Transit

The U.S. Navy had a vital need for a navigation system to guide a new class of submarines carrying Polaris missiles, and the first satellite navigation program was born. The system was named *Navy Navigation Satellite System*, but came to be better known as *Transit*. Transit was a pioneering achievement of the *Applied Physics Laboratory* (APL) of The Johns Hopkins University, which was responsible for the whole thing from the initial concept developed in 1958 to the experimental satellites launched in 1961–1962, and the final system which became operational in 1964 (Stansell.,1983).

Transit was realized with four to seven satellites in low-altitude (1100 km), nearly circular, polar orbits. Each satellite broadcast signals at 150 MHz (VHF) and 400 MHz (UHF) with a total transmitted power of one watt. Only one satellite was in view at a time and a user waited up to about 100 minutes

between successive satellite passes to determine position. When a satellite came in view, the receiver recorded continuously the Doppler shift of the received signal and the navigation message giving the satellite position during the satellite pass, which lasting about 10–20 minutes.

Transit was used by the U.S. submarine fleet to update the ship's position and reset the inertial navigation system. The system saw a limited civil use in the maritime industry and geodesy, starting in 1967. Transit receiver tracks and records measurements from multiple satellite passes from a fixed location.

There was a Cold War echo from the Soviet Union in the form of two systems virtually identical to Transit: *Parus* for the Soviet Navy and *Tsikada* for merchant ships. The Doppler-based system worked well for ships at sea which required infrequent position updates and could track a signal continuously during the 10–20 minute satellite pass. This technique is not suited for aircraft or mobile users requiring frequent or continuous positioning.

Transit was decommissioned in 1996. In 1997, they were rechristened the *Navy Ionospheric Monitoring Satellites* (NIMS). There have been several generations of these satellites, with the last satellite launched in 1988. They have exceeded their operational lifetime, but are still in orbit and transmitting.

A Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receivers (CIDR) was designed to observe the ionospheric effects upon navigation signals from the U.S Navy's Transit satellites (Danchik 1998).

4.1.1. Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receivers (CIDR)

The *Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver* (CIDR) system developed by the *Applied Research Laboratories*, University of Texas at Austin, as a radio receiver that measure the Doppler shift in UHF (400 MHz) and VHF (150 MHz) signals from radio beacons on board Low-Earth-Orbit (LEO) satellites (Transit/NIMS, GFO).

The radio beacons on these spacecraft transmit in either an operational or maintenance channel. In addition, a number of scientific research satellites (Bernhardt and Siefring 2006) carry radio beacons broadcasting in a geodetic

channel that CIDRs can observe. Each radio beacon transmits UHF (~ 400 MHz) and VHF (~ 150 MHz) radio signals. Table 4.1 presents the radio frequencies for each of the three beacon modes observed by the CIDRs.

Table 4.1 The radio frequencies observed by CIDR system.

Radio channel	VHF frequency (MHz)	UHF frequency (MHz)
Operational	149.988	399.968
Maintenance	149.97825	399.942
Geodetic	150.012	400.032

CIDR components are composed of four primary components: an antenna, a receiver, a single frequency GPS unit and a laptop. Figure (4.1a) is a picture of a CIDR system showing the four main components.

Figure. 4.1: A photo of the CIDR system. (a), the CIDR's four component. (b), CIDR's dual frequency quadrifilar antenna.

While different antenna designs have been tested, the primary CIDR antenna is a dual frequency quadrifilar antenna of a coupled, helical design, displayed in Figure 4.1b. In addition, the antenna contains certain preamplifiers and filters. The antenna and electronics are contained in a fiberglass cylinder with an aluminum base.

A 30 m low-loss cable connects the antenna to the receiver, which allows the antenna to be deployed up to five stories above the receiver. The majority of

the system electronics are contained within the receiver where the analog signals from the antenna are digitize and the principle measurements are determined. The GPS unit provides the CIDR with the Universal Time and geographic location of CIDR. The final component is the laptop. Using a Linux operating system, the CIDR laptop is connected to the receiver by a USB cable and to the Internet by an Ethernet cable. It acquires the satellite ephemeris via the Internet, converting the ephemeris information into specific observing jobs for the receiver, converting the receiver data into ASCII data files, providing a user interface that allows the user to monitor the CIDR, adjust system parameters and storing the CIDR output for several weeks.

In May 2008, the first CIDR was deployed at Helwan University, Egypt (29.8641° N, 31.3172° E) as a part of the *Ionospheric Tomography Network in Egypt* (ITNE) project, which consists of a chain of ionospheric tomography receivers that will be deployed in Egypt to investigate the equatorial regions of the Earth's ionosphere (Garner et al., 2009). This chain will cover most of Egypt. Figure 4.2 shows the relative position of these units.

The northern most CIDR will be located at the University of Alexandria. The central site is already installed at Helwan University in Cairo, while the southernmost CIDR will be located in Aswan at the National Research Institute of Astronomy and Geophysics (NRIAG). More importantly, it will extend from roughly 13° – 24° magnetic latitude. Since the typically field-of-view for a CIDR receiver extends 10° – 15° to either side of receiver, ITNE's field-of-view should extend from roughly 40° to the magnetic equator. Hence, it will be well suited to study the plasma structures associated with the equatorial fountain. The TEC extraction method from CIDR receivers and its results are discussed later in chapter five and six, respectively.

LEO satellites quickly pass through the CIDR field-of-view. For a typical satellite pass, the satellite moves through the receiver's field-of-view in ~ 20 min, which corresponds to a ray separation of $0.15^\circ/\text{sec}$. Hence, a data rate of 1 Hz is equivalent to ray paths that are 0.15° apart (assuming no ray bending). The maximum CIDR data rate is 1 kHz, which corresponds to a ray separation of $0.00015^\circ/\text{sec}$.

Figure. 4.2. A map of the Ionospheric Tomography Network of Egypt (ITNE). The squares represent the locations of the CIDRs to be deployed. The dotted lines represent the geographic latitude and longitude lines, while the dashed lines show lines of constant magnetic latitude.

The fundamental ionospheric parameters observed by CIDRs are the TEC rate of change, the relative TEC, and the ionospheric phase change in the UHF and VHF channels.

Each CIDR records the frequency *Doppler shift* and the *phasor* between the incoming broadband signal and the internal system clock for both the UHF and VHF channels. These measurements are taken at an internal data rate of 1 KHz, which can be decimated to lower frequencies specified by the user. Typically, the CIDR data is decimated to a 1 Hz data rate. The measured Doppler shift includes both the Doppler shift caused by the ionospheric time delay and by the satellite motion (Garner et al., 2009).

The difference phasor measures the phase difference between the incoming signal and the expected signal, and is related to both the signal strength of the incoming signal and the phase shift of the signal within the receiver. In the raw data, the phasor values are given as a correlation count from 0 to 195.31 with pure noise equal to 97.66. In post-processing, the phasor values are normalized to values from -1 to 1. The phasor contains two components: a correlation count [CC] and a phase error [PE] (Garner et al., 2009).

These components correspond to the amplitudes of the in-phase and quadrature terms of the correlated signal within the receiver, respectively. For a perfect, noiseless measurement, the phasor will be [195.31, 97.66] or [1, 0]. The magnitude of the phasor is a measure of the signal strength received by the CIDR. Typically, CIDRs can convert Doppler shifts with phasor magnitudes as low as 0.02 (99.61) into usable TEC measurements (Garner et al., 2009).

Figure 4.3 is an example of the local CIDR diagnostic plot of OSCAR 32 satellite pass at 3 Sept.2008, 11:07 UT. Similar plots are created during each satellite pass, and are available on the CIDR laptop both during and after the pass.

Figure. 4.3. A sample of the real-time CIDR diagnostic plots. The upper panel is a plot of the Doppler shifts scaled to the UHF frequency as a function of time during the satellite overpass. The measured VHF (red) and UHF (yellow) are shown with expected scaled Doppler shifts (green). The side bars show the upper and lower bounds for an acceptable receiver lock. The lower panel shows the correlation count as a function of time for both channels. The correlation count is unnormalized with a correlation count of 100 or greater being a usable signal.

The first of the diagnostic plots (the upper panel of Fig. 4.2) shows the measured Doppler shifts scaled to the VHF frequency (the UHF Doppler shift is divided by 3/8). This plot is useful for detecting radio interferers. A local interferer will generate a sharp turn off of expected Doppler shift, and any measurements outside of the acceptable bounds are rejected.

The second diagnostic plot shows the correlation count for each channel as a function of the time. These plots basically provide a view of the signal strength at the receiver. In many ways, they are similar to a signal-to-noise measurement. In particular, measurements with a correlation count less than 99.61 are often ignored as bad data (Garner et al., 2009).

4.1.1.1. CIDR data format

Operationally, each local CIDR produces three files per satellite pass:

- (1) ***.dop** files: these files contain the measured and predicted Doppler shift and the components of the receiver phasor for both the UHF and VHF channels as a function of Universal Time (see Table 4.2). The .dop file is used in post-processing to solve for the relative TEC and the phase shift in each signal.
- (2) ***.rtec** files: it is a quick check files containing the time history of the computed TEC change, the integrated relative TEC, the elevation angle, the latitude, longitude and altitude of the satellite. As a quick check file, it does not contain any quality checking and has only rough calculations.
- (3) ***.stdout** files: contains the Doppler shift measurements and the correlation count and a certain electronic steering commands. It provides the information for the diagnostic plots available for each satellite pass.

4.1.1.2. CIDR data software

A program CIDR2Ncdf, takes CIDR data, performs quality assurance filtering of the data, and writes out change in TEC and relative TEC data in NetCDF (Network Common Data Format) or ASCII files, according to the user's wishes.

As a part of the quality assurance process, data is flagged as bad if it is below a minimum correlation count, has a Doppler shift beyond an accepted tolerance, or is an outlier beyond three standard deviations from the mean. No output file will be generated if, after flagging bad data, there is not enough good data to meet the minimum required value. The data is then interpolated over the bad data gaps and averaged over sampling rates greater than 1 Hz to produce an output data set of 1 Hz TEC data.

To run the executable CIDR2Ncdf , it must be located in the directory containing the *.dop files to process plus the following input files:

- Process.cfg** a configuration file that contains parameters used to perform quality assurance on the *.dop files (see Appendix A).
- recvrlst.txt** contains receivers names, locations, and location names (see Appendix B)
- navsat.txt** (actual file name specified in process.cfg) contains information about the satellites location and its path. This allows for the CIDR to be able to predict where the satellite will be and allow it to electronically steer towards the satellite. Using the location of the satellite we are able to correct for the curvature of the earth when calculating Vertical TEC from Slant TEC (see Appendix C). The information for the navsat files are pulled from two sites, www.celestrak.com and www.io.com.
- ncdf_atts.txt** (actual filename specified in process.cfg) contains any user-supplied global attributes to put in the output (see Appendix D).

The program will attempt to process all *.dop files in the directory and generate ASCII (*.txt) or NetCDF (*.nc) files as output files:

- *.nc** NetCDF files with the same base name as the *.dop files from which they were created. If no such file was created, then the *.dop data did not pass all of the quality assurance criteria. These are only created if “use_ascii” is set to 0 in process.cfg.
- *.txt** ASCII output files with the same base name as the *.dop files from which they were created. These are only created if “use_ascii” is set to 1 in process.cfg.

Four IDL (Interactive Data Language) programs are used to read the output and doppler files (*.dop) and plot relative VTEC, change in VTEC, satellite track and doppler data. (see Appendix E for a list and description of these software). These plots are already constructed from a real data and given in chapters 5 and 6.

4.2. Global Positioning System (GPS)

The success of Transit begat follow-on programs for space-based navigation systems. The U.S. Navy and the Air Force each had a development program in the late 1960s and the two were eventually combined into GPS.

The *Global Positioning System* (GPS) as a space-based navigation system has been developed by the US military to provide real-time and world wide absolute positioning under all weather conditions. It is the first *Global Navigation Satellite System* (GNSS) offering the accuracy nowadays for surveying, geodesy, navigation, and geophysics. More or less synchronously to GPS, the former Soviet Union has been developing a similar system under the name GLONASS. Both of these systems are now undergoing extensive modernization. Other systems such as the European Galileo system and the Compass from China are joining the GNSS club (Hein and Eissfeller, 2007).

In the early 1960s, several US government organizations including the military, (National Aeronautic and Space Administration) NASA, and Department of Transport (DoT) were interested in developing a satellite systems for determining position on the Earth. Furthermore, the US army was investigating many radio techniques, including ranging, and the use of Doppler measurements. The result of these investigations was the recommendation to use Pseudo-Random Noise (PRN) modulation for ranging with digital signals. Finally in the early 1970s the Global Positioning System (GPS) was developed. The US Department of Defense (DoD) conceived the system as a worldwide, continuously available, and a navigation aid for its troops, aircraft, and ships. The DoD launched the first GPS test satellite on 1978 and since that year, there have been 5 generations of GPS satellites, the so-called *Block I*, *Block II/IIA*, *Block IIR* (Replenishment), *Block IIR-M* (Replenishment-Modernization) and *Block IIF* (Follow-on). The last successful launch was on March 24, 2009 from Block IIR-M generation. Figure 4.4 shows the five types of GPS spacecrafts.

Figure.4.4. *Block I, Block II/IIA, Block IIR , Block IIR-M and Block IIF* spacecrafts.

The system was declared operational in 1995. The development cost of GPS has been reported to be about \$10 billion; the annual operation and maintenance cost is estimated to be about \$500 million. As an aside, we should note that the full name given to GPS was *NAVSTAR*, as an acronym for *Navigation System with Time and Ranging* (Parkinson., 1996). More details of the history of the GPS program can be found in Kaplan (1996) and wellenhof et al. (1997).

Although the GPS was designed and funded by the US Air Force mainly for the purpose of navigation, the civilian community has taken advantage of its presence for a host of other applications including ionospheric monitoring (Klobuchar et al., 1994, Klobuchar, 1996), tomographic imaging of the ionosphere (Kunitsyn et al., 1997), atmospheric water vapor and ionospheric calibration (Wilson et al., 1992), investigation of seismic tectonic motions (Blewitt et al., 1993), and many more.

The GPS as a space based radio navigation system comprises of three main components: *Space, Control, and User* segments.

The Space Segment consists of 24 satellites or more (orbited as a spares), distributed in 6 orbital planes at an altitude of about 20,000 Km and with an inclination angle of 55° to the equator (Fig. 4.5). The present constellation exceeds the nominal constellation with more than 30 satellites. The period of each satellite is 12 sidereal hours (11 h 58 m), and typically remains in a ground receiver's field-of-view (typical 160°) for roughly 8 hours. This design provides global coverage with at least four satellites simultaneously visible anywhere on earth at any given time.

Figure.4.5: Schematic view of the GPS satellite constellation.

Each GPS satellite broadcast in two different frequencies at the microwave L-band: L1 signal with a carrier frequency $f_1 = 1.57542$ GHz (corresponds to a wavelength of 19.05 cm) and L2 signal with a carrier frequency $f_2 = 1.2276$ GHz (corresponds to a wavelength of 24.45 cm), with a common frequency $f_0 = 1.023$ MHz (i.e.; $f_1 = 1540 f_0$ and $f_2 = 1200 f_0$). The typical data rate is 33.3 MHz, which corresponds to an angular difference of 0.167° between adjacent slant paths.

The Control Segment consists of a Master Control Station (MCS) in Colorado Springs, plus a further five monitor stations (Hawaii, Kwajalein, Ascension Island, Diego Garcia, Colorado Springs) and three ground antennas (Kwajalein, Ascension Island, Diego Garcia) as shown in Figure 4.5. This segment operates the satellites, determines their positions accurately and calibrates the satellite clocks.

Figure.4.6: GPS control segment

The User Segment consists of antennas and receiver-processors that provide positioning, velocity and precise time to the user.

4.2.1. GPS signals and its characteristics

Each GPS satellite carries an atomic clock to provide timing information for the signals transmitted by the satellites.

The satellites *Block I*, *Block II/IIA*, *Block IIR*, were launched before December 2005, broadcasts two spread spectrum L-band radio signals (f_1 and f_2). These two carrier frequencies are derived from the same atomic clock driven oscillator with a base frequency $f_0 = 1.023$ MHz (i.e., $f_1 = 1540 f_0$ and $f_2 = 1200 f_0$). The carriers are modulated by so-called PRN (*Pseudo Random Noise*) codes, which are unique for each satellite.

In the *Block I*, *Block II/IIA*, *Block IIR* satellites, two types of PRN codes: *Precision (P)* code and *Coarse/Acquisition (C/A)* code, are modulated on the carriers. The carrier waves on L1 and L2 are modulated by P-code and only the L1 carrier is modulated by the C/A-code. The Coarse/Acquisition (C/A) code is a short PRN code broadcast at a bit (or chipping) rate of 1.023 MHz, while the P-code has a 10 times higher resolution, 10.23 MHz, than the C/A-code and thereby the determination of the pseudoranges can be done more precisely.

A navigation message, containing information about the satellite orbits, satellite clock corrections and satellite status, is also modulated onto the carrier waves. Figure 4.7 shows the different GPS satellite signal components.

Figure.4.7: GPS satellite signal components (Rizos, 1997).

Since the American DoD owns the GPS, it implemented techniques that deliberately broadcasted accuracy errors in order to deny full navigation accuracy to non-authorized users. *Selective Availability* (SA) and *Anti-Spoofing* (AS) were the two national security techniques that DoD applied deliberately to initially limit the accuracy achievable by civilian users. The SA policy, the denial of full accuracy, was accomplished by manipulating navigation message orbit data and/or satellite clock frequency, whilst the AS policy guarded against fake transmissions of satellite data by encrypting the P-code to form the Y-code (Wellenhof et al.,1997).

Under *Selective Availability* (SA) policy the DoD denied P1 code information to non-authorized users resulting in the ranging accuracy dropping from 6m to 20m (Kaplan, 1996). Range measurement with the latter accuracy is known as the *Standard Positioning Service* (SPS). However, the *Precise Positioning Service* (PPS) which was sometimes only accessible by DoD (and authorized users), was designed for precise positioning with an accuracy of 3 to 6m.

Similarly, when *Anti-Spoofing* (AS) was activated, to effectively deny civilians access to L2 frequency, the P code was replaced with another code, the Y code, on the L1 and L2 carrier frequencies. The Y code had a similar property to the P code, but was unknown to the unauthorized users. However, as of 1May 2000 these national security service policies were removed from the system by a special order from the American president Bill Clinton.

Although these services are of relatively good quality, the United States planned for modernizing the signals in order to improve the quality and protection of the both civil and military users.

According to the GPS modernization plan, from December 2005 the L2 carrier wave, like the L1, was modulated with a civil C/A like code in the GPS satellites. Furthermore, for military users a Military (M) code was modulated on L1 and L2 carriers. These satellites are known as the *Block IIR-M* generation. *Block IIF* satellites are the latest generation which will transmit a third frequency (L5=1176.45 MHz) additional to L1 and L2. The L5 wave will be modulated by two I and Q codes. Table 4.3 gives an overview of the GPS signals.

Table 4.3: Overview of current and future GPS signals.

Carrier	Frequency (MHz)	Wavelength (cm)	Civil	Precise	Military
L1	$154 \times 10.23 = 1575.42$	19.03	C/A	P	M
L2	$120 \times 10.23 = 1227.60$	24.42	C/A	P	M
L5	$115 \times 10.23 = 1176.45$	25.48	I + Q		

4.2.2. SCINDA (Scintillation Network and Decision Aid) receiver

The Scintillation Network and Decision Aid (SCINDA) system is a network of ground-based receivers that monitor scintillation at UHF and L-band frequencies caused by electron density irregularities in the equatorial ionosphere (Groves et al., 1997).

The GPS-SCINDA system consists of a GPS receiver, GPS antenna, GPS - SCINDA data collection software and a computer running LINUX with access to the Internet. A schematic of the setup is shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.8. Overview of the GPS Data Acquisition System for SCINDA.

The GPS antenna should be mounted on a pole in clear view of the sky, with a minimum of obstruction nearby (in particular, metallic objects and power lines should be avoided). The antenna is connected to the receiver using the supplied antenna cable. A specialized serial cable connects the GPS receiver to the local computer via its serial port interface.

While the system is operating, the receiver tracks the constellation of visible GPS satellites. The GPS-SCINDA software running on the local computer records the stream of data from the receiver and computes post-processed parameters such as scintillation intensity (S4) index and TEC, and displays them along with information about which satellites the receiver is tracking on the computer screen.

4.2.2.1. SCINDA data format

The GPS-SCINDA software can generate a number of different file types. Each file contains approximately one hour of data, and new files are generated each time the hour changes. The type of files that GPS-SCINDA can generate are differentiated according to their filename extensions (*.xxx). A list of file types that GPS-SCINDA can generate is presented in the following table 4.4:

Table 4.4. Format of the hourly data files produced by GPS-SCINDA.

<i>Filename Extension</i>	<i>File Contents</i>
*.scn	Ionospheric statistics
*.psn	Receiver position
*.msg	Error log and diagnostic messages
*.nvd	Raw data
*.obs	GPS raw observables (S/N ratios, pseudoranges and phases)

These files are named according to the date and time of day, using the format YYMMDD_hhmmss.*:

Table 4.5. Format of the naming file.

Hourly file naming convention, YYMMDD_hhmmss.xxx	
YY	Two digit year
MM	Month (1-12)
DD	Day of month (1-31)
hh	Hour of day (0-23)
mm	Minute of hour (0-59)
ss	Second of minute (0-60)
xxx	Filename extension (different for each type of output file)

For example, the filename for ionospheric statistics data collected starting 7 November 2009 at 12:00 UT would be 091107_120000.scn.

Each data record in the *.scn and *.psn files is preceded by a time-tag of the form: "T YY MM DD SSSSS", followed by the actual data in the record.

Ionospheric Statistics Files (*.scn)

The ionospheric statistics are written to the *.scn files each minute, using data collected during the previous minute. One line of data is written for each satellite tracked, with columns for the different measured parameters shown in table 4.6:

Table 4.6. Ionospheric statistics file description.

<i>Column</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Units</i>
1	Azimuth , α	degree
2	Elevation , ϵ	degree
3	L1S4 : S4 of the C/A code on L1	dimensionless
4	%SAM : Percentage of S/N samples used to compute the S4 on L1, relative to the number expected (0-100%)	
5	L2S4 : S4 of the P code on L2 (unreliable -- do not use)	dimensionless
6	%SAM : Percentage of S/N samples used to compute the S4 on L2, relative to the number expected (0-100%)	
7	TEC _P : Differential pseudorange, DPR	TECU
8	TEC _{ϕ} : Differential carrier phase (with unknown additive offset), DCP	TECU
9	ROTI : Standard deviation of rate of change of TEC over one minute	TECU/sec
10	TEC _R : Relative TEC (uncalibrated slant TEC)	TECU
11	Time since last cycle slip (min)	minutes
12	PRN number	

Below is an excerpt from a sample *.scn file showing ionospheric statistics for the three tracked satellites with PRN numbers 3, 6, and 14.

Table 4.7. *.scn file structure.

Sample *.scn file											
T 09 11 07 54069											
313.7	56.0	0.03	98	0.04	100	45.4	-13.444	6.90	45.0	115	03
318.5	66.7	0.03	98	0.04	100	45.4	-15.716	7.19	46.3	150	06
146.4	31.6	0.09	98	0.16	100	48.8	-56.992	9.29	49.8	59	14
.....											
T 09 11 07 54129											
313.4	56.4	0.03	100	0.04	100	46.2	-13.481	6.89	45.0	116	03
318.2	67.1	0.03	100	0.03	100	45.6	-15.730	7.48	46.3	151	06
146.0	32.0	0.07	100	0.16	100	51.1	-57.312	7.73	49.5	60	14
.....											

Position Files (.psn)*

The receiver position is written to the *.psn files every second. A time-tag is provided only once per minute, but following it will be 60 receiver position updates at one second intervals. The number of columns in the *.psn record is a variable of length, according to the number of satellites tracked (see table 4.8):

Table 4.8. position file description.

<i>Column</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Units</i>
1	Latitude	degrees
2	Longitude	degrees
3	Altitude	meters
4	Number of satellites tracked	
5-17	PRN followed by “U” if it is used in position solution, “-” otherwise.	

Below is an excerpt from a sample *.psn file, showing the time-tag followed by the receiver position and tracking information for a period of one minute beginning at 54069 and 54129 seconds.

Table 4.9. *.psn file structure.

Sample *.psn file											
T	09	11	07	54069							
29.8642353	31.3172692	57.249	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
29.8642352	31.3172695	57.242	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
29.8642351	31.3172692	57.274	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
.....											
.....											
											57 more samples follow
T	09	11	07	54129							
29.8642354	31.3172672	57.474	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
29.8642354	31.3172672	57.445	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
29.8642356	31.3172673	57.477	07	21U	03U	18U	16U	22U	06U	26U	
.....											
.....											
											57 more samples follow

Receiver Independent GPS Observables Files (*.obs)

The SCINDA’s receiver independent GPS observables files (*.obs) contains the raw GPS observables including the pseudoranges, phases, and signal to noise ratios for both the L1 and L2 channels. The information stored in a *.obs file is similar to what would be found in a RINEX * observables file, but the *.obs format uses more significant digits and is more compact in terms of disk space. The format of the receiver independent GPS observables files is given in table 4.10.

A sample excerpt from a receiver independent GPS observables file (*.obs) is given in table 4.11.

* Receiver Independent EXchange format (RINEX) is a data interchange format for raw satellite navigation system data.

Table 4.10. observation file description.

<i>Column</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Units</i>
1	GPS milliseconds of GPS week (0 - 604,800,000)	
2	Warning status on C/A (uZ and Z12 receivers only, otherwise 255)	
3	Warning status on P1 (uZ and Z12 receivers only, otherwise 255)	
4	Warning status on P2 (uZ and Z12 receivers only, otherwise 255)	
5	Signal to noise ratio of the C/A code on L1	dBHz
6	Signal to noise ratio of the P code on L2	dBHz
7	Pseudorange on L1, P ₁	meters
8	Differential pseudorange, P ₂ - P ₁ (note the sign convention)	meters
9	Phase on the L ₁ carrier	L1 cycles
10	Differential carrier phase, L ₂ - 60/77 L ₁ (note the sign convention and units)	L2 cycles
11	PRN	

Table 4.11. *.obs file structure.

Sample *.obs file										
572440000	255	255	255	43.649	35.916	2.30e+07	3.54e+00	1.21e+08	1.77e+02	21
572440000	255	255	255	48.824	42.538	2.08e+07	4.77e+00	1.09e+08	3.16e+01	03
572440000	255	255	255	47.040	38.223	2.22e+07	3.78e+00	1.16e+08	2.24e+01	18
572440000	255	255	255	45.333	38.338	2.26e+07	4.47e+00	1.19e+08	2.02e+02	16
572440000	255	255	255	49.644	44.520	2.04e+07	2.57e+00	1.07e+08	4.85e+01	22
.....										
.....										
.....										

Note that one may convert the differential pseudorange (column 8) and differential carrier phase (column 10) in the *.obs file into units of TECU as follows:

$$DPR = (9.52 \text{ TECU/meter}) \times (\text{column 8}) \tag{4.1}$$

$$DCP = (-2.32 \text{ TECU/L2 cycle}) \times (\text{column 10}) \tag{4.2}$$

More details about this conversion are discussed in chapter 5.

4.2.2.2. SCINDA’s data software

GPS-SCINDA is a real-time GPS data acquisition and ionospheric analysis system for SCINDA, written in C-language for the LINUX operating system. It computes ionospheric parameters S4 and TEC using the full temporal resolution of the receiver. This high rate sampling (10-50 Hz) makes scintillation monitoring possible. Also, it provides a real-time display of satellite tracking status and the ionospheric parameters. The latest version of the software may be downloaded from this URL: <https://wfs.bc.edu/carranoc/scinda/>, including the following files:

Table 4.12. Description the SCINDA software’s package.

Files	Description
install	Script to install (or upgrade) SCINDA software
gps-scinda-1.76.tar.gz	GPS-SCINDA data collection software (binary version)
gps-scinda-src-1.76.tar.gz	GPS-SCINDA data collection software (source code)
wintec-p-1.05.tar.gz	WinTEC-P software for TEC calibration (binary version)
wintec-p-src-1.05.tar.gz	WinTEC-P software for TEC calibration (source code)
gps-scripts-2.00.tar.gz	Scripts for automated data management and delivery

WinTEC-P is a software for the calibration of GPS TEC measurements made using GPS-SCINDA. It is written in C for the LINUX operating system. It can estimate and remove instrumental biases associated with the GPS receiver and (optionally) the GPS satellites without any external information (e.g. satellite biases or almanac files), which makes it well suited for automated processing in the field. It is also have several new features including estimation and removal of the plasmaspheric contribution to the TEC. It has programs written in the GNU R to plot S₄ and calibrated TEC. Scripts are included to automatically generate and archive daily S₄ and TEC plots with 15 minute updates.

A long sequence of ionospheric statistics files (*.scn) can be processed with WinTEC-P, and the coordinates of the station are obtained from the corresponding *.psn files (if present), or they must be specified in the *wintec-p.conf* configuration file.

Make sure that the configuration files *wintec-p.conf*, *s4.conf*, and *tec.conf* are located in the current directory along with the *wintec-p* executable file and the scripts *s4.r*, *tec.r*. These configuration files are listed in Appendixes F, G and H, respectively. It specifies the options to use when calibrating the TEC, for plotting the S4 index, and for plotting the TEC.

When WinTEC-P is run automatically on the data collection computer, output files are two directories “plots” and “processed_data”.

The directory “plots” includes Scintillation intensity index (S4) and calibrated TEC Portable Network Geographic (*.PNG) format for each day (e.g: SYYYYMMDD.PNG and TYYYYMMDD.PNG).

Directory “processed_data” include the following files described in table 4.13.

Table 4.13. Files included in the SCINDA-output directory” processed_data”.

YYMMDD_tec.dat.gz	calibrated TEC
YYMMDD_res.dat.gz	post-fit residual
YYMMDD_cov.dat.gz	Covariances
YYMMDD_state.dat.gz	Kalman state
YYMMDD_model.dat.gz	zenith TEC estimates (ionosphere & plasmasphere)
YYMMDD_biases.dat.gz	Estimated receiver and satellite biases

Here, the structure of the calibrated TEC file (*tec.dat*) and the biases file (*biases.dat*) are shown in table 4.14. The VTEC and S4 plots are already constructed from a real data and given in chapters 5 and 6.

Ch.4. Instruments and Software.

#YYMM DD UTSEC	AZ	EL	PLAT	PLON	PCGLAT	PCMLT	S4	DPR	PTEC	STEC	STECE	VTEC	VTECE	PRN
10 01 01 00063	226.20	25.60	-49.95	-160.74	-50.93	-10.00	0.07	6.55	0.00	6.55	80.32	3.40	41.68	05
10 01 01 00063	68.60	32.20	-44.42	-148.57	-43.02	-9.46	0.06	6.65	0.00	4.01	80.41	2.39	48.01	08
10 01 01 00063	209.10	21.50	-51.87	-159.61	-52.55	-9.83	0.11	9.32	0.00	8.22	80.33	3.87	37.86	10
10 01 01 00063	314.50	48.50	-44.36	-156.98	-44.64	-10.00	0.04	4.69	0.00	3.10	80.33	2.41	62.50	15
10 01 01 00063	135.40	47.90	-48.05	-151.63	-47.14	-9.51	0.05	4.25	0.00	3.90	80.33	3.01	62.02	17
10 01 01 00063	299.50	17.70	-42.01	-163.47	-43.62	13.48	0.12	7.02	0.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	27
10 01 01 00063	32.30	50.40	-44.13	-152.59	-43.54	-9.73	0.05	2.54	0.00	2.75	80.33	2.19	64.01	28
..
YY	2 digit year													
MM	Month													
DD	Day													
UTSEC	Seconds since midnight													
AZ	Azimuth (deg)													
EL	Elevation (deg)													
PLAT	Latitude of IPP (deg)													
PLON	Longitude of IPP (deg)													
PCGLAT	Magnetic latitude of IPP (deg)													
PCMLT	Magnetic local time (hrs)													
			-1 indicates missing values (e.g. elevation too low)											
			(a)											

WINTEC	GNSS C1-P2 DCB SOLUTION, ENDING D001, 2010	01-APR-10 16:15

DIFFERENTIAL (C1-P2) CODE BIASES FOR SATELLITES AND RECEIVERS:		
PRN / STATION NAME	CODE VALUE (TECU)	RMS (TECU)
*****	*****	*****
G01	0.000	316.228
G02	-13.665	56.796
G03	6.870	56.796
...
G30	5.836	56.796
G31	-4.983	56.796
G32	8.402	56.796
REC	31.230	56.796
		(b)

Table 4.14: (a) Structure of the calibrated TEC file (tec.dat), **(b)** Structure of the Biases file (biases.dat).

4.3. Other Satellite-Based Navigation Systems

4.3.1. GLONASS

While GPS was under development, the Soviet Union undertook to develop a similar system called GLONASS. *The GLObal NAVigation Satellite System* (GLONASS), like GPS, is also a dual-use (military and civilian) system that provides both the SPS and PPS services. Since the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the Russian Federation has assumed responsibility for GLONASS.

Its nominal constellation is composed of 24 satellites with an orbital inclination of 64.8° and an orbital radius of 25500 *km*. GLONASS also transmit on the L1 and L2 frequency band, but each satellite transmits its signal with a different frequency offset(Hein and Eissfeller, 2007).

The GLONASS carriers are often denoted by G1 and G2 to distinguish them from the GPS carriers. The complete GLONASS constellation of 24 operational satellites has only been available for a short time in 1996. The current status is far away from its nominal numbers and as of January 18, 2007 only 9 active GLONASS satellites were transmitting from space (Hein and Eissfeller, 2007).

4.3.2. Galileo

The Galileo is the European global navigation satellite system. Unlike GPS and GLONASS, Galileo is under civilian control that have international participation and investment. The Galileo satellite constellation will consist of 30 satellites [27 operational + 3 non-active (spares)].

The satellites are divided over three orbital planes with orbital radius 29,600 *km* at an inclination of 56° . Galileo is not yet in operation but two Galileo's satellite GIOVE-A and GIOVE-B were successfully launched respectively in December 2005 and in April 26 2008. Galileo's satellites transmit on four carrier frequencies that are given in table 4.15.

Galileo plans to provide four types of navigation services:

- The Open Service (OS) provides basic navigation service, like GPS SPS, using freely accessible signals and which are the Open Access Navigation Signals (denoted as F/N) on E5a and the Integrity Navigation Signals

(denoted as I/N) on E5b and E1 (also denoted as L1 or E2-L1-E1), but without the commercial data or integrity messages.

Table 4.15: Galileo’s signal plan (+: with integrity message, ++: with commercial data) [adopted from (Verhagen, 2005)].

Carrier	Frequency [MHz]	Wavelength [cm]	OS	SOL	CS	PRS
E1	$154 \times 10.23 = 1575.42$	19.0	I/N	I/N+	I/N++	G/N
E6	$125 \times 10.23 = 1278.75$	23.4			C/N++	G/N
E5b	$118 \times 10.23 = 1207.14$	24.8	I/N	I/N+	I/N	
E5	$116.5 \times 10.23 = 1191.79$	25.2				
E5a	$115 \times 10.23 = 1176.45$	25.5	F/N	F/N	F/N	

- Safety-Of-Life (SOL) provides access to the same signals as OS users, but additionally SOL users have access to the I/N including the integrity messages transmitted on the E5b and E1 carriers.
- The Commercial Service (CS) is also available at the same signals at the OS, but users will have additional access to commercial data (for which they have to pay) transmitted on the Integrity Navigation Signals on E5b and E1, and to the Controlled Access Navigation Signals (denoted as C/N) on E6.
- The Public Regulated Service (PRS) will include navigation and timing services through Restricted Access Navigation Signals (denoted as G/N) on E6 and E1.

4.3.3. Compass

A Chinese satellite navigation system called *Compass* (or *Beidou-2*) which is presently under development. As with GPS, GLONASS, and Galileo, the system is a dual use system which will provide two navigation services: an open service for (commercial) users and an authorized positioning, velocity, and timing communications service (Hein and Eissfeller, 2007). Compass consists of a constellation of 35 satellites, 5 geostationary orbit (GEO) satellites, and 30 Medium-Earth-Orbit (MEO) satellites, that will offer complete coverage of the globe (Hofmann- Wellenhof et al., 2008). The non-stationary satellites will be in 3 orbital planes with an inclination of 55° and with orbital radius of 27,900 km. The geosynchronous orbit satellites have an

altitude of 35,785 *km* with an inclination angle equal to 55°. China sent the first non-stationary Compass satellite on April 13, 2007 and the first GEO satellite of Compass has been launched on February 3, 2007. Each Compass's satellite transmits navigational signals the same for carrier frequencies. Frequencies for Compass are allocated in four bands: E1, E2, E5B, and E6 and overlap with Galileo. The fact of overlapping could be convenient from the point of view of the receiver design, but on the other hand raises the issues of inter-system interference, especially within E1 and E2 bands, which are allocated for Galileo's publicly-regulated service [Galileo, Compass on collision course, GPS World, April 2008, p. 27]. Little official information is publicly available about structure of the Compass's signals.

4.3.4. QZSS

The Japanese government in conjunction with an industry consortium is undertaking development of *Quasi-Zenith Satellite System (QZSS)*, a regional system to transmit ranging signals over Japan from satellites in highly elliptical orbits.

4.3.5. International GNSS Service (IGS)

Similar systems and satellite-based augmentations are being developed and deployed by governments, international consortia, and commercial interests. The generic name given to these systems is Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS).

Within the last decades, the GPS has come to play a major role in Earth sciences. In the fact of continued growth and diversification of GPS applications, the international scientific community has made an effort to promote international standards for GPS data acquisition and analysis, and to deploy and operate a common, comprehensive global GPS tracking network. As a result of this effort, the International Association of Geodesy (IGS) in 1993 and began its official operation on 1 January 1994 (Beutler et al., 1994, 1995b; Neilan, 1995).

The International GNSS Service (IGS), formerly the International GPS Service, is a voluntary federation of more than 200 worldwide agencies that pool resources and permanent GPS & GLONASS station data to generate precise GPS & GLONASS products. The IGS is committed to providing the

highest quality data and products as the standard for Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) in support of Earth science research, multidisciplinary applications, and education. Currently the IGS includes two GNSS, GPS and the Russian GLONASS, and intends to incorporate future GNSS. You can think of the IGS as the highest-precision international civilian GPS community.

Finally, the idea of satellite navigation is not limited to the Earth. After two recent high-profile failures in the Mars program, NASA has considered a system of low-orbiting satellites around Mars to provide GPS-like navigation signals and a better communications link to the control center.

4.4. MAGnetic Data Acquisition System (MAGDAS)

The MAGDAS System provides amplitude-time records of ordinary magnetic field variations and time-derivative magnetic field variations. The ordinary data is useful for studies of long-term variations, e.g. magnetic storm, auroral substorms, Sq, etc., while time-derivative data is useful for studies of ULF waves, transient and impulsive phenomena.

Figure 4.9. MAGDAS/CPMN (MAGnetic Data Acquisition System/Circum-pan Pacific Magnetometer Network) system.

The MAGDAS Project effectively started in May of 2005, with the installation of the first unit in Hualien, Taiwan. Since then, over 40 units have been deployed around the world. The goal of MAGDAS is to become the most comprehensive ground-based monitoring system of the Earth's magnetic field. It does not compete with space-based observation. Rather, this ground-based network complements observation from space.

The MAGDAS system is now being deployed in order to carry out space weather studies. We have in Egypt two stations installed of this project, one of them at Fayum and the other at Aswan as shown in figure 4.9. The coordinate details of the two stations and installation date is shown in table 4.16.

Table 4.16. the coordinate details of the two MAGDAS stations in Egypt.

Station Name	Abbrev.	Geog. Lat.	Geog. Long.	Geomag. Lat.	Geomag. Long.	Install
Fayum	FYM	29.18	30.50	26.54	107.83	14/01/2008
Aswan	ASW	23.59	32.51	15.20	104.24	23/12/2008

5 TEC extraction and measurements

Since the launch of *Sputnik I* (1957), satellite radio beacon signals have been widely used in exploring the temporal and spatial structure of the ionosphere (Jakowski et al., 1996) and proved their usefulness for remotely sensing the Earth's ionosphere. Nowadays, the space-based radio navigation systems offer a good opportunity for studying the ionosphere on a global scale. This is possible because their satellites transmit coherent dual-frequency signals, which is low enough in frequency to measure the ionospheric contribution.

The Global Positioning System (GPS) and Coherent Ionospheric Doppler Receiver (CIDR) system offers good opportunities for studying the ionosphere on a global scale. Both of these systems have their own satellites which transmit their own coherent dual-frequency signals. The ionospheric contribution is proportional to the Total Electron Content, TEC, along the ray path between satellite and receiver. TEC is measured in total electron content units (TECU; 1 TECU being 10^{16} electrons/m²). Depending on local time, solar activity, geomagnetic conditions, region of the Earth, etc., the vertical TEC varies from about 1 to 180 TECU. In this chapter, the methods and techniques of extracting ionospheric Total Electron Content (TEC) from both GPS and CIDR signals will be discussed.

When an electromagnetic wave propagates in free space, its velocity is known to be equal to the velocity of light c . When the wave propagates in a medium, its velocity changes due to interaction with the particles present in that medium. This is known as wave refraction and the amount of refraction is described by the medium specific refractive index. Refractive index of a medium n is defined as the ratio of the velocity of light in free space c to the velocity of the wave in a medium v ,

$$n = c/v \quad (5.1)$$

In free space the refractive index equals 1. When the refractive index is smaller than 1 we say that the wave is advanced and when it is larger than 1 it is delayed.

The measurements of TEC are based on the description of the ionosphere as a refractive medium, so it is important to have an understanding of the ionospheric refractive index.

5.1. Refractive index of the Ionosphere

The ionosphere is an ionized medium, or plasma, of relatively low temperature compared to other plasmas encountered in space and the laboratory. As a cold plasma, the *phase refractive index* (n_p) for the electrically neutral ionosphere, with a uniform magnetic field, is expressed by the complex *Appleton-Hartee* (or *Appleton-Lassen*) formula, derived in many books and papers on the ionosphere (e.g. Ratcliffe, 1959, Hargreaves, 1992 and Klobuchar, 1996).

$$n_p^2 = 1 - \frac{X}{1 - iZ - \frac{Y_T^2}{2(1 - X - iZ)} \pm \left[\frac{Y_T^4}{4(1 - X - iZ)^2} + Y_L^2 \right]^{1/2}} \quad (5.2)$$

where;

$$X = \frac{N_e \cdot e^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e \omega^2} = \left(\frac{f_N}{f} \right)^2 \quad \text{a non-dimension form of the plasma freq.}$$

$$Z = \frac{\nu}{\omega} \quad \text{a non-dimension form of the electron collision freq.}$$

$$Y_L = \frac{e B_L}{m_e \omega} = \frac{f_H \cos \theta}{f} \quad \text{the Longitudinal gyro-freq.}$$

$$Y_T = \frac{e B_T}{m_e \omega} = \frac{f_H \sin \theta}{f} \quad \text{the Transverse gyro-freq.}$$

e the electron charge ($e = 1.602 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C).

ϵ_0 permittivity of free space ($\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F m^{-1}).

m_e the electron rest mass ($m_e = 9.107 \cdot 10^{-31}$ Kg).

f the system operating frequency in Hz.

f_N the electron plasma frequency.

N_e the plasma electron density in m^{-3} .

f_H the electron gyrofrequency .

ν the electron-neutral collision frequency.

ω the angular frequency ($\omega = 2\pi f$).

θ the angle of the ray with respect to the Earth's magnetic field.

The ionosphere refractive index is unfortunately not a constant. This is because the ionosphere is an *inhomogeneous*, *anisotropic* and a *dispersive* medium and all of these properties are all present in the *Appleton-Hartree formula* (eq.5.2).

The *inhomogeneity* of the ionosphere is reflected in the free electron density N_e , which is not a constant, but a function of place and time. As a consequence, the ionospheric refractive index varies significantly in the spatial domain. Changing in the ionospheric refractive index along propagation path results in bending of the path of a signal ray, making the path longer than the geometrical straight line path, see figure 5.1.

Moreover, the *dispersive* nature of the ionosphere can be recognized in the dependence on the frequency of the wave.

Notes

To describe the propagation of a modulated electromagnetic wave through a dispersive medium, we should distinguish between the phase velocity, denoted as v_ϕ (velocity of the carrier wave), and the group velocity of the signal, denoted as v_g (velocity of the modulation of a wave). Hence, the refractive indices for phase and group of the signal are different;

$$n_\phi = c/v_\phi$$

$$n_g = c/v_g.$$

The relation between v_g and v_ϕ is given by the Rayleigh equation;

$$v_g = v_\phi + f \frac{\partial v_\phi}{\partial f}$$

where f is frequency of the carrier wave.

The *anisotropic* ionosphere is expressed in the terms depending on the geomagnetic field (\vec{B}). A medium is said to be isotropic if the phase refractive index (or the phase velocity) of a wave is independent of the direction. Since the Earth's ionosphere is coupled with the geomagnetic field, the ionospheric refractive index depends on the direction of wave propagation relative to the geomagnetic field (\vec{B}). Therefore, the ionosphere is not an isotropic medium for electromagnetic wave propagation.

There is also another effect. Under influence of the geomagnetic field an electromagnetic wave is split up into two approximately parallel wavefronts, which each have an opposite (circular) polarization. One wave, the *ordinary*

wave, with a right-handed polarization, but the other one, the extraordinary wave has a left-handed polarization. Both waves show a small difference in propagation velocity and consequently in refractive index. This effect is known as double refraction or birefringence. Despite this double refraction, only the ordinary wave needs to be considered in case of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), because the extraordinary wave contains less than 0.35% of the power (for L1) (Bassiri and Hajj, 1993).

The double-refraction is reflected by the \pm sign in equation 5.2, which means that either a plus or minus sign can be used, depending on the polarization of the wave: A^{++} corresponds to the left-handed circularly polarized wave (the extraordinary wave) and a^{--} to the right-handed circularly polarized wave (the ordinary wave). Since for (GNSS) only the ordinary wave is significant, from now on only the refractive index using the *minus sign* is considered.

Since the electron gyrofrequency (f_H) is typically 1.5 MHz ; whereas the plasma frequency (f_N) exceeds 20 MHz and the collision frequency (ν) is approximately 10^4 Hz (Klobuchar,1996), then for an electromagnetic wave at ultra-high frequency both the electron-neutral collisions(ν) and the effects of geomagnetic field (\vec{B}) on the refractive index are negligible, which leads to $Z = Y_L = Y_T = 0$ (Ratcliffe, 1959, Hargreaves, 1992, Klobuchar,1996).

Then the *ionospheric phase refractive index* (n_p) is reduced to:

$$n_p^2 = 1 - X. \tag{5.3}$$

Since at ultra-high frequency $X \ll 1$, then by using the Binomial Theorem;

$$n_p = 1 - \frac{X}{2} = 1 - \frac{N_e e^2}{2 \epsilon_0 m \omega^2} = 1 - \frac{N_e e^2}{8\pi^2 \epsilon_0 m f^2} \tag{5.4}$$

$$\boxed{n_p = 1 - \frac{K N_e}{2f^2}} \tag{5.5}$$

Where $K = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e 4\pi^2} = 80.96 \text{ m}^3/\text{sce}^2$.

The phase (n_p) and group (n_g) refractive indices are related to each other (Raticlife, 1959; Wellenhof et al., 1997) as follows:

$$n_g = n_p + f \frac{dn_p}{df} \tag{5.6}$$

This leads to an expression for n_g being more complicated than that for n_p (Ratcliffe, 1959; Hofmann-Wellenhof et al., 1997). However, by using the same approximations used to reduce eq 5.2 to Eq 5.5 and substituting it into Eq 5.6, the *ionospheric group refractive index* is given as follows:

$$n_g = \left(1 - \frac{KN_e}{2f^2}\right) + f \frac{d}{df} \left(1 - \frac{KN_e}{2f^2}\right) \quad (5.7)$$

$$= 1 - \frac{KN_e}{2f^2} + f \left(\frac{KN_e}{f^3}\right)$$

$$= 1 - \frac{KN_e}{2f^2} + \frac{KN_e}{f^2}$$

$$\boxed{n_g = 1 + \frac{KN_e}{2f^2}} \quad (5.8)$$

It is seen that the phase refractive index is always smaller than 1, while the group refractive index is larger than 1. This implies that in the ionosphere the phase of the wave is advanced while at the same time its group is delayed.

Figure 5.1. Bending of a wave through inhomogeneous refractive medium.

5.2. GPS signal propagation effect

As explained before in chapter 4, each GPS satellite continuously transmits on two different frequencies at the microwave L-band at $f_1 = 1.5754$ GHz (L1) and $f_2 = 1.2276$ GHz (L2). When traveling through the atmosphere, the signals are subject to modifications in amplitude, phase and polarization.

Of particular relevance here are *phase changes* and *propagation delays* in the GPS signals observed on the ground. These effects are made up of several contributions, including; the ionospheric delay (I), the tropospheric delay (T), delays due to system clocks (D_S), and RF delays in the RF stages of the transmitters (D^T) and receivers (D^R).

The total time delay inferred at the L carrier frequencies f_1, f_2 respectively is;

$$t_1 = I_1 + T + D_S + D_1^T + D_1^R + \varepsilon_t \quad (5.9)$$

$$t_2 = I_2 + T + D_S + D_2^T + D_2^R + \varepsilon_t \quad (5.10)$$

where,

I_1, I_2 Ionospheric group delay imposed at the L carrier frequencies f_1, f_2 , respectively.

T Tropospheric time delay.

D_S Delays due to system clocks.

D_1^T, D_2^T Transmitter group delays imposed at the L carrier frequencies f_1, f_2 , respectively.

D_1^R, D_2^R Receiver group delays imposed at the L carrier frequencies f_1, f_2 , respectively.

ε_t random error in the time delay.

All the delays (I, D^T and D^R) are due to the dispersive nature of the ionosphere, whereas the Tropospheric delay (T) contributes to the non-dispersive neutral atmosphere (with respect to radio waves up to frequencies of 1.5 GHz). Similarly the delay due to the system clocks (D_S) in the same for both frequencies. So no distinction is made between these contributions (T and D_S) to the carrier phases and code ranges on different carriers.

Then, the difference in delay between the two frequencies (Δt) is given as;

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t &= t_2 - t_1 = (I_2 - I_1) + (D_2^T - D_1^T) + (D_2^R - D_1^R) \\ \Delta t &= (I_2 - I_1) + \Delta D^T + \Delta D^R \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

The ionospheric contributions (I_1 and I_2) are proportional to the line integral of electron densities along the GPS ray path (Klobuchar et al., 1994; Klobuchar, 1996; Breed, 1996), and mathematically written as:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \frac{K}{2c f_1^2} \int N_e ds = \frac{K}{2c f_1^2} STEC \\ I_2 &= \frac{K}{2c f_2^2} \int N_e ds = \frac{K}{2c f_2^2} STEC \end{aligned} \quad (5.12)$$

where,

($C = 3 * 10^8$ m/sec) is the speed of electromagnetic wave in free space.

Note that the time delay difference between L1 and L2 signals cancels out the unknown time delay due to system clocks (D_S) and the tropospheric delay(T), see eq. 5.11, and the frequency dependent ionospheric delay (I) provides an expression for $STEC$. In the subsequent section a detail of GPS TEC extraction method are given.

5.3. GPS TEC extraction

Methods of extracting TEC from trans-ionospheric satellite signals have been described by several authors (Garriott, et al, 1970, Klobuchar et al., 1994; Klobuchar, 1996, Hargreaves, 1992, Sardon et al., 1994; Jakowski et al., 1996; Leva and Dyke, 1996).

Each of the 31 operational GPS satellites is broadcasting information on two frequency carrier signals, and the receivers provides two distances (known as *Pseudorange*, P_1, P_2), and two phase measurements (φ_1, φ_2) corresponding to the two signals. Due to the dispersive nature of the ionosphere, the two radio signals are delayed and their phases are advanced.

The two main techniques used to determine the ionospheric effects on GPS signals are known as ⁽¹⁾ the differential time delay technique and ⁽²⁾ the differential phase advance technique.

Hence, the electron content along the GPS signal path between the satellite and receiver (*STEC*) can be obtained from ⁽¹⁾ the difference between the pseudoranges (P_1 and P_2), and from ⁽²⁾ the difference between the phases (φ_1 and φ_2) of the two signals (Klobuchar et al., 1994; Klobuchar, 1996; Breed , 1996; Jakowski et al., 1996).

5.3.1. Slant TEC extraction from differential time delay

Here, the differential time delay is calculated from the GPS observable "group path lengths P_1 and P_2 " that are given in units of meter. The equivalent absolute STEC can be then obtained from the differential time delay as following.

For the L1 frequency, the total group path length (*pseudorange*) P_1 between the satellite and receiver is given as:

$$P_1 = \int_R^S n_g dr \quad (5.13)$$

By defining \mathcal{R} as the free space path length between the satellite and receiver, it obtained by setting $n_g = 1$

$$\mathcal{R} = \int_R^S 1 dr. \quad (5.14)$$

Then, the group path defect (pseudorange defect) ΔP_1 will be the difference between the group path length P_1 and the free path length \mathcal{R} :

$$\Delta P_1 = P_1 - \mathcal{R} = \int_R^S (n_g - 1) dr \quad (5.15)$$

$$= \int_R^S \left[\left(1 + \frac{K N_e}{2f_1^2} \right) - 1 \right] dr$$

$$\Delta P_1 = \frac{K}{2f_1^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.16)$$

and the ionospheric group time delay (Δt) will be

$$\Delta t_1 = \frac{\Delta P_1}{c} = \frac{K}{2cf_1^2} \int_R^S N_e dr. \quad (5.17)$$

In the same way, for GPS signal at L2 frequency:

$$\Delta P_2 = P_2 - \mathcal{R} = \int_R^S (n_g - 1) dr = \frac{K}{2f_2^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.18)$$

The difference between ΔP_2 and ΔP_1 provides the *differential group defect* $P_{1,2}$ (in units of meter);

$$P_{1,2} = \Delta P_2 - \Delta P_1 = \frac{K}{2} \left(\frac{f_1^2 - f_2^2}{f_1^2 f_2^2} \right) \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.19)$$

By defining the Slant Total Electron Content (*STEC*) as: $\int_R^S N_e dr = STEC$, equation (5.19) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} STEC_P &= \int_R^S N_e dr = \left[\frac{2}{K} \left(\frac{f_1^2 f_2^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} \right) \right] P_{1,2} \\ STEC_P &= (9.509 * 10^{16}) P_{1,2} \end{aligned} \quad (5.20)$$

(i.e., every meter of pseudorange difference represents 9.509 TECU of STEC.)

Similarly, the *differential time delay* ($\delta\Delta t$) can be obtained from eq. (5.19) as:

$$\delta\Delta t = \frac{\Delta P_2}{c} - \frac{\Delta P_1}{c} = \frac{K}{2c} \left(\frac{f_1^2 - f_2^2}{f_1^2 f_2^2} \right) \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.21)$$

and the STEC can be obtained as;

$$\begin{aligned} STEC &= \int_R^S N_e dr = \frac{2c}{K} \left(\frac{f_1^2 f_2^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} \right) \delta\Delta t \\ &= (2.852 * 10^{25}) \delta\Delta t \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

(i.e., every nanosecond of the differential time delay represents 2.852 TECU of STEC.)

Therefore, by measuring the group path delay (P) independently at two frequencies f_1, f_2 and calculating the differential group defect $P_{1,2}$, the STEC could be extracted using the differential group path defect (Eq 5.19) or the differential time delay ($\delta\Delta t$), eq 5.21.

Note that;

The ionospheric group delay (Δt_1 & Δt_2) can also be expressed in units of time delay, using Eqs (5.16) and (5.18), as follows.

$$\Delta t_1 = \frac{\Delta P_1}{c} = \frac{K}{2cf_1^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.23)$$

$$\Delta t_2 = \frac{\Delta P_2}{c} = \frac{K}{2cf_2^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.24)$$

and related to the differential time delay using equation (5.21);

$$\Delta t_1 = \left(\frac{f_2^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} \right) \delta \Delta t \quad (5.25)$$

5.3.2. Slant TEC extraction from differential phase advance

An alternative method to estimate the TEC along the LOS of each GPS satellite is by measuring the carrier phase on the L1 and L2 frequencies. This method is the same as that of range error (pseudorange) except the expression for the group path length, P , is replaced by the phase path length, ϕ , and the group refractive index, n_g , by the phase refractive index, n_p . Hence the phase path length of L1 frequency ϕ_1 is given as:

$$\phi_1 = \int_R^S n_p dr \quad (5.26)$$

and the phase path defect (carrier phase advance), $\Delta \phi_1$, at L1 frequency is :

$$\Delta \phi_1 = \phi_1 - \mathcal{R} = \int_R^S (n_p - 1) dr = -\frac{K}{2f_1^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.27)$$

A similar expression is obtained for the phase path defect at L2 frequency, such that the differential phase path becomes;

$$\phi_{1,2} = \Delta \phi_2 - \Delta \phi_1 = \phi_2 - \phi_1 = \frac{K}{2} \left(\frac{f_1^2 - f_2^2}{f_1^2 f_2^2} \right) \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.28)$$

Note that the minus sign in equation 5.27 indicates that the ionosphere introduced different effects on carrier phase and pseudorange measurements. The former experience an earlier arrival at the receiver than it would have had the signal travelled from the satellite in a complete vacuum (hence termed a phase advance). On the other hand the latter suffers a propagation delay. However, the magnitude of the group delay is identical to the magnitude of the phase advance, it just has an opposite sign.

Note that;

The phase path defect (carrier phase advance), $\Delta \phi_1$, (eq 5.26) and the group time delay, Δt_1 , (eq 5.22) at L1 frequency are related by:

$$\Delta \phi_1 = -c\Delta t_1 = -c \left(\frac{f_2^2}{f_1^2 - f_2^2} \right) \delta\Delta t = -\frac{K}{2f_1^2} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.29)$$

(Measured in length units)

Also, if the phase path defect is given in units of wavelength or cycles and keeping in mind that the speed of light is $c = \lambda f$, then:

$$\Delta \phi_1 = -f_1\Delta t_1 = -\frac{K}{2cf_1} \int_R^S N_e dr \quad (5.30)$$

(Measured in numbers of wavelength)

5.3.3. Absolute TEC from GPS measurements

The TEC estimated above are affected by different types of errors. The $STEC_P$, extracted from the differential pseudorange GPS signals, is strongly affected by multipath effects* especially at low elevation angles, introducing strong fluctuations that may exceed the expected TEC values because of the extra path length travelled (see Figure 5.2). Therefore, in order to minimize the multipath effect, a minimum 20° elevation cut off angle has been set throughout the TEC extraction.

On the other hand for the $STEC_\phi$, derived from the differential phase, any phase errors must be between 0 and 2π , and due to the short wavelength of the radio waves, the multipath effect practically disappears and thus smooth and high precision values of STEC are obtained.

However, the 2π ambiguity in the phase measurements means that the absolute level of TEC is not obtained, so an "offset" TEC, often called *relative TEC*, is obtained and referenced to an arbitrary zero reference value at the start of the observation of satellite pass. Therefore, to retain the absolute level of differential group delay data ($STEC_P$), the much more precise differential carrier phase data ($STEC_\phi$) are then adjusted by a constant to the level of the differential group delay.

* Multipath effects: describes reflections due to surfaces in the vicinity of the receiving antennae, introducing different delays and reflection coefficients relative to the direct path.

Figure 5.2. A typical GPS satellite pass shows the pseudorange (code) TEC, phase TEC and elevation angle. The two vertical broken lines depict a minimum 20° elevation cut off angle.

This of shift is termed as a *baseline correction* or *calibration constant* (Mannucc et al., 1998; Horvath, 2002). So the *Absolute Slant TEC* (ASTE_C), sometimes called the leveled slant TEC, is given as:

$$ASTE_{C} = STEC_{\varphi} + Baseline \tag{5.31}$$

If N measurements are available, the Baseline can be computed as a RMS of the differences between the pseudorange derived $STEC_{P}$ and the phase derived $STEC_{\varphi}$ values over the index i from $i = 1$ to N .

$$Baseline = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N [(STEC_{P})_i - (STEC_{\varphi})_i]^2}{N}} \tag{5.32}$$

Finally, these leveled (or ASTEC) carrier phase data are then used for further processing.

The TEC estimated above (Eq. 5.31) have two errors due to the hardware systems (satellite and receiver) and are usually known as differential instrumental biases or simply instrumental biases which can reach up to several nanoseconds ($1ns = 2.852 \times 10^{16} \text{ electron}/m^2$).

Several ways of estimating these instrumental biases (Davies and Hartmann 1997, Breed et al 1997, Makela and Kelley, 2001, Ma and Maruyama 2003), all require an implicit assumptions such as the assumption of a constant vertical TEC, at least for relatively short time series (no more than about 30 minutes), and the assumption of zero horizontal TEC gradients. Outlines about these instrumental errors and methods of estimating it is presented at the end of this section.

The actual unbiased (bias corrected) ASTEC is given as:

$$ASTEC_{cor} = ASTEC - B^S - B^R \quad (5.33)$$

where

B^S is the satellite bias (TECU).

B^R is the receiver bias (TECU).

The Slant TEC can be converted into Vertical TEC, which is more useful parameter for describing the overall ionization on the ionosphere, by using a mapping function $\xi(h_{pp}, \alpha)$.

In determining this mapping function, the ionosphere is assumed to be equivalent to a thin shell encircling the Earth with its center the same as that of the Earth. Thus, it is assumed that there is no horizontal gradient along the slant line of sight path from the satellite to the receiver. The geometry of the satellite, receiver and the ionosphere is shown in Figure 5.3. The interaction of the slant path from the satellite (S) to the receiver (R) at the ionospheric median height (h_{pp}) is referred to as an ionospheric piercing point (IPP). Its projection vertically downwards to the surface of the Earth (G) is known as the sub-ionospheric point, and the angle between the vertical and the slant path at piercing point is called the *satellite zenith angle*, χ , (Jakowski, 1996; Jakowski et al., 1996; Ma and Maruyama, 2003). Thus, the zenith angle χ is expressed as:

$$\chi = \sin^{-1} \frac{R_E \cos \alpha}{R_E + h_{pp}} \quad (5.34)$$

The mapping function then will be $\xi(h_{pp}, \alpha) = \sec \chi$, and then the VTEC can be obtained as follows;

$$VTEC = \frac{ASTEC_{cor}}{\xi(h_{pp}, \alpha)} = ASTEC_{cor} \left(\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{R_E \cos \alpha}{R_E + h_{pp}} \right)^2} \right). \quad (5.35)$$

Previous studies indicate that within an altitude range from 350 km to 450 km, different sub-ionospheric point altitude when computing TEC will result in an error ranging from 0.1 TECU to 0.7 TECU. The sub-ionospheric point, in this study, is set at 350 km altitude.

Figure 5.3. The ray path geometry for trans-ionospheric satellite signals between satellites S1, 2 and receiver R. χ is the zenith angle of the ray path RS1 at the ionospheric pierce point (IPP) at an altitude of h_{pp} . The projection of the pierce point P on the ground G is known as sub-ionospheric point.

Now let's show the ways of instrumental biases estimation in this study:

- **Satellite biases** are offsets between the times of transmission, from each GPS satellite, of similar signals at the two L-band frequencies. Each of the 31 satellite has its own bias.

We use estimates for the instrumental biases provided by the Center for Orbit Determination in Europe (CODE) at this URL: <http://www.aiub.unibe.ch/download/CODE/>. These biases are available by FTP download as 30 day averages with the mean satellite differential biases removed (Schaer, et al., 1998).

- Similarly, **receiver biases** are offsets introduced by the receiving hardware or software (Breed et al (1997), Makela and Kelley, 2001).

There are many techniques available for estimating the differential code bias for a GPS receiver (e.g. Mannucci et al. 1998 and Rideout et al. 2006).

These approaches often rely on common volume observations provided by intersecting lines of sight to the satellites from multiple GPS receivers on the ground. The SCINDA system is generally too sparse for this approach to be effective.

The approach we use to estimate the receiver bias is founded on the principle that the slant TEC is a function of elevation (due to the increased path length through the ionosphere) while the contribution due to the receiver bias is not. If the single layer approximation for the ionosphere is valid (a single thin layer at an assumed height) and in the absence of spatiotemporal density gradients, then the verticalized TEC from each satellite should be the same (DattaBarua et al., 2003).

At low to mid latitudes this condition is most closely met just before local sunrise, although there are cases where the ionosphere is highly structured even late at night so that this assumption is invalid (Carrano et al., 2006). We estimate the receiver bias once per day using data collected between 03:00 - 06:00 LT, according to the following algorithm which is valid when gradients in TEC approximately vanish during this time period.

Given a guess for the receiver bias, we can compute the total variance, $V(B^R)$, of the calculated VTEC values summed over bins (i) of local time (at the ionospheric penetration points) taken between 03:00 and 06:00 LT when ionospheric gradients are generally smallest:

$$V(B^R) = \sum_i \text{Variance}[VTEC(B^R)]_i \quad (5.36)$$

Only data from satellites above 20° in elevation are included to minimize multipath effects. Since the variance in Eq (5.36) is a function only of the assumed receiver bias, we can minimize it to determine the value of the receiver bias that yields the least variation between the vertical TEC curves from each satellite during the nighttime window (e.g.; Press et al., 1992) .

The subdivision and binning of the data in local time is intended to decrease the contribution of small local time gradients in TEC to the net variance. We find these small temporal gradients to have minimal adverse effects on the bias determination and that minimizing the variance of vertical TEC in 12 minute bins of local time yields better results than simply minimizing the variance over the entire three hour window.

We find that the estimation of the receiver bias we produce with this method sometime fluctuate unsatisfactorily from night to night. Therefore, we use a 14 day running average of the estimated receiver bias (with outliers discarded) to calibrate the TEC for that day. This approach is taken to minimize the effects of ionospheric disturbances that occur during the calibration window on a night to night basis (Carrano et al., 2006).

Figure 5.4 shows an example for the calibrated vertical TEC from Helwan (26.91°N Magnetic Latitude) versus local time (LT = UT + 2) and versus also universal time (UT). The post-processing were made at Space Weather Monitoring Center (SWMC), using the DPR and DCP measurements from the hourly *.scn files generated by GPS-SCINDA . The TEC measured along each GPS satellite link is colored according to the magnetic latitude of the ionospheric penetration point (IPP).

Figure 5.4. Calibrated vertical equivalent TEC at Helwan on February 4, 2010. The TEC from each satellite is plotted against the local time and the ionospheric penetration point (IPP) set at a height of 350 km. The TEC curves are colored according to the magnetic latitude of the vertical projection of the IPP onto the ground.

Plotting in this format facilitates the study of large scale TEC gradients as a function of both time and magnetic latitude as measured by a standalone GPS receiver. The receiver's field of view covers measurements ranging from 13.4° MLT (low latitude) into 29° MLT (mid latitude), colored from blue to red, respectively.

We note that the subtraction of the satellite and receiver differential code biases from the relative TEC occasionally produces slightly negative values for the calibrated TEC. This situation is unphysical, of course, and is generally a result of poor estimate for the receiver bias. This can happen when there is structure in the TEC late at night so that our assumption of no spatial gradients during the calibration window is violated. Whenever a negative estimate for the calibrated TEC occurs, we re-estimate the receiver bias as the value that produces no negative values for the calibrated TEC.

5.4. CIDR TEC Extraction

TEC measurements associated with Low-Earth-Orbit (LEO) radio beacons are quite different from GPS-based TEC measurements.

The first difference is in the frequency of the radio signals. These LEO beacons operate in the VHF (150 MHz) and UHF (400 MHz) frequencies.

The second difference is that these spacecraft fly at a variety of altitudes and inclination as is shown in Table 5.1. Because these spacecraft fly at lower orbits, the measured TEC is purely ionospheric as opposed to GPS TEC measurements which have a minor plasmaspheric component. In addition, the satellite crosses the receiver's field-of-view more quickly in roughly 20 min. The rapid transit of the satellite across the receiver's field-of-view leads to TEC measurements which primarily detect spatial variations within the ionosphere.

Finally, these radio beacons do not transmit a valid navigation message. The former navigation satellites still transmit a navigation message on operational or maintenance channels. However this message has not been updated for several years and can not be used to calculate either the pseudorange or the carrier phase. Hence, the TEC needs to be calculated differently.

Table 5.1: The satellites with functioning radio beacons observable by CIDR systems and their orbital parameters as of December 2006.

Satellite	Inclination (°)	Altitude (Km)	Period (min)
OSCAR 23 (NIMS)	90.25	1158	109
OSCAR 25 (NIMS)	89.88	1103	107
OSCAR 31 (NIMS)	89.88	1103	107
OSCAR 32 (NIMS)	90.25	1157	108
GFO	108.05	787	101
RADCAL	89.51	816	101
DMSP F15	98.56	839	102
FORMOSAT 3A	72.02	521	95
FORMOSAT 3B	72.03	521	95
FORMOSAT 3C	72.02	802	101
FORMOSAT 3D	72.02	521	95
FORMOSAT 3E	72.01	521	95
FORMOSAT 3F	72.03	716	99

Note that FORMOSAT and COSMIC are interchangeable names.

The fundamental ionosphere parameters observed by CIDRs are the TEC rate of change, the relative TEC, and the ionospheric phase change in the UHF and VHF channels.

The actual measurements are the frequency Doppler shift in the UHF and VHF radio channels. The Doppler shift (δf) is considered to be made up of two components: Doppler shift caused by the satellite's motion and Doppler shift contributed to the ionosphere (Garner et al., 2008). So we can write:

$$\delta f = \frac{f}{c} V_{LOS} - f \frac{dI}{dt} + v_f \tag{5.37}$$

Where V_{LOS} is the velocity of the slant path, I is the ionospheric delay (see eq.5.12), and v_f is the noise in the frequency term. The second term is due to the plasma motion.

In order to remove the frequency independent Doppler of the satellite motion and separate the frequency dependent Doppler of the ionospheric contribution, the above Eq. (5.37) must be down-converted to a common frequency $f_o = 50$ MHz so that $f_{VHF} = 3f_o$ and $f_{UHF} = 8f_o$, and then differencing the resultant Doppler shifts (Garner et al., 2008).

This is given as;

$$\Delta\delta f_{DC} = \frac{1}{8}\delta f_{UHF} - \frac{1}{3}\delta f_{VHF} \quad (5.38)$$

$$\Delta\delta f_{DC} = \frac{1}{8}\left(\frac{f_{UHF}}{c}V_{LOS} - f_{UHF}\frac{dI_{UHF}}{dt}\right) - \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{f_{VHF}}{c}V_{LOS} - f_{VHF}\frac{dI_{VHF}}{dt}\right) + \Delta\nu_f \quad (5.39)$$

Substituting the value of the ionospheric time delay (I) from eq.(5.12), the result will be,

$$\Delta\delta f_{DC} = \frac{1}{8}\left(-\frac{K}{2cf_{UHF}}\frac{dSTECC}{dt}\right) - \frac{1}{3}\left(-\frac{K}{2cf_{VHF}}\frac{dSTECC}{dt}\right) + \Delta\nu_f \quad (5.40)$$

$$\Delta\delta f_{DC} = \frac{K}{2c}\frac{dSTECC}{dt}\left(\frac{1}{3f_{VHF}} - \frac{1}{8f_{UHF}}\right) + \Delta\nu_f$$

$$\Delta\delta f_{DC} = \frac{K}{2c}\frac{dSTECC}{dt}\left(\frac{55}{576f_o}\right) + \Delta\nu_f \quad (5.41)$$

When rearranged, it becomes;

$$\frac{dSTECC}{dt} = \frac{576f_o}{55}\frac{8\pi^2c\epsilon_0m_e}{e^2}(\Delta\delta f_{DC} - \Delta\nu_f) \quad (5.42)$$

$$\approx \frac{\Delta\delta f_{DC}}{2.569 \times 10^{-16}[m^2]}$$

The frequency noise ($\Delta\nu_f$) can be ignored since a large noise term causes a loss of signal lock and prevents a usable measurement (Garner et al., 2008). In practice, equation (5.42) can be integrated to produce a relative $STECC$ and then converted to VTEC by the mapping function $\xi(h_{pp},\alpha)$, Eq.(5.35).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.5. A sample plot of CIDR observation on day 246 of 2008. The top panel (a) shows the satellite track (solid thin line) and the pierce points of the F region (solid thick line) over the Egyptian region. The middle panel (b) shows the relative slant and vertical TEC (STEC, VTEC) in TECu, respectively, as a function Universal Time. The bottom panel (c) shows the relative VTEC and the change in TEC, respectively, in TECu as a function of geographic latitude of the F-region intercept.

Figure 5.5 is a sample of the standard CIDR data plot. The observation includes the satellite track and the relative STEC, VTEC and TEC rate of change. These measurements were taken from OSCAR 25 satellite at 2303 UT on 2 September 2008.

As with GPS-based TEC measurements, the UHF–VHF beacon TEC measurements contain an unknown bias. Either a baseline density distribution is needed or the unknown biases must be solved for and removed. Either way an optimal analysis algorithm will be needed. Hence, these measurements represent a relative TEC measurement.

6 Observations and Results

It has been well known that ionospheric responses to geomagnetic storms are rather complex even for these relatively simple storm studies, which is related to dynamics, as the meridonal wind push F layer to new heights, and to composition changes. During the day, the equatorward wind causes a positive ionospheric disturbance. At night the ion density is low, so ionospheric storm effects are more difficult to detect in the density change (Fuller-Rowell T J, 1994). It is generally regarded that the electron density in D, E and F regions is dominated by a balance among photo-ionization, chemical recombination and diffusion processes. Thus at night there is a reduction in photo-ionization, destroying the previous photochemical equilibrium and results in a depletion in electron density. On the whole, electron density is lower at nighttime than in the daytime and the maximum value of electron density takes place from noon to afternoon of local time. Thereby this variation also presented in the perturbations induced by the ionospheric storms and the ionospheric storms manifested different effects between daytime and nighttime. In time range when the electron density was high, ionospheric effects were dominant.

The studies of individual geomagnetic storms behavior are highly essential for a detailed knowledge of ionospheric storm behavior. During decades of ionospheric measurements, studies and modeling, knowledge about the morphology of the ionospheric response to geomagnetic storms has accumulated. At mid-latitudes, thermospheric winds and electromagnetic fields are believed to play a dominant role in the ionospheric plasma changes. As studies continue to search for the actual physical mechanisms that explain the spatial and temporal morphologies over various space weather events, it would be useful to have a well-defined pattern for a mid-latitude ionosphere storm.

Here, the results of case studies for four geomagnetic storms occurring in 2008, 2009 and 2010 in different seasons, were presented. Two of these storms

were monitored by CIDR receiver and the others by SCINDA-GPS receiver. These observations were supported by a geomagnetic one using MAGDAS-magnetometers. Table 6.1 presents the coordinates of the ionospheric and geomagnetic observatory stations used in this study.

Table 6.1. Ionospheric and geomagnetic observatories.

Observatory Name	Station	Geographic Coordinate
LEO-CIDR	Helwan	29.86° N, 31.32° E
GPS-SCINDA	Helwan	29.86° N, 31.32° E
MAGDAS	Fayoum	29.18° N, 30.50° E
	Aswan	23.59° N, 32.51° E

The Solar Wind (SW) speed, Auroral Electrojet (AE) index, the Z-component (B_z) of the Interplanetary Magnetic Field (IMF) in Geocentric Solar Magnetospheric (GSM) coordinates, 3-hourly Kp index of geomagnetic activity and the Disturbed storm time (Dst) index were plotted for each geomagnetic storm. In one case, AL and AU indices have been used. AE index, 3-hourly Kp index and Dst index data were obtained promptly from the World Data Centre for Geomagnetism, Kyoto University, Japan while the solar wind speed and the IMF data are from ACE (Advanced Composition Explorer) spacecraft.

6.1. Geomagnetic storms monitored by CIDR receiver

Since the installation of CIDR system at Helwan-Egypt in 2008, many geomagnetic storms have been monitored and their corresponding responses on the ionosphere were investigated. Two geomagnetic storm analyses [2-6 Sept.2008, and 12-14 March.2009,] are discussed here, giving the geomagnetic and ionospheric variations associated with these storms. The satellites used in this study were shown in table 6.2.

Table 6.2. LEO satellites used in CIDR observation.

Satellite ID	Satellite Name	Satellite Type
19419	OSCAR 25	Operational
19071	OSCAR 32	Operational
25157	GFO	Geodetic

6.1.1. Geomagnetic storm of 3 September 2008

At 21:00 UT (Sept.2nd 2008), a solar wind stream hit the Earth. The coronal hole on the sun responsible for this activity was a broad one, which means the solar wind could blow unabated for days. The variation of the solar wind (SW) speed, AE index, IMF-Bz, Kp-index and Dst-index are all presented in figure 6.1. The Dst plot indicates approximately a quiet day (2 Sept.) followed by a more disturbed period (3-6 Sept.). The maximum sum of Kp reached 30 on 4 September.

The Dst index begin to decrease from 19 nT on 3 September 23:00 UT (initial phase) reaching -51 nT on 4 September 05:00 UT (main phase) and then followed by the recovery phase which takes several days. During 4th of September, the maximum depression in Dst index meets a maximum in Kp index = 6 (00:00 to 06:00 UT), IMF-B_z = -9.9 nT (06:40 UT), AE index = 1586 nT (02:45 UT) and solar wind speed = 612.95 km/s (20:05 UT). The September 3, 2008 geomagnetic storm was a moderate one.

Figure 6.1. The most frequently used geomagnetic activity indices, from top to bottom; Solar Wind (SW) Speed in Km/sec , AE - index (values each min), the IMF Bz-component (at five minute intervals), Kp index (three-hourly), and the hourly Dst values, shown versus UT for a typical storm (2 – 6 September 2008).

The CIDR results during the storm period 2-6 Sept.2008 were presented in figure 6.2, in which each panel represent one satellite pass showing both the latitudinal variation Vertical Total Electron Content (VTEC) and its rate of change, or scintillation, under the satellite's path.

Each panel is labeled, from top, by "CIDR" followed by the *station number* "026", *year* "e.g.: 2008", *day of year* "e.g.: 246", *Universal Time* "HHMM", and then the *satellite ID* "e.g.: 19071". The local time of Helwan is UT+2 hrs. Here, the TEC data provides information related to the formation of the mid-latitude nighttime TEC peaks over Egypt.

It is known since the early days of ionospheric research that there are anomalous increases in the nighttime F2 region total electron content (TEC) at mid latitudes and since the first paper of Arendt and Soicher (Arendt, P.R. and H. Soicher., 1964), the same phenomenon has been reported and further established by many researchers (Evans, 1965; Davies et al., 1979; Janve et al., 1979; Essex and Klobuchar, 1980; Kersley et al., 1980; Joshi and Iyer, 1990; Bailey et al., 1991; Balan et al., 1991).

One must note that Equatorial Spread-F (ESF) refers to the density irregularities, with a wide spectrum of scale sizes, occurring in the nightside equatorial F region. Among various ESF phenomena, the one with largest scale sizes is localized plasma depletions, sometimes referred to as "*plasma bubbles*". Theoretical and observational investigations indicate that they are generated on the bottomside of the nightside equatorial F region and rise to higher altitudes as a result of nonlinear evolution of the generalized Rayleigh-Taylor and $E \times B$ instabilities.

The TEC data provides information related to the formation of the mid-latitude nighttime TEC peaks that the vertical $E \times B$ drift velocity reversal in equatorial latitudes and the downward plasma flows from greater heights, producing the mid-latitude nighttime peaks, are triggered from a common source: the *westward electric field*.

The equatorial electrojet is a relatively intense belt of current of the E-region travelling along the geomagnetic equator in a few degree wide latitude-band. The eastward or daytime and westward or nighttime currents are associated with the equatorial electrojet and equatorial counter-electrojet, respectively. The equatorial electrojet is closely associated with the equatorial anomaly through the vertical $E \times B$ drift velocity. During periods of solar minimum,

the electrojet current can create a relatively large daytime perturbation in the horizontal intensity (H-component) of the geomagnetic field (B) at ground level, in the close vicinity of the geomagnetic equator. Accordingly, changes in the Dst index reflect changes in the equatorial electrojet and the equatorial plasma fountain, as well. During the initial and main phases (3^{ed}, 4th September), the Dst index shows large variation, reaching maximum (26 nT) in Sept.3^{ed} at 0700 UT and minimum (-51 nT) in Sept.4th at 05:00 UT.

During these more disturbed days (3^{ed}, 4th Sept.) the nighttime TEC enhancement ,around 25° latitude, shows a large reduction from 3 TECU in the pre-storm day , Sept.2nd , (figure 6.2.a) to reach 1 TECU in Sept.3^{ed} (figure 6.2.b). The reduction increase during the following day (4-Sept.), see figure 6.2.c, d. During the recovery phase, 5 – 6 Sept., the NTE in the total electron content begins to recover itself, increasing gradually to reach more than 2 TECU (figure 6.2.e, f, and g). All of these variations in TEC were also associated with a change in TEC rate-of-change between 0.1 and 0.06 TECU. One should note that the TEC rate of change measures the fluctuations and variations in TEC and considered a good index for plasma bubble activity.

The strength of the equatorial electrojet current can be related directly to the degree of development of the nighttime peaks. The strong counter-electrojet current indicates the complete reversal of the electrojet. During these nights, the larger size of the mid-latitude nighttime peaks suggests that a stronger electric field with longer duration, which results in a more intensive downward plasma flow at mid latitudes. Le et al. (2003) proposed that the eastward polarized electric field within the plasma bubble is responsible for the density enhancement. We also can see that TEC enhancement can be observed pre-midnight and post-midnight. And the occurrence in post-midnight is larger than in pre-midnight. Figure 6.3 present the satellite tracks corresponding to observations in figure 6.2.

Another case about the night-time TEC disturbances on 12-14 March, 2009 geomagnetic storm is discussed later.

Ch.6.Results and Observations

(a: 2 Sept.)

(c: 4 Sept.)

(b: 3 Sept.)

(d: 4 Sept.)

(e: 5 Sept.)

(f: 5 Sept.)

(g: 6 Sept.)

Figure 6.2. Variation of TEC on 2-6 September, 2008 observed from OSCAR32 (ID: 19071) and GFO (ID: 25157) satellites at Helwan, EGYPT. In each panel, the top graph gives the relative Vertical Total Electron Content VTEC while the second one gives the rate of change of VTEC .

Figure 6.3. The satellite tracks (thin line) and the pierce points of the F region (thick line) corresponding to those in figure 6.2.

6.1.2. Geomagnetic storm of 12 March 2009

A solar wind stream hit the Earth late at 12 March 2009 night at $\sim 22:00$ UT. An increase in the southward IMF- B_z , AE and Kp indices with a depression in the Dst index are all associated with the solar wind hitting (see figure 6.4). The onset of this storm began when the B_z component of the IMF turned southward ($\sim 22:00$ UT), reaching a maximum value of -11 nT at $\sim 23:45$ UT, with an increasing in the solar wind speed.

Figure 6.4. The most frequently used geomagnetic activity indices, from top to bottom; Solar Wind (SW) Speed in Km/sec , AE - index (values each min), the IMF B_z -component (at five minute intervals), Kp index (three-hourly), and the hourly Dst values, shown versus UT for a typical storm (12 – 14 March 2009).

The March 12, 2009 geomagnetic storm was a minor one with a maximum Kp index = 5 at 13 March. In 13 March, the 1-hour Dst index began a gradually decline, reaching a minimum value of -31 nT at approximately 09:00 UT while the AE index reached 883 nT (02:25 UT). A geomagnetic variation was observed, during the storm period, at Fayoum's magnetometer station. The variation in geomagnetic H-component during the three days storm (12, 13 and 14 March) was plotted in figure 6.5. The variation shows more disturbances in days 13 and 14, concurring with that

discussed in figure 6.4. As said above, the electrojet current can create a relatively large daytime perturbation in the horizontal intensity (H-component) of the geomagnetic field (B) at ground level, in the close vicinity of the geomagnetic equator reflecting changes in the equatorial electrojet and the equatorial plasma fountain, as well.

Figure 6.5. The geomagnetic H-component (nT) plot shows its diurnal variation during the 12-14 March 2009 storm from a ground-based magnetometer at Fayoum.

The effect of this geomagnetic storm on vertical TEC and its rate of change, measured at Helwan station, are shown in figure 6.6 in which;

The first panel (a) present the observation during the pre-storm quite day 12 March at 00:58 UT. Small disturbances is present at the range of $28^{\circ} - 31^{\circ}$ latitude, graduate from a small bulge have 0.5 TECU at 28° latitude to minimum TECU at $\sim 29^{\circ}$ latitude and then begin to increase into 0.8 TECU at 31° . One should remember that these observations represent relative measurements, not absolute one.

The 2nd and 3^{ed} panels (b) and (c) present the observations during the day 13 March at 00:14 and 12:10 UT, respectively. Panel (b) shows that the reduction discussed in the previous panel (a) is increased to reach 1.1 TECU at 31° latitude. Panel (c) shows the northern limitation for the northern hump of the equatorial fountain.

The 4th panel (d) presents the observations during the day 14 March at 13:14 UT in which the northern limitation for the northern hump of the equatorial fountain shows a movement to higher latitudes.

One may think that these disturbances appeared at night and the movement of the EA northern hump were caused by an energy input to the thermosphere/ionosphere system and daytime growth eastward electric field, respectively.

Figure 6.6. Variations of VTEC and its rate of change collected at Helwan, CIDR receiver during the five days storm period March 12-14, 2009.

Figure 6.7. The satellite tracks (thin line) and the pierce points of the F region (thick line) corresponding to those in figure 6.6.

6.2. Geomagnetic storms monitored by GPS receiver

Here two geomagnetic storms were presented, one in April 2010 and the other in May 2010, showing the positive and negative phases of the ionosphere during these disturbed periods. The geomagnetic storm of May 2010 was followed by a substorm which has a notable effect on the ionospheric and geomagnetic observations.

6.2.1. Geomagnetic storm of 5 April 2010

The severe ($K_p = 8$) geomagnetic storm of April 5th was analyzed using a stand-alone GPS receiver, showing its effects on the Earth’s ionosphere. At 08:00 UT (April 5th, 2010), the vertical dashed line, a sharp gust of Solar Wind hits the Earth’s magnetosphere (Figure 6.8).

Figure 6.8. The most frequently used geomagnetic activity indices, from top to bottom; Solar Wind (SW) Speed in Km/sec , the IMF Bz-component (at five minute intervals), AE - index (values each min), Kp index (three-hourly), and the hourly Dst values, shown versus UT for a typical storm (5 – 8 April 2010).

At 08:00 UT (April 5th, 2010), the vertical dashed line, a sharp gust of Solar Wind hits the Earth's magnetosphere causing a pressure pulse which reforms the magnetosphere such that the magnetopause moves Earthward, creating an equatorial ring current which appear in the Dst-index depletion. The Dst-index reaches its maximum depression (-73 nT) at 15:00 UT in April 6th. It measures the intensity of the globally symmetrical equatorial electrojet (the ring current).

The solar wind speed begins to increase in addition with increasing the measured southward B_z -component of the IMF, which reaches its maximum value at 09:40 UT coincidence with the AE index measurements which has its maximum value at 09:35 UT. The maximum K_p is 8 in the 09:00-12:00 UT interval. All of these features represent an energy transfer into the magnetosphere which can then either be deposited "directly" into the ionosphere or be stored in the magnetosphere.

In addition, the variation in geomagnetic H-component shows a disturbance begin in days April 5th,6th and coincidence with that of the Dst index. The electrojet (ring) current can create a relatively large daytime perturbation in the horizontal intensity (H-component) of the geomagnetic field at ground level, in the close vicinity of the geomagnetic equator reflecting changes in the equatorial plasma fountain.

The magnetic latitude of Helwan station (26.91°N), located near the northern hump of the equatorial anomaly, is characterized by a very high electron density. The hump phenomenon can be explained by the $E \times B$ electrodynamic drift and the diffusion of plasma along the geomagnetic field lines. Obviously for perturbations, ionospheric TEC varied more in such region than that has low electron density (Chen An-hua, 1999). The ionospheric data obtained at Helwan gives a good representation of the northern hump of the equatorial anomaly. The preliminary results of TEC measurements at Helwan confirm a high degree of ionosphere variability at this region.

Figure 6.9 shows the VTEC taken at the days April 3^{ed}, 4th immediately before the storm. These days were taken as a reference days, to observe the TEC deviations from its normal recognized values, in which the dominant contribution to the typical diurnal variation in TEC is due to ionization from solar radiation, and to distinguish the TEC variability from its normal values.

As mentioned before, The TEC measured along each GPS satellite link is colored according to the magnetic latitude of the ionospheric penetration point (IPP). Plotting in this format facilitates the study of large scale TEC gradients as a function of both time and magnetic latitude as measured by a standalone GPS receiver.

The TEC values, for these reference days, at mid-latitudes (green curves) is ranging in early twenties, while at low-latitude (blue curves) it is ranging in thirty's (see Figure 6.9).

TEC variation over Helwan during 5-10 April 2010 geomagnetic storm were shown in figure 6.10, in which the southern delimitation of TEC measurement region located near the northern hump of equatorial anomaly ($\approx 13.4^\circ$ MLat), implying the fountain effect was dominant in such area. Positive and negative ionospheric storms were detected during the geomagnetic storm period.

The ionosphere reacts to the geomagnetic activity in a complex way and its behavior varies with latitude, longitude, season and time of day (Dieminger et al., 1996).

Figure 6.9: Diurnal variation in TEC measured at Helwan, SCINDA-station during pre-storm April 3^{ed}, 4th 2010.

The mid latitude F2-region response to geomagnetic storm in three phases: **(1)** an initial or positive phase in which the peak electron density increases with respect to pre-storm conditions (Figure 6.10.a) and lasts for a few hours on the first day of a storm “*positive ionospheric storm*”.

The TEC values at low latitudes (blue curves) reach 40 TECU while at mid-latitudes (green curves) exceeds 30 TECU.

(2) a negative phase in which the peak electron density decreases relative to pre-storm conditions, “*negative ionospheric storm*”, which can last several days (Figure 6.10.b). The TEC at low latitude (blue curves) is reduced to twenties while at mid latitude (green curves) it is reduced to be less than 20 TECU.

(3) Finally, the ionosphere gradually returns to its normal conditions over a period of one to several days in the recovery phase (Figure 6.10.c, d,e and f).

The positive phase of the ionospheric storm for the TEC is detected on April 5th (Fig.6.10.a) which is generally believed to be caused by uplifting the F-region by equatorward winds in the early hours of a storm development. The TEC at mid latitude (green curves) were enhanced to be ranging in thirties, relative to the TEC values from twenties at a quiet pre-storm day April 4th (Fig.6.9).

This positive phase was followed by a negative one seen at April 6th (Fig.6.10.b), reducing the TEC value below its pre-storm one. Negative storm phases have been attributed to changes in the atomic to molecular neutral density ratio.

During the recovery phase, the TEC values tries to return to its pre-storm values (Fig.6.10.c, d). One should note that, at the recovery day April 8th, Fig.6.10.d, the TEC values at low latitudes has an enhancement (blue curves). This may be attributed to an energy input to the thermosphere /ionosphere system. The AE-index in Fig.6.8 shows an enhancement also at the recovery days, which agree with the idea of energy input.

Figure 6.11 shows an average two-dimension plot (contour plot) and a three-dimension plot (surface plot) for the total electron content (TEC) during the storm period, in which the TEC enhancement appears clearly in day April 4th (positive phase) followed by a TEC depletion in day April 5th (negative phase).

Figure 6.10: Variations of VTEC at Helwan, SCINDA-GPS receiver during the six days storm period (April 5th -10th, 2010).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.11: (a) TEC contour plot (2D), and (b) TEC surface plot (3D) for the eight days (3 – 10 April, 2010) storm period.

6.2.2. Geomagnetic storm of 2 May 2010

Here; GPS data were analyzed to establish the daily behaviors of TEC in the region of northern crest of the equatorial anomaly during the moderate geomagnetic storm 1-5 May 2010, illustrating F region spatial and temporal variations.

At 09:00 UT on 2 May a Sudden Storm Commencement (SSC) impulse was registered, indicating the beginning of a geomagnetic storm. The Dst value dropped to a minimum (- 68 nT) at 18:00 UT on May 2 and took more than 48 h to recover to the quiet time levels (Fig. 6.12). During this storm, planetary geomagnetic activity indices reached high values: $\sum K_p = 29$ on 2 May and $\sum K_p = 30$ on 3 May with several 3-h intervals of $\sum K_p = 19, 14$ in 4, 5 May, respectively (Fig. 6.12).

Figure 6.12. The most frequently used geomagnetic activity indices Solar Wind (SW) Speed in Km/sec , AE - index (values each min), AU-AL indices (values each min), the IMF Bz-component (at five minute intervals), Kp index (three-hourly), and the hourly Dst values, shown versus UT for a typical storm (2 May 2010).

During May 2nd, the Dst-index dropped to a minimum (- 68 nT) at 18:00 UT and took more than 48 h to recover to the quiet time levels, Kp-index recorded a maximum value (Kp = 6) at the three time interval 12:00-15:00 UT, IMF-Bz has a maximum depression (- 17.6233 nT) at 12:50 UT, and both the solar wind speed reaches 658.46 km/s at 16:50 UT, and the AE-index recorded 1146 nT at 19:37 UT in that day.

The geomagnetic storm lasted until 5 May 2010. The AU and AL indices were used in this case in order to use it in studying a substorm followed the geomagnetic one.

The turning of B_z to southward at 2 May 14:55 UT indicates the penetration of high latitude eastward electric fields to low latitudes at this time. These fields enhances the equatorial $E \times B$ vertical drifts and hence the fountain mechanism after a period of about an hour. The large duration of this positive effect suggests downwelling of the thermospheric gas due to storm-induced circulation which leads to an increase of the atomic oxygen [O] contributing to the positive storm effect (Blanc and Richmond, 1980).

The geomagnetic activity during this storm is illustrated also by the variations of the H-component of the geomagnetic field taken from MAGDAS station at Aswan, Egypt. For the storm period, 1-5 May 2010, the H-component of the geomagnetic field was plotted against the universal time to show its daily variation (see Fig.6.13). During quiet geomagnetic conditions (day 1, 5), the H-component exhibits a regular diurnal pattern with peak amplitudes occurring around local midday or 12 UT.

Figure 6.13. The geomagnetic H-component (nT) plot shows its diurnal variation during the 1-5 May 2010 storm from a ground-based magnetometer at Aswan.

The regular daily development of the peak amplitude is due to the more enhanced daytime eastward electrojet current induced by the higher day-time electron concentration. At nighttime, the H-component is a minimum because of the weak westward current created by a much lower electron concentration. During the more disturbed period of 2-4 May, the regular pattern becomes largely modified.

In general, the eastward or daytime and westward or nighttime currents are associated with the equatorial electrojet and equatorial counter-electrojet, respectively. The equatorial electrojet is closely associated with the equatorial anomaly through the vertical $E \times B$ drift velocity. During periods of solar minimum, the electrojet current can create a relatively large daytime perturbation in the horizontal intensity (H) of the geomagnetic field (B) at ground level, in the close vicinity of the geomagnetic equator. Accordingly, changes in the H-component reflect changes in the equatorial electrojet and equatorial plasma fountain, as well. During this storm, the SSC impulse was registered at 09:00 UT, indicating the beginning of the storm. Within 6 hr from the registration of the SSC, changes of the intensity of the horizontal field component (H) reached values exceeding -50 nT.

In order to show the ionospheric TEC perturbations induced by the magnetic storms, the deviation of TEC during the storm days from a pre-storm reference day, taken as 1 May, is observed (Figure 6.14). During that day, the dominant contribution to the diurnal variation in TEC is due to ionization from solar radiation. The TEC variations over Helwan during storm period (2 – 5 May) were shown in figure. 6.15 in which, there was an obvious features induced by ionospheric storms, which were more dominant in local daytime (LT=UT+2) than at night. Notable positive and negative storm effects often appeared in the dayside.

F-region storm morphology: It can easily be seen that the total ionospheric electron content was highly disturbed both in time and in space over the Egyptian area during the storm time (see Fig 6.15). A positive phase of the ionospheric storm for the TEC is detected in both 2 and 4 May, separated by a negative phase in 3 May. A prominent large-scale ionospheric disturbance is evident with an ionization enhancement at low mid-latitudes (Fig. 6.15, a, c) during the main and recovery phases, and an ionization depletion (Fig. 6.15, b) before the main phase of the geomagnetic storm is fully developed.

Figure 6.14: Diurnal variation in TEC measured from Helwan, station in May 1th 2010.

The positive storm effects observed during the daytime (Fig.6.15,a) are mainly due to increases in $E \times B$ vertical plasma drifts causing equatorial anomaly enhancements. Thermospheric wind and electromagnetic fields are thought to be the two main drivers of ionospheric storms (Ho C M,1998). At mid-latitude, thermospheric wind are believed to play a dominant role in ionospheric density changes. However at lower latitude, electric field effect cannot be neglected (Fuller-Rowell T J.1994). Simultaneously ionospheric variations over large scale can result from penetration to low altitude of magnetospheric electric fields or electric fields associated with ring current shielding in the storm time outer plasmasphere (Fejer B G, 1983).

1st panel (a) explain the TEC, deviated from its normal values, during the main phase of the storm in which the ionospheric storm manifested a lasting positive effects and the maximum positive deviation reached more than 10 TECU at mid-latitudes (blue and green lines). The long-playing positive effects during the main phase of the storm may be caused by promotion of plasma to a high altitude, resulting from the strong electric fields generated by postdusk effect, leading to a low recombination (Fuller-Rowell T J.1994).

Figure 6.15: Diurnal variation in TEC observed with a GPS receiver operating at mid-latitude. The measurements were collected at Helwan, Egypt (magnetic latitude 27.07 °N) during the five days storm period May 2-5, 2010.

In the 2nd panel of Fig.6.15 (b), during the recovery period, there was a negative storm effect. During the recovery phase, the negative phase of the storm is mainly due to ionospheric composition change (Ho C M, 1998) and perturbations of the neutral gas composition (Fuller-Rowell T J.1994). Another study shows that thermospheric composition changes also play an important role in plasma density changes (Fuller-Rowell T J, 1994). The neutral gas composition changes bring more N_2 to higher altitude after intensive ionospheric heating for many hours. The N_2/O ratio increases leading to an increase of chemical loss by ionization and thus a negative phase at middle and low latitude (Fuller-Rowell T J, 1996). We can see a clear depletion process which expands from middle latitudes (green curves) to lower ones (blue curves) and from daytime to nighttime. A large-scale circulation in the thermosphere driven by high latitude heating has been considered also as a source of the molecular enriched atmosphere (Fuller-Rowell T J.1996).

Figure (6.15, c) shows a strange positive effect in the ionospheric TEC. This enhancement is believed to be caused due to a substorm followed the geomagnetic one.

Figure 6.16. Geomagnetic H-component variation and pi2 magnetic oscillations at Aswan station on 3,4 May 2010.

At the onset of auroral substorm, impulsive hydromagnetic oscillations with periods of 40-150 *sec*, so called Pi2 magnetic oscillations, are excited globally in the magnetosphere (Saito, 1969; Olson, 1999; Yumoto et al., 2001). The source of Pi2 pulsation is believed to be a sudden change in magnetospheric configuration or convection during substorm expansion phase (McPherron et al., 1973). The reason is that these processes – geomagnetic storms and substorms - create distributions of charged particle pressure, energy, and pitch angle that are unstable to the creation of various types of waves (McPherron, R. L., 2005). During the substorm, an earthward directed flow occurs in the plasma sheet by bursts of magnetic reconnection in the magnetotail. The flows transport plasma and magnetic field earthward. As they approach the Earth (8-15 R_E), the pressure gradients in the midnight region slow the flow and divert it around the Earth. When the Earthward flow bursts impact the inner magnetosphere they radiate compressional waves that travel across the field lines and eventually couple to field line resonances.

Such pulsations were detected at Aswan station during the recovery days of the storm. Figure 6.16 displays the Pi2 magnetic pulsation and the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field during the recovery phase days (3, 4 May). Pi2 has maximum amplitude (≈ 0.54) about 18:48 UT in May 3rd and ≈ 0.5 about 20:30 UT. Note that, at lower latitudes, Pi2 may appear in a wider range of local time including the day sector, i.e. lower the latitude, wider the extent of occurrence in local times. Thus, the low-latitude Pi2 pulsations are one of the most widely used onset tools for substorm (Ching, 2004).

Since the magnetic field fluctuations were indicated that electrons are moving around leading to a TEC change, then any change to the TEC of a particular area should be corresponds to a change in the observed magnetic field. This change may be caused by a sudden generation of the substorm current wedge (McPherron et al., 1973) with field-aligned currents (FACs) between the polar ionosphere and magnetospheric plasmashet in association with the disruption of cross-tail currents (Yumoto, 1986, 1988) and earthward plasma flows (Kepko and Kivelson, 1999) from reconnection region. This increase in the electric fields of magnetospheric origin may be cause F2 layer uplifting due to vertical drift which is the dominant

mechanism at lower latitudes (Jakowski, 1999) and be a probable source of the ionospheric storm positive effect.

The last panel in figure 6.15,(d) shows the TEC during 5 May which returns to its quite values before the storm time, but an enhancement is observed at 20:00 LT at mid-latitudes (green curves). This enhancement may be caused by several different mechanisms such as; vertical plasma motion across the magnetic fields lines due to ionospheric and magnetospheric electric fields (e.g, Balan et al., 1991); plasma diffusion from the plasmasphere (e.g., Horvath and Essex, 2003a), and may be correlated with Pi2 magnetic oscillation appeared during the same period (see figure 6.16).

One should see the AE and AU-AL indexes (figure.6.12) which has an obvious enhancements during the recovery phase days (3, 4 May), and agrees with the above conclusions about these two recovery days.

Figures 6.17 shows a contour (2D) and surface (3D) plots for the TEC values during the five day storm period in which the ionospheric positive phase appeared clearly in 2 May (main phase) and the ionospheric negative phase in 3 May (beginning of recovery phase). In 4 May, the TEC value increases in a shyness way and return to its normal values in 5 May with an enhancement in the nighttime.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.17: (a) TEC contour plot (2D), and (b) TEC surface plot (3D) for the five days (1 – 5 May, 2010) storm period, showing the effects of the onset, main and recovery phases of the storm on the ionosphere.

6.3. TEC Annual survey (2010)

Davies (1992), using data from GPS and GEOS-2 satellites, reported that the summer TEC diurnal pattern differs significantly from that of winter. He reported also that in the Northern Hemisphere the largest diurnal maximum occurred in equinox and the minimum in summer.

Changes in atmospheric circulation at the equinoxes giving rise to changes in the pattern of vertical drifts may be responsible for the increase in the TEC at the equinoxes (e.g.; Garriott at al., 1970; Essex, 1978; Davies, 1990). Also, the height of transition from O^+ to H^+ ions may be higher during the equinoxes than during summer and winter, leading to an increase in the daytime atom to molecule ratio and thus a daytime TEC increase at equinox rather than at solstices.

During large magnetic disturbance periods, however, this regular predictable variability can be dramatically altered as different forces, which drive ionization from one place to another, are imposed into the ionosphere. This is in a good agreement with the earlier observations that have been made. Table 6.3 gives the average TEC values for each month which shows a maximum at equinoxes and minimum at solstices.

Table 6.3. Average TEC values for each month in year 2010.

Winter		Equinox		Summer		Equinox	
Jan.	15 TECU	Mar.	30 TECU	June.	22 TECU	Sept.	35 TECU
Feb.	20 TECU	April.	27 TECU	July.	20 TECU	Oct.	30 TECU
		May	30 TECU	Aug.	24 TECU	Nov.	22 TECU
Dec.	16 TECU						

Figure 6.18 shows the annual variation of TEC at different seasons of the year 2010, obtained by the GPS ground station. The figure consists of 12 panels at the rate of one panel for month. The white spaces are missing data. Note that the TEC-scale, at the right of each panel, is not fixed for all months. It is adjusted upon the largest and smallest values of TEC during that month.

Figure 6.18. Total Electron Content (TEC) survey, by a GPS receiver, during the year 2010 at Helwan .

Ch.6.Results and Observations

6.4. Summary and Future directions

The previous sections describe the results obtained from both CIDR and GPS observations. Observations by the MAGDAS magnetometer have been also presented. As described in chapter one, the objective of this M.Sc. research has been to investigate the ionosphere during a geomagnetic storms.

From the above observation and measurements, we could conclude that:

1- The SCINDA-GPS receiver gives more accurate measurements than that from LEO-CIDR in that it gives absolute values for the Total Electron Content (TEC) instead of relative ones in LEO-CIDR.

2- Due to the low altitude of the CIDR's satellites (~ 1000 Km), all the TEC measurements gives a spatial observations whereas those for SCINDA receiver, it gives a TEC temporal observation extracted from a high altitude GPS satellites (~ 20,000 Km).

3 - Most of the geomagnetic storms investigated within this thesis are associated with a positive phase of ionospheric storm followed by a negative one.

4- These conclusions here are specific to the enhancing phase of the current solar activity, and mid-latitude conditions.

5- All the important features of the ionosphere such as equatorial anomaly, ionization troughs, TEC nighttime enhancement, equatorial spread-F, and the ionospheric storms have been clearly observed but, the satellite-based ground receivers are not dense enough to investigate these ionospheric features on a large scale.

6- This study was limited by a single space-based ionospheric monitoring ground station. However, the results presented in this research work are the first using data from GPS in the region.

Based on these conclusions, a software modification was done which will be described in subsequent publications.

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Appendixes

Appendix A

Sample process.cfg file:

```
DTEC_max:  0.1      #Maximum Delta TEC between
              measurementsin TECU

S_min:      0.02    #Minimum correlation count to be
              considered good data

T_min:      120.    #Minimum length of time for good
              data

P_good:     0.60    #Percent of good data required

G_max:      30      #Maximum seconds continguous gap
              (neg toignore)

F_min:      0.75    #Minimum fraction of data > 1 Hz
              sample rate that must be good

ht_int:     350.    #Ionospheric intercept ht (km)

nav_file    navsat.txt #Name of satellite two-line
              emphersis file

avg_rate:   -1      #Rate (in Hz) to which data will be
              averaged, 1=none(must be <=
              sampling rate)

atts_file:  ncdf_atts.txt #Global attributes file name

use_ascii:  0        # 0 => output as netcdf, 1 =>
              output as ascii
```

Appendix B

recvrlist.txt file:

NOTE: The format of this file has yet to be determined. A possible format is presented below. Until this file exists, CIDR2Ncdf will assign “ARLUT” as the location name for the receiver. The code for CIDR_process::WriteNetCDFFile and CIDR_process::GetLocationName in cidr.cpp should be changed once the format for this file has been decided upon.

```
CIDR 001 0.0 0.0 0.0 Caribbean1
CIDR 002 0.0 0.0 0.0 Caribbean2
CIDR 003 0.0 0.0 0.0 Caribbean3
CIDR 004 0.0 0.0 0.0 Caribbean4
CIDR 005 0.0 0.0 0.0 Fort_Yukon, Alaska
CIDR 006 0.0 0.0 0.0 Kaktovik, Alaska
CIDR 007 0.0 0.0 0.0 Qegetarsuaq, Greenland
CIDR 008 0.0 0.0 0.0 Sondrestrom, Greenland
CIDR 009 0.0 0.0 0.0 Nuuk, Greenland
CIDR 010 0.0 0.0 0.0 Narsarsuaq, Greenland
CIDR 011 0.0 0.0 0.0 Sevilleta, New Mexico
CIDR 012 0.0 0.0 0.0 MillstoneHill1, Massachusetts
CIDR 013 0.0 0.0 0.0 MillstoneHill2, Massachusetts
CIDR 014 0.0 0.0 0.0 MillstoneHill3, Massachusetts
CIDR 015 0.0 0.0 0.0 Ancon, Peru
CIDR 016 0.0 0.0 0.0 Bogota, Columbia
CIDR 017 0.0 0.0 0.0 Whiteface Mountain, New York
CIDR 018 0.0 0.0 0.0 Siena Albany, New York
CIDR 019 0.0 0.0 0.0 Suny-Oneonta, New York
CIDR 020 0.0 0.0 0.0 Cornell, New York
CIDR 021 0.0 0.0 0.0 Wallops Island, Virginia
CIDR 022 0.0 0.0 0.0 Uchinoura, Kyushu
CIDR 023 0.0 0.0 0.0 Sendai, Kyushu
CIDR 024 0.0 0.0 0.0 Taramizu, Kyushu
CIDR 025 0.0 0.0 0.0 Fukue, Kyushu
CIDR 026 0.0 0.0 0.0 Helwan, Egypt
CIDR 027 0.0 0.0 0.0 Alexandria, Egypt
CIDR 028 0.0 0.0 0.0 Aswan, Egypt
CIDR 063 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 105 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 106 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 107 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 108 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 109 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 110 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 111 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 112 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 113 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 900 0.0 0.0 0.0 ARLUT, Texas
CIDR 999 0.0 0.0 0.0 AFRL, Massachusetts
```

Appendix C

Sample navsat.txt file:

```
1967-048A
1 02807U 67048A 01332.97201794 .00000073 00000-0 10000-3 0 614
2 02807 89.5724 317.5229 0018289 278.2540 81.6598 13.49268303698738
1967-092A
1 02965U 67092A 01332.95812043 .00000078 00000-0 10000-3 0 4496
2 02965 89.2440 328.8984 0050172 140.0889 220.4051 13.51959629684482
1968-012A
1 03133U 68012A 01332.44844279 .00000048 00000-0 59766-4 0 9975
2 03133 90.0058 286.3561 0076103 20.3078 340.1144 13.50004599660388
NNSS 19
1 04507U 70067A 01332.96870737 .00000330 00000-0 45932-3 0 2009
2 04507 89.9722 333.1931 0174484 134.4801 227.0774 13.49590485537683
NNSS O-20
1 06909U 73081A 01332.71097237 .00000460 00000-0 47420-3 0 5859
2 06909 89.7123 337.7162 0023724 291.0687 68.7932 13.47951020184548
TRANSAT
1 10457U 77106A 01333.52550138 .00000071 00000-0 10000-3 0 7100
2 10457 89.7123 337.7162 0023724 291.0687 68.7932 13.47951020184548
NOVA I
1 12458U 81044A 01332.31969113 .00000050 00000-0 10000-3 0 4959
2 12458 90.1677 75.8091 0014988 175.7120 184.4193 13.22444665991292
NOVA 3
1 15362U 84110A 01332.81541122 .00000051 00000-0 10000-3 0 8915
2 15362 89.8843 69.5192 0033380 37.8812 322.4702 13.22227712826686
OSCAR 30
1 15935U 85066A 01332.70801829 .00000082 00000-0 13538-3 0 2314
2 15935 89.9929 19.3799 0169899 355.2161 4.7348 13.34892614792751
OSCAR 24
1 15936U 85066B 01332.69677239 .00000248 00000-0 43896-3 0 3022
2 15936 89.9825 18.2122 0171314 356.7979 3.2052 13.34807989794909
POLAR BEAR
1 17070U 86088A 01332.94445664 .00000282 00000-0 28801-3 0 1240
2 17070 89.5991 224.5770 0038272 292.8743 66.8382 13.73917822753968
OSCAR 27
1 18361U 87080A 01333.54472873 .00000049 00000-0 66429-4 0 7376
2 18361 90.2715 158.0576 0108542 142.5092 218.3700 13.43688259696360
...
```

Appendix D

Sample ncdf_atts.txt file:

```
# the institution that created this output file
Institution
University of Texas Applied Research Labs

# a contact email for the output
Contact
person@domain.edu
```

Appendix E

(1) *read_ncdf.pro*

```
.....  
; read_ncdf.pro - This file contains IDL functions to read netCDF data files  
;   into IDL variables.  
; This file contains the following functions and procedures:  
; functions:  
;   getFile - strips the directory and optionally) any suffixes from  
;   the path+file  
;   getDir - returns the directory from the full path+file  
;   validateName - validates the name that will be used as a netCDF  
;   variable  
; procedures:  
;   read_ncdf - reads netCDF variables into IDL  
; History:  
; Date   Name   Action  
; -----  
; 06 Jun 97 S. Rupert   Created.  
; 09 Jun 97 S. Rupert   Fully tested.  
; 10 Jun 97 S. Rupert   Modified keyword usage.  
; 03 Feb 98 S. Rupert   Added additional error checking, and warning to  
;   output script.  
; 17 Feb 98 S. Rupert   Corrected validation routine to handle instance  
;   of name strating with a number and containing a  
;   dash.  
; 17 Mar 02 D. Morrison  Changed routine to return data into a  
; structure  
.....
```

```
function getFile, fullpath, suffix=suffix  
; func_description  
; This function returns the filename name from the full path.  
; Inputs: fullpath - full directory+file path  
; Keyword: /suffix: include inptu suffix in output file name  
; Outputs: file - filename  
; Example Call: file = getFile(fullpath)
```

```

; Retrieve the position at which the first '/' character occurs from
; the end of the string.
dirlen = rstrpos(fullpath, '/')
; Retrieve the full length of the original string.
len = strlen(fullpath)
; Retrieve the filename.
fullfile = strmid(fullpath, dirlen+1, len)
; Retrieve the position at which the first '.' character occurs from
; the end of the string.
len = -1
if not(keyword_set(suffix)) then len = rstrpos(fullfile, '.')
if (len EQ -1) then len = strlen(fullfile)
; Retrieve the file.
file = strmid(fullfile, 0, len)
; Return the file name.
return, file
; End function.
end

```

```

function getDir, fullpath
; func_description
; This function returns the directory name from the full path.
; Inputs: fullpath - full directory+file path
; Outputs: dir - directory path
; Example Call: dir = getDir(fullpath)
; Retrieve the position at which the first '/' character occurs from
; the end of the string.
len = rstrpos(fullpath, '/')
; Retrieve the filename.
if (len EQ -1) then dir = "./" $
else dir = strmid(fullpath, 0, len+1)
; Return the file name.
return, dir
; End function.
end

```

```

function validateName, varname
; func_description
; This routine ensures that the given name does not start with a number,
; nor contain a dash. IDL cannot accept a variable starting with a
; number or containing a dash. If the name starts with a number, an

```

```
; underscore is prepended to the name, and if it contains a dash, the
; dash is replaced with an underscore.
; Initialize the name.
name = varname
```

```
; If the name starts with a number, prepend it with an underscore.
if (strpos(varname, '0') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '1') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '2') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '3') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '4') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '5') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '6') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '7') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '8') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
if (strpos(varname, '9') EQ 0) then name = strcompress("_"+varname)
```

```
; If the name contains a dash replace it with an underscore.
if (strpos(name, '-') NE -1) then begin
  pieces = str_sep(name, '-')
  n_pieces = n_elements(pieces)
  name = pieces(0)
  for i=1,n_pieces-1 do begin
    name = strcompress(name+"_"+pieces(i))
  endfor
endif
; Return the file name.
return, name
; End function.
end
```

```
pro read_ncdf, infile, data, attrib=attrib
; pro_description, infile
; This procedure reads the data in a given netCDFfile into an IDL data
structure
; Inputs:      infile - full path to netCDF file of interest
;              attrib - includes extractions of all input file
;              attributes in idl script
; Outputs:     data - structure into which data is returned
; Example: read_ncdf, '/vol1/cids/netCDF.file', data, /attrib
; Establish that the correct data have been input.
```

```

if n_params() LT 1 then begin
  print, "Usage: read_ncdf, 'inputfile', data, "+$
    "/attrib"+string(10B)+$
    string(9B)+"inputfile - full path to netCDF file of
interest"+string(10B)+$
    string(9B)+"data - desired name of resultant idl data
structure"+string(10B)+$
    string(9B)+"/attrib: keyword indicating inclusion of netCDF
attributes"
  return
endif

; Ensure that the netCDF format is supported on the current platform.
if not(ncdf_exists()) then begin
  print, "The Network Common Data Format is not supported on this
platform."
  return
endif

; Open the netcdf file for reading.
ncid = NCDF_OPEN(infile)
if (ncid EQ -1) then begin
  print, "The file "+infile+" could not be opened, please check the path."
  return
endif

; Retrieve general information about this netCDF file.
ncidinfo = NCDF_INQUIRE(ncid)

; Write the file header.
dir = getDir(infile)
if (dir EQ './') then dir = 'the current directory'
file = getFile(infile,/suffix)

; Place the desired variables in local arrays.
for i=0, ncidinfo.Nvars-1 do begin
  vardata = NCDF_VARINQ(ncid, i)
  valid_varname = validateName(vardata.Name)
  varname=valid_varname
  NCDF_VARGET, ncid, i, varname ; Read in variable vardata.Name
  if i eq 0 then begin

```

```

        data = create_struct(valid_varname,varname)
    endif else begin
        data = create_struct(data, valid_varname,varname)
    endelse
if (keyword_set(attrib)) then begin
    for j=0, vardata.Natts-1 do begin
        att = NCDF_ATTNAME(ncid, i, j)
        attname =
strcompress(valid_varname+"_"+strcompress(att,/REMOVE_ALL))
        valid_attname = attname
        NCDF_ATTGET, ncid, i,att,attname
        junk = NCDF_ATTINQ(ncid,i,att)
        CASE junk.DataType OF
            'FLOAT': attname=STRING(attname,FORMAT='(G0.12)')
            'DOUBLE': attname=STRING(attname,FORMAT='(G0.12)')
            ELSE: attname = STRING(attname)
        ENDCASE
        data = create_struct(data, valid_attname,attname)
    endfor
endif
endifor

if (keyword_set(attrib)) then begin
; Read in the Global Attributes."
for i=0, ncidinfo.Ngatts-1 do begin
    name = NCDF_ATTNAME(ncid, /GLOBAL, i)
    attname = validateName(name)
    valid_attname = attname
    NCDF_ATTGET, ncid, /GLOBAL, name, attname
    junk = NCDF_ATTINQ(ncid,/GLOBAL,name)
    CASE junk.DataType OF
        'FLOAT': attname=STRING(attname,FORMAT='(G0.12)')
        'DOUBLE': attname=STRING(attname,FORMAT='(G0.12)')
        ELSE: attname = STRING(attname)
    ENDCASE
    data = create_struct(data, valid_attname, attname)
endfor
endif

NCDF_CLOSE, ncid ; Close the NetCDF file"

```

```
; Return to the caller.  
return  
; End procedure.  
end
```

(2) *read_cidr_dop.pro*

```
PRO read_cidr_dop, infile, time, fd150, fp150,fd400, fp400,sn150, sn400,
$
pe150, pe400,header
;
;
bigsize = 1500000L
MAXHEAD = 20
bigarr = ftarr(9,bigsize)
oneline = ftarr(9)
junk = ''
num = 0L
header = strarr(MAXHEAD)
openr,1,infile
ISHEADER = 1
nheader = 0
while (NOT EOF(1) AND ISHEADER) do begin
    readf,1,junk
    ctest = strmid(junk,0,1)
    if (ctest ne '#') then ISHEADER = 0
        header[nheader] = junk
        nheader = nheader + 1
endwhile
header = header[0:nheader-2]
line_a = strsplit(junk,/extract)
bigarr[* ,0] = float(line_a)
num = 1L
while (NOT EOF(1)) do begin
    readf,1,oneline
    bigarr[* ,num] = oneline
    num = num + 1L
endwhile
close,1
if num lt 1 then num = 1
time = bigarr[0,0:num-1]
fp150 = bigarr[1,0:num-1]
fd150 = bigarr[2,0:num-1]
sn150 = bigarr[3,0:num-1]
pe150 = bigarr[4,0:num-1]
```

```
fp400 = bigarr[5,0:num-1]
fd400 = bigarr[6,0:num-1]
sn400 = bigarr[7,0:num-1]
pe400 = bigarr[8,0:num-1]
return
end
```

(3) *Plot_doppler_data.pro*

pro go

```
f=findfile('CIDR_*.dop')
cvt=2.*128./25000.
```

```
!p.multi=[0,1,2]
xt='Universal Time (Hrs)'
for j=0,n_elements(f)-1 do begin
t150='VHF Channel '+strmid(f(j),0,28)
t400='UHF Channel '+strmid(f(j),0,28)
```

```
read_cidr_dop, f(j),ut1,fd150,fp150,fd400,fp400,sn150,sn400,pe150,
pe400,header
ut=ut1/3600.
```

```
eletit='Maximum Elevation '+strmid(header(1),12,3)
qa150=sqrt((sn150*cvt-1.)^2.+(cvt*pe150-1.)^2.)
qa400=sqrt((sn400*cvt-1.)^2.+(cvt*pe400-1.)^2.)
;plot,ut,sn150,ystyle=16,title=f(j),ytitle='150 CC'
;plot,ut,pe150,ystyle=16,title=f(j),ytitle='150 PE'
plot,ut,qa150,title=t150,ytitle='Correlation Count at 150
MHz',psym=1,symsize=0.5,xtitle=xt,yrange=[-0.25,1.]
oplot,[floor(min(ut)),ceil(max(ut))],[0.02,0.02]
plot,ut,fp150,title=eletit,ytitle='Doppler Shift (kHz) [Solid=Pred,
+=Meas]',xtitle=xt
oplot,ut,fd150,psym=1,symsize=0.3
;read,daat1
;plot,ut,sn400,ystyle=16,ytitle='400 CC',title=eletit
;plot,ut,pe400,ystyle=16,ytitle='400 PE',title=eletit
plot,ut,qa400,title=t400,ytitle='Correlation Count at 400
MHz',psym=1,symsize=0.5,xtitle=xt,yrange=[-0.25,1.]
oplot,[floor(min(ut)),ceil(max(ut))],[0.02,0.02]
plot,ut,fp400,title=eletit,ytitle='Doppler Shift (kHz) [Solid =Pred,
+=Meas]',xtitle=xt
oplot,ut,fd400,psym=1,symsize=0.3
; read,sdafff
endfor
end
```

(4) *plot_cidr_tec.pro*

```
pro plot_cidr_tec,WATCH=watch

fname=findfile('CIDR_*.nc',count=fcnt)
for i=0,fcnt-1 do begin
read_ncdf,fname(i),c,/att

;Calculate positions
slat=90.-
atan(sqrt(c.Transmitter_X^2+c.Transmitter_Y^2),c.Transmitter_Z)*!rade
g
slon=atan(c.Transmitter_Y,c.Transmitter_X)*!radeg
glat=c.F_Region_Latitude

ut=c.UniversalTime/3600.
ele=c.Elevation_Angle*!dtor

rflayer=350.+6380.
relayer=100.+6380.
rrec=6380.+c.Receiver_altitude/1000.
rsat=6380.+c.satellite_altitude

obliqf=rflayer/sqrt(rflayer^2-(rrec*cos(ele))^2)
obliqs=rsat/sqrt(rsat^2-(rrec*cos(ele))^2)
oblique=relayer/sqrt((relayer-250.)^2-(rrec*cos(ele))^2)

range=sqrt((c.transmitter_x-c.receiver_x)^2+(c.transmitter_y-
c.receiver_y)^2+(c.transmitter_z-c.receiver_z)^2)

vtec=c.RelativeTEC/obliqf
igood=where(c.qualityflag eq 1)
!p.multi=[0,1,2]
;if (max(c.elevation) gt 35.) then begin
plot,ut,c.RelativeTEC,psym=1,title=fname(i),xtitle='Universal Time
(secs)',ytitle='Relative Slant TEC (TECu)'
;Check for good azimuth angles
print,c.azimuth_at_max_elevation
; if (abs(c.azimuth_at_max_Elevation) lt 30) then begin
```

```

plot,ut,vtec,psym=1,title=fname(i),xtitle='Universal Time
(secs)',ytitle='Relative Vertical TEC (TECu)'
if keyword_set(watch) then read,adfs
plot,glat(igood),vtec(igood),psym=1,title=fname(i),xtitle='Geographic
latitude (deg)',ytitle='Relative Vertical TEC (TECu)'
;endif
plot,glat(igood),c.DeltaTEC(igood),psym=1,xtitle='Geographic latitude
(deg)',ytitle='Change in TEC (TECu)'
if keyword_set(watch) then read,adfs

; Plot the satellite Track on a map of the Earth
!p.multi=0
map_set,/mercator,/continents,limit=[-
30.,0.,60.,80],/isotropic,title=fname(i)
;plots,c.E_Region_Longitude,c.E_Region_Latitude,psym=1
plots,c.F_region_longitude,c.f_region_latitude,psym=2
plots,slon,slat
plots,c.receiver_longitude,c.receiver_latitude,psym=4
if keyword_set(watch) then read,adfs
endfor
end

```

Appendix F

Sample *wintec-p.conf* file:

The configuration file *wintec-p.conf* specifies the options to use when calibrating the TEC:

```
# ----- active options -----  
  
# Estimate the plasmaspheric TEC  
estimate_plasmasphere = 0  
  
# Estimate the receiver bias  
estimate_rx_bias = 1  
  
# Estimate the satellite biases  
estimate_sat_biases = 1  
  
# Force TEC to be non-negative  
non_negative_tec = 1  
  
# Set to 1 for receivers that track the C/A code on L1, set to  
# 0 for receivers that track the P code on L1  
plc1 = 1  
  
# Use the last bias estimates from the Kalman filter (to avoid  
# transients)  
use_last_biases = 1  
  
# Use the last plasmaspheric scaling factor from the Kalman  
# filter (to avoid transients)  
use_last_plasmasphere = 1  
  
# Specify the path to the satellite biases from CODE  
path_to_biases = ./biases  
  
# ----- inactive options -----  
  
# Minimum value of TEC to enforce (if enforce_min_tec > 0)  
# min_tec = 0.0  
  
# Enforce the minimum value of TEC to be min_tec  
# enforce_min_tec = 0  
  
# If TEC is negative but larger than this and non_negative_tec  
# > 0, force minimum TEC to be zero  
# min_tec_threshold = -10.0
```

```
# Minimum number of samples required in a phase connected arc
to keep it
# seglen = 15

# Repair cycle slips
# repair_slips = 1

# Automatically download the satellite biases from CODE
# download = 0

# Restart the Kalman filter from a previously saved state
# restart = 0

# Print debugging information
# debug = 1

# Assumed altitude of the ionospheric penetration point in km
# alt_ipp = 350.

# Altitude at which to compute altitude-adjusted corrected
geomagnetic coordinates (AACGM)
# alt_mag = 0.0

# The elevation mask
# elmask = 20.0

# Discard the TEC if the corresponding S4 exceeds this
threshold
# s4thresh = 1.e6

# Discard the TEC if the corresponding ROTI exceeds this
threshold
# rotithresh = 1.e6

# Discard the TEC this many samples after a cycle slip (since
they are often noisy)
# ntecthresh = 2.0

# Discard the phase connected arc if the running elevation-
weighthed STD between DPR and DCP exceeds this
# rmsthresh = 5.0

# Maximum allowed chi-squared for the polynomial fit to
consider cycle slip repair successful
# max_chisq = 1.0

# Geographic latitude of the station in degrees (only needed
if no *.psn file is available)
# slat = 0.0
```

```
# Geographic longitude of the station in degrees (only needed
if no *.psn file is available)
# slon = 0.0

# Geographic altitude of the station in meters (only needed if
no *.psn file is available)
# salt = 0.0

# Maximum value attained by the Kp index over the past 24
hours (only used if estimate_plasmasphere > 0)
# kpmax = 1.0

# 13 month average sunspot number (only used if
estimate_plasmasphere > 0)
# rbar = 7.9

# The assumed measurement error to be used with the Kalman
filter
# measurement_error = 0.04

# The process noise associated with the bilinear fit to the
vertical-equivalent TEC
# process_noise_fit = 1.e-6

# The process noise associated with the estimate for the
receiver bias
# process_noise_rx_bias = 0.0

# The process noise associated with the estimate for the
satellite biases
# process_noise_sat_biases = 0.0

# The process noise associated with the estimate for the
plasmaspheric scaling factor
# process_noise_plasmasphere = 0.0
```

Appendix G

Sample *S4.conf* file:

The configuration file *s4.conf* specifies the options for plotting the S4 index using the GNU R script *s4.r*:

```
# Name of station (can be left blank)
site =

# Range for the time axis (set equal to -1 to
autoscale)
hr_min = 0
hr_max = 24

# Maximum value of S4 to plot
s4_max = 1.2

# Type of output (bitmap,png,ps,eps)
output_type = bitmap
```

Appendix H

Sample *TEC.conf* file:

The configuration file *tec.conf* specifies the options for plotting the TEC using the GNU R script *tec.r*:

```
# Name of station (can be left blank)
  site =

# Variable to plot (vtec, stec, ptec)
  tec_type = vtec

# Plot versus (ut=ut, mlt=mlt of IPP)
  time_type = mlt

# Units for the time axis (min, hr)
  time_units = "hr"

# Range for the time axis (set equal to -1 to
autoscale)
# hr_min = -1.0
# hr_max = -1.0

# TEC Range (set tec_max=0 to autoscale)
  tec_min = -2
  tec_max = 60

# Type of output (bitmap, png, ps, eps)
  output_type = bitmap

# Plot type (no=all data on one page, yes=separate
pages for each PRN)
  multipage = no

# Detrend option for multipage plots (M=0 for no
detrend, M>0 to subtract a boxcar average of width
2M+1)
  M = 0
```

مستخلص الرسالة

الاضطراب في طبقة الأيونوسفير أثناء العواصف المغناطيسية الأرضية

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تعتبر طبقة الأيونوسفير الخاصة بكوكب الأرض هي منطقة من الغلاف الجوي العلوي مؤينة جزئيا و تمتد من طبقة الميزوسفير - مارة بطبقة الثيرموسفير - وصولا لأرتفاع $\sim 1000\text{Km}$ حيث تندمج في نهاية المطاف مع طبقة الماجنيتوسفير . الاقتران القوى بين طبقة الأيونوسفير و المناطق الكثيفة أدناها و الماجنيتوسفير (المتأثرة بالنشاط الشمسي) أعلاها تجعل من هذه الطبقة الأكثر تغيرا في طبقات الغلاف الجوي. مصادر الاضطراب في طبقة الأيونوسفير تنشأ من التأثيرات الشمسية والنشاط المغناطيسي الأرضي و المناخ الجوي.

دافع واحد لدراسة طبقة الأيونوسفير هو تحسين تقنيات التنبؤ بما يسمى "الطقس الأيونوسفيري" الذي يؤثر على النظم التكنولوجية الفضائية والأرضية المستخدمة في الاتصالات والملاحة والمراقبة والبحوث الأساسية. العواصف المغناطيسية الأرضية يمكن ان تؤدي إلى اضطراب كبير ولا سيما في أنظمة الأقمار الصناعية. يمكن للأضطرابات في اوقات السكون - مثل ما يسمى بال scintillation و الانتشار المضطرب للطبقة - F ان تؤثر على الاتصالات ذات التردد المرتفع ، لا سيما في المناطق ذات خطوط العرض القطبية والاستوائية.

ويتمثل الهدف الرئيسي لهذه الرسالة في قياس ورصد المحتوى الكلي للإلكترونات (Total Electron Content) في طبقة الأيونوسفير ودراسة ظواهر هذه الطبقة فوق جمهورية مصر العربية خلال أيام السكون و الاضطراب، وذلك باستخدام مستقبلات لنظم الملاحة اللاسلكية الفضائية. تم استخدام اثنين من مستقبلات التردد المزدوج في هذه

الدراسة : (1) نظام دوبلر للأستقبال ، مستخدما موجات الراديو عالية و فائقة التردد المرسله من على متن الأقمار الصناعية الأرضية المنخفضة المدار، (2) ونظام تحديد المواقع العالمي، مستخدما موجات الراديو فائقة التردد. تم تثبيت هذه المستقبالات في مركز مراقبة الطقس الفضائي التابع لجامعة حلوان فى جمهورية مصر العربية (الإحداثيات الجغرافية : ° 29،86 شمالا ، ° 31،32 شرقا) خلال العامين 2008 و 2009 على التوالي.

تمت دراسة اربعة عواصف مغناطيسية ارضية (خلال الأعوام من 2008 الى 2010) و بحث آثارها على تغيرات طبقة الأيونوسفير. بالإضافة لذلك ، تمت دراسة حالة واحدة من العواصف الثانوية التابعة للعواصف المغناطيسية الأرضية مستعرضا فيها العلاقة بين العواصف المغناطيسية الأرضية و النبضات المغناطيسية. هذه الدراسات تمت من خلال مساعدة محطات الرصد المغناطيسى (MAGDAS) و التى تم تركيبها فى كلا من الفيوم (الإحداثيات الجغرافية : ° 29.18 ،شمالا، ° 30.50 شرقا) و اسوان (الإحداثيات الجغرافية : ° 23،59 شمالا، ° 32،51 شرقا)، جمهورية مصر العربية .

تتضمن الرسالة ايضا رصد للقمّة الشمالية لما يسمى بال (Equatorial Anomaly) وسلوكها اليومي خلال الأوقات الهادئة / المضطربة "مغناطيسيا". يعتقد ان الانعكاس فى السرعة الأنجرافية العمودية $E \times B$ عند خطوط العرض الأستوائية و تدفق البلازما الهابط من مستويات عليا ، من المصادر الرئيسية لتعزيز (زيادة) المحتوى الكلى للألكترونات اثناء الليل ، و هذه الزيادة تظهر قبل منتصف الليل و تمت دراستها من خلال بيانات الأقمار الصناعية . و اخيرا، تم عمل مسح سنوي لطبقة الأيونوسفير، خلال عام 2010، من أجل عرض التباين الموسمي فى المحتوى الكلى للألكترونات الخاص بطبقة الأيونوسفير.

باسم الله الذي يهداه تتيين الحجج و الآيات ، و بحكمته تكون مخلوقاته دلائل عليه بينات. و الحمد لله الذي جعل الايمان به فطرة تبه العقول ، و حقائق طبيعية لا ينكر دلائلها الا كل معاند مجود.

و الصلاة و السلام على خاتم المرسلين ، المبعوث بالقرآن و السنة هداية للعالمين ، تزداد نضوعا بمر الزمان ، و تراكم علوم الانسان.

وَتِلْكَ الْأَمْثَالُ لِنُصْرِهِمُ لِلنَّاسِ ۖ وَمَا يَعْقِلُهَا إِلَّا الْعَالِمُونَ.

[العنكبوت 43]

و بعد ، فهذا جهد من مقلد يتناول دراسة علمية لجزء من علوم الفضاء، و بين صفحاتها سوف يجد القارئ المتخصص و راغب الاطلاع غاياتهم في زمن اصبحت فيه المعلومات عصب مستقبل الأجيال ، بل و محور الحياة.

اسأل الله تعالى ان يجعله عملا مباركا خالصا ، و لأمتنا العربية المجد و الرفعة،

و الحمد لله أولا و آخرا.

فَتَعَالَى اللَّهُ الْمَلِكُ الْحَقُّ ۖ وَلَا تَعْجَلْ بِالْقُرْآنِ مِنْ قَبْلِ أَنْ يُقْضَىٰ إِلَيْكَ وَحْيُهُ ۗ
وَقُلْ رَبِّ زِدْنِي عِلْمًا.

[طه 114]

دراسة الاضطراب في طبقة الايونوسفير اثناء العواصف المغناطيسية الأرضية .

رسالة مقدمة للأستيفاء الجزئي لمتطلبات الحصول على درجة الماجستير في
العلوم (تخصص نوية)
مقدمة من:

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2011